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Lessons learned from the quantification of the pathways

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RAINFOREST PROJECT SUMMARY

Co-produced transformative knowledge to accelerate change for biodiversity

Food and biomass production systems are among the most prominent drivers of biodiversity loss worldwide. Halting and reversing the loss of biodiversity therefore requires transformative change of food and biomass systems, addressing the nexus of agricultural production, processing and transport, retailing, consumer preferences and diets, as well as investment, climate action and ecosystem conservation and restoration. The RAINFOREST project will contribute to enabling, upscaling and accelerating transformative change to reduce biodiversity impacts of major food and biomass value chains. Together with stakeholders, we will co-develop and evaluate just and viable transformative change pathways and interventions. We will identify stakeholder preferences for a range of policy and technology-based solutions, as well as governance enablers, for more sustainable food and biomass value chains. We will then evaluate these pathways and solutions using a novel combination of integrated assessment modeling, input-output modeling and life cycle assessment, based on case studies in various stages of the nexus, at different spatial scales and organizational levels. This coproduction approach enables the identification and evaluation of just and viable transformative change leverage points, levers and their impacts for conserving biodiversity (SDGs 12, 14-15) that minimize trade-offs with targets related to climate (SDG13) and socioeconomic developments (SDGs 1-3). We will elucidate leverage points, impacts, and obstacles for transformative change and provide concrete and actionable recommendations for transformative change for consumers, producers, investors, and policymakers.

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Introduction

There is growing consensus that transformative change is needed to achieve futures in which biodiversity, climate and socio-economic goals agreed under UN conventions (Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework, Paris Agreement and Sustainable Development Goals) are met.

However, there is limited understanding of what transformative change entails for food and biomass value chains, and how this could differ based on alternative value perspectives about justice and human-nature relationships.

Following recommendations from the IPBES Transformative Change assessment, the RAINFOREST project addressed this gap by developing and quantifying the “Value-explicit transformative and equitable pathways in Food and Biomass Systems” (VITAL-Paths-Food pathways), a set of three plausible and value coherent pathways designed to meet global biodiversity, climate and human well-being goals, and reflecting contrasted views about justice and nature.

By supporting a more transparent account of the values underpinning pathways of transformative change and their impacts for multiple competing value perspectives, this work is expected to help overcome existing tensions about ambitious and fair collective action in food and biomass value chains.

This report documents the methodological approach to the quantification of the VITAL-Paths-Food pathways, the analyses of the resulting projections in terms of efforts and impacts, and the lessons learned for transformative change in European food and biomass systems within the global context.

The pathways and the quantification approach

The three VITAL-Paths-Food pathways integrate distinct interventions across the food and biomass system, based on alternative perspectives on nature and justice:

- The Global Sustainability Orchestration (GSO) pathway advocates high levels of intergovernmental cooperation, where states empower international organizations to coordinate global production, redistribute resources, and protect nature's intrinsic value to simultaneously address biodiversity loss, climate change, and social inequality.
- The International Market-driven Innovation (IMI) pathway posits that transformative change is achieved through a market-led, "green-growth" approach where permissive regulations and technological innovation enable private actors to decouple economic development from biodiversity loss in pursuit of long-term profitability.
- The Local Commons Stewardship (LCS) pathway focuses on community-led conservation where authority is devolved to local, democratic institutions that leverage indigenous and local knowledge to manage landscapes as integrated, needs-based social-ecological systems.

We parameterized the pathways in the GLOBIOM land use model, to generate projections of various indicators from 2020 to 2030 and 2050, at the level of 13 world regions. A counterfactual business-as-usual (BAU) scenario, as well as additional decomposition scenarios were also generated.

We analyzed how the projected efforts and impacts vary across pathways, actors and regions, with a focus on Europe within a global context. Efforts are defined as trends in indirect drivers of biodiversity loss (such as dietary preferences or restoration), while impacts are defined as trends in drivers of biodiversity loss (such as land use or pollution), in biodiversity, and in other socio-economic indicators (such as value of production, or health impacts from food consumption).

The feedback on preliminary results gathered from stakeholders in a dedicated workshop informed methodological choices and result interpretation and helped identify lessons learned. The final projections of indicators are publicly available on Zenodo (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18788047>).

Key results and lessons learned

Multiple transformative change trajectories are possible and need to be explored

While pointing to the need for a high level of transparency and detail, stakeholders expressed a high interest in model and scenario applications that can explore the complexities of plural, value-explicit, pathways of transformative change.

We found that differences in efforts across regions (for a given pathway) and across pathways (for a given region) are often shaped by the complex interaction of value perspectives and region characteristics such as the extent of degraded agricultural land, the conservation value of remaining natural ecosystems, or levels of consumption. Within a pathway, value perspectives often entailed multiple, and at times conflicting, narrative elements for a given type of efforts.

We also found that the relation between efforts and impacts is often contextual, and that, even for pathways with contrasted value perspectives, differences can be limited by normative assumptions common to all pathways (e.g., a net increase in ecosystem integrity must be achieved).

Europe in a global context: selected results

- Efforts for protected area expansion represented in Europe a lower share of total land than at global scale. This is due to comparatively higher coverage in 2020, lower conservation and carbon value natural ecosystems. Alternative perspectives about human-nature relationships however lead to varying shares of strict protection.
- Efforts for additional restoration of degraded agricultural land through sustainable agricultural practices (23-68 million ha) often went well beyond allocated requirements to meet KMGBF Target 2 (4-29 million ha), due to the required contributions to climate mitigation and pollution reduction objectives.
- Efforts for additional restoration of degraded agricultural land through conversion to nature-friendly afforestation was highest for the LCS pathway (23 million ha), despite a preference for the restoration through sustainable agricultural practices related to a higher weight of cultural over intrinsic nature values. This is due to concomitant large amount of land freed from agriculture through a sufficiency-based approach to sustainable consumption.

- Impacts in Europe were often most affected by demand-side efforts, with a 68% (resp. 19%) reduction in livestock product consumption achieved for the LCS (resp. GSO) pathway as compared to the BAU by 2050. This led to benefits for biodiversity and climate (similarly to most World regions) and health impacts from food consumption (comparable to World level in relative terms), but negative impacts on the value of agricultural production (comparable to or - for LCS - worse than at global level), despite systematic gains in the value of production per hectare of cropland when including potential revenues from carbon sequestration in agricultural soils.
- Even though outcomes at global scale were sometimes comparable due to the normative assumptions of the pathways, the efforts, impacts and the relation between efforts and outcomes varied significantly at regional level. For example, as illustrated in the below figure, a relatively similar level of reduction was achieved for all pathways in Europe by 2050 as compared to the BAU scenario in terms of land occupation-related terrestrial biodiversity impacts embedded in the consumption of agricultural products. Yet, the reduction is primarily achieved through reducing imported impacts in IMI, and through reducing domestic impacts in LCS & GSO. And reduced domestic impacts are primarily achieved through demand-side efforts in LCS, and through conservation efforts in GSO.

Projection of the imported, domestic and total impacts of climate mitigation, conservation, demand-side, supply-side, trade and combined efforts in each pathway (GSO, IMI, LCS) on the terrestrial biodiversity land occupation impacts embedded in the consumption of agricultural products in Europe by 2050, as compared to the BAU counterfactual scenario

Needs for future research

Even though variable across pathways in amplitude and regional patterns, we projected a systematic downsizing of agricultural activities in terms of physical volume and value of production in pathways as compared to the BAU scenario, associated to sustainable consumption efforts towards environmental but also human health objectives.

Stakeholders considered this as a relatively likely outcome and raised the need to better explore potential options to manage related impacts, as an important pre-requisite for the transition to occur. They also pointed to a potential bias in the modeling through the lack of inclusion of further degradation of agricultural land and potential consequences for agricultural producers, which might lead to an overly pessimistic impact of the pathways for agricultural producers.

They also pointed to a more general limited capacity of the modeling toolbox to deal with multiple aspects relevant to the farm-scale economic impacts of the transition, such as impacts on input and machinery costs, access to price premiums, changes in subsidies and capital and skill requirements. Adequately covering these aspects needs additional model development.

Additional work could also explore novel pathways, designed to explore how transformation unfolds dynamically in the real-world. This means more dynamic pathways, featuring actions and reactions that rest on globally less coherent and temporally dynamic value perspectives across value chain actors. This requires additional research efforts, through innovative combinations of modeling and social sciences, in a participatory research setting.

1. INTRODUCTION

As part of the RAINFOREST project, a novel set of pathways for transformative change in food and biomass supply chains towards nature-, climate- and people-positive futures was generated: the Value-explicit transformative and equitable pathways in Food and Biomass Systems (VITAL-Paths-Food pathways). The pathways were designed to explore what the transition to such futures might look like, based on identified common groupings about value perspectives on human-nature relationships, environmental justice and just societal organizations.

First, detailed scenario narratives for these pathways were co-designed, as described in RAINFOREST deliverable D1.2 (Woodhouse et al., 2024). Then, cross-scale target translation tools were used to generate alternative distributions of country-level targets for three 2030 action targets from the Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework (KMGBF), consistent with the global ambition level for each target, but differentiated in the distribution of efforts across countries (see D1.2, Woodhouse et al., 2024, and D1.3, Nowak et al., 2025).

Vital-Paths-Food Narratives

International Market Innovation

The IMI pathway is a market-led transition model that leverages green-growth, technological innovation, and trade liberalization to decouple economic development from environmental degradation. Rooted in a utilitarian framework with an instrumentalist value of nature, it prioritizes "land-sparing" through agricultural and forestry intensification, using precision technologies and high-yield plantations to maximize spatial efficiency, thereby freeing up marginal lands for restoration and protected areas. Governance in this scenario relies on a permissive regulatory environment where the private sector takes the lead, utilising market-based instruments like biodiversity offsetting, Payments for Ecosystem Services (PES), and carbon credit markets to internalize ecological externalities. While consumption levels remain high, sustainability is pursued through product substitution and efficiency gains rather than lifestyle shifts, allowing globalized value chains to redistribute resources according to marginal utility while meeting international conservation targets cost-effectively.

Global Environmental Orchestration

The GSO pathway represents a top-down, expert-led transition that prioritises the intrinsic value of nature and prioritarian distributive justice through expansive international cooperation. Central to this model is the expansion of large, strictly protected, and interconnected wilderness areas, supported by a "land-sparing" approach that combines sustainable agricultural intensification with state-mandated shifts in consumption, such as the adoption of plant-based diets and the reduction of North-South inequalities. Global governance institutions play a decisive role in coordinating production, redistributing resources, and facilitating technology transfers to the Global South, ensuring that conservation efforts do not impede poverty alleviation. By rejecting market-based offsetting in favor of direct regulation, price controls, and reparative payments, the GSO pathway seeks to harmonize ecological integrity with a moral commitment to global equity.

Local Cooperation & Stewardship

The LCS pathway focuses on the devolution of power to the local level, promoting a "land-sharing" model where biodiversity is integrated into managed landscapes rather than separated from them. Underpinned by degrowth and egalitarian principles with a relational value of nature, this pathway prioritises community-led governance, needs-based consumption, and agroecological farming practices that utilise traditional and indigenous knowledge. Global trade is significantly reduced in favor of shortened, local supply chains and circular economies, while conservation goals are met through multifunctional "Protected Landscapes" and OECMs that respect the sovereignty of Indigenous Peoples and Local Communities (IPLCs). Ultimately, LCS seeks a just transition by fostering deep relational values with nature, replacing the pursuit of economic growth with local autonomy and a "minimum-maximum" consumption window that ensures global equity within planetary boundaries.

Finally, as described in this deliverable, the GLOBIOM model (Havlík et al., 2014; IBF-IIASA, 2023) from the RAINFOREST toolbox (see deliverable D2.2, Kuipers et al., 2025) was used to generate a broader quantitative analysis of the distribution of efforts and impacts in these pathways, contrasted with a business-as-usual future scenario. The analysis relies on model-based projections from 2020 to 2030 and 2050 of indicators describing indirect and direct drivers of biodiversity change, biodiversity and ecosystem services outcomes, and socioeconomic outcomes in various world regions (with a focus on Europe, other OECD countries and non-OECD countries in this deliverable), with a differentiation of the crop and livestock sectors, and in some cases among crop production systems (e.g., conventional vs organic vs precision-farming crop production systems). Some of the methodological choices in model developments and quantitative pathway analysis, as well as lessons learned, were discussed with stakeholders during online workshops.

The quantitative projections of the drivers and impacts associated with the VITAL-Paths-Food, as well as the analysis of the distribution of efforts and impacts it enables, is expected to support transformative change through facilitating deliberations about what the way forward could look like according to different perspectives, and reaching an improved understanding of leverage points, impacts, and obstacles for transformative change.

In this deliverable, we provide:

1. A summary of the methodological approach to generate quantitative projections, including the implementation of the scenario narratives in the model, the scenario ensemble for which quantitative projections were generated, the various indicators quantified, and the inclusion of stakeholder feedback
2. An analysis of the distribution of efforts and impacts across regions and actors, as estimated by the model.
3. A discussion of limitations, key insights from the results, and lessons learned for transformative change in food and biomass value chains.

2. METHODOLOGICAL APPROACH

2.1 Objectives and overall approach

The main objectives of the pathway quantification task in WP5 were the following:

- Use the integrated assessment modelling tool from the RAINFOREST model toolbox (see Kuipers et al., 2025) to translate the VITAL-Paths-Food scenario narratives into quantitative, spatially- and temporally-explicit, future projections of indicators describing indirect and direct drivers of biodiversity change, biodiversity and ecosystem services outcomes, and socioeconomic outcomes at various geographic scales, time horizons and sectoral levels of detail.
- Use these quantitative projections to provide evidence on how transformative change in the nexus can be mobilized to reach ambitious targets for biodiversity and climate in a fair and viable manner, and how various sectors, regions and actors might be affected. The analysis presented in this deliverable focused primarily on the following questions:
 - For each pathway, what level of effort in various intervention domains is needed to reach nature-, climate- and people goals, and how are those efforts distributed between regions?
 - For each pathway, what are the expected impacts on consumers, producers and the environment, how do those differ across regions and pathways, and how do those relate to different interventions?
- Derive key lessons about leverage points, impacts, and obstacles for transformative change, and provide recommendations for transformative change for consumers, producers, investors, and policymakers.

This deliverable represents an application of one of the common methods mobilized in global change research, based on the use of model and scenarios to quantitatively explore plural target-seeking scenarios, designed to reach normative targets (see e.g., Figure SPM.2 in IPBES, 2016). It is innovative in three aspects. Firstly, it addresses a relatively novel type of normative target space, termed “nature-, climate- and people-positive future” and defined by the joint achievement

of climate, biodiversity and social goals from the sustainable development agenda, the Paris Agreement, and the Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework. For example, these target spaces were previously often explored in isolation by global change research. Secondly, it focuses on the notion of transformative change, defined by IPBES as “a fundamental, system-wide reorganization across technological, economic, and social factors—including paradigms, goals, and values—needed to address the root causes of nature’s decline” (IPBES, 2019). In contrast, for example, scenario and model applications on biodiversity often considered the role of indirect drivers. Thirdly, our application is also innovative by explicitly considering a diversity of pathways that reflect alternative value perspectives human-nature relationships and equity, which are increasingly recognized as a pre-requisite for enabling transformative change (Obura et al., 2023). Altogether, these innovations are an important step forward for global change research.

As detailed in the next sections, our approach entails the following methodological steps:

1. Initial pathway implementation: translating the VITAL-Paths-Food pathway & BAU scenario narratives about transformative change action into contrasted model parameters for each of the three pathways, as well as for a business-as-usual scenario.
2. Projections of quantitative indicators: running the modeling framework to generate projections for a range of environmental and socio-economic indicators, at first for the initial pathway implementation.
3. Pathway implementation adjustments to reach the target space: assessing the initial pathway projections for multiple indicators against a defined set of targets characterizing the end point that all three VITAL-Paths-Food pathways are expected to reach, and iteratively adjust scenario parameters to ensure the target space is reached.
4. Analysis conceptualization and operationalization to answer the research questions: elicit what combinations of scenarios (including the business-as-usual and VITAL-Paths-Food scenarios, but also variants of those) are needed, how the projections for multiple indicators and scenarios will be interpreted, and execute the model simulations and indicator analysis.

5. Lessons learned and recommendation formulation: synthesizing results of the analysis and formulating recommendations for transformative change.

As further specified in the next sections, parts of these methodological steps were discussed with stakeholders through online workshops, and lead to specific adjustments in methodological details, as well as specific considerations for result interpretation and recommendation formulations.

2.2 Initial pathway implementation

Four scenarios were quantified with the integrated modeling framework: the three VITAL-Paths-Food pathways developed in WP1, alongside a counterfactual Business-as-Usual (BAU) scenario. The BAU counterfactual scenario is a common type of scenario, and is described here with limited details, while the implementation of the VITAL-Paths-Food pathways are described in more details, including material in the appendix.

BAU scenario

The BAU scenario represents a continuation of historical trends and serves as a counterfactual against which transformative pathways are evaluated. Key model drivers, including population and GDP, dietary preferences, food waste and losses, trade costs, technological change, protection and restoration policies, and within-country inequalities in food consumption, are assumed to follow trajectories consistent with the Shared Socioeconomic Pathway SSP2 (“Middle of the Road”; Popp et al., 2017). A large literature is available to understand how this scenario was designed and used in the community (O’Neill et al., 2014, 2020), how it was parameterized in GLOBIOM (e.g., Havlík et al., 2014; Valin et al., 2013, 2014) and additional references in IBF-IIASA (2023)), what the projected outcomes look like and how they compare to that of other models for the same scenario (e.g., (Leclère et al., 2020; Popp et al., 2017; Schmitz et al., 2014; Stehfest et al., 2019)). To facilitate the understanding of how the parameterization of the VITAL-Paths-Food scenarios differ from that of the BAU scenario, SSP2 assumptions are recalled when presenting the pathway assumptions below.

Initial implementation of the VITAL-Paths-Food pathways

The three pathways (International Market Innovation IMI, Global Sustainability

Orchestration GSO, Local Commons Stewardship LCS) are expected to all reach a similar end point by 2050: the society is on track to avoid the climate and biodiversity crisis, while significant progress towards socio-economic goals such as reducing inequality and hunger. These outcomes depart significantly from what might be expected from a Business-as-usual (BAU) pathway, in which historical trends are prolonged, with at best moderate progress towards socio-economic goals and further exacerbation of the biodiversity and climate crisis. The focus on value-explicit and plural pathways recognizes that there might be alternative ways to reach the target space, that reflect different values and perspectives about human-nature relationships and justice.

Each pathway is operationalized through deviations from BAU assumptions in selected model parameters, reflecting differences in dominant intervention strategies. These include adjustments to many aspects: demand-side factors (e.g., dietary preferences and food waste), conservation measures (e.g., protected area expansion and ecosystem restoration), supply-side efficiency (e.g., yield, nutrient and water use efficiency), climate mitigation policies (e.g., carbon price and biomass demand), and trade dynamics (e.g., trade costs, border adjustment mechanisms). The main adjustments across aspects and pathways are presented in *Table 1*, while more detailed tables (*App-Table 1* to

App-Table 5) are provided in appendix for each aspect.

Table 1: Summary of scenario assumptions (Baseline & deviations from baseline in the VITAL-Paths Food)

Scenario	Demand	Supply	Conservation & restoration	Climate mitigation	Trade regulation
BAU - Business-as-usual	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Moderate consumption growth and increasing share of livestock products in diet, following projected income growth and historical relationship between income level and dietary preferences - No reduction in consumption waste - Constant level of within-country inequalities across the human population in food energetic intake 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Annual yield growth from 0.6% in OECD, 1% in NonOECD. - Constant pesticides application rates - Baseline N/P use efficiency trends: progress towards sustainable use efficiency targets by 2050, only partially met for non-OECD countries, see (Chang et al., 2021) - Roundwood short rotation plantations do not expand beyond 2020 (energy short rotation plantations expansion allowed over abandoned agricultural land and, to some extent, non-forest natural and semi-natural land) - Medium reductions in losses, following SSP2 (-15% for pulses and oilseeds and -20% for dairy by 2050) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 17% of protected area (constant to 2020 levels) - No restoration target 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - No carbon price - Constant biomass bioenergy demand - Global deforestation rate declining by 30% (resp. 45%) from 2020 to 2030 (resp. 2050) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Trade costs following SSP2 (moderate further reduction in trade costs globally) - No biodiversity border adjustment mechanisms

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<p>IMI - International Market Innovation</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - SSP2 Diet with 33% substitution of animal products by Novel-Plant Based Alternatives (NPBA) - Within-country inequalities in food energetic intake reduced by 10% by 2050 - Circular economy measures in forest supply chains, with increased re-use and recycling and lower use of secondary products for energy - 35% reduction in consumer waste by 2050 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Highest yield growth: -0.5% in OECD, 1.3% in non-OECD annual increase, enabled by technology improvements - Convergence towards sustainable nutrient efficiency targets and improvement of manure recycling by 2030 - High risk pesticides application rates reduced in 2030 - Expansion of roundwood short rotation plantations allowed (similar to BAU rules for energy short rotation plantations) - 75% supply side losses reduction by 2050 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 30% protected areas by 2030, cost effectiveness distribution - Restoration of 30% of degraded land by 2030, 50% by 2050, geographical distribution by cost effectiveness - Restoration achieved through transitions to unmanaged land (60%) - Zero net forest loss has to be achieved globally from 2030 onwards (with compensation between deforestation and restoration allowed across regions) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Higher carbon price (up to 135.54 USD/t CO2 in 2050) - Higher biomass demand for energy (doubling by 2100) and increase in construction demand (90% of buildings for new urban population made of wood) - Global deforestation rate declining by 50% in 2030, 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Higher reduction in trade costs (similar to SSP1 by 2050, but faster reduction) - Biodiversity border adjustment tax applied to all agricultural products, with high tax value
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					by 75% in 2050	
GSO - Global Sustainability Orchestration	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Half progress to Eat Lancet 2 diet by 2050, 25% of meat consumption substituted by NBPA - 85% reduction of food waste by 2050 - Within-country inequalities in food energetic intake reduced by 30% by 2050 - Circular economy measures in forest supply chains, with increased re-use and recycling and lower use of secondary products for energy 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Stable OECD yields until 2050 (0.2% annual increase); moderate non-OECD increases (1.1% annual increase) - Convergence towards high NUE and improvements of manure recycling by 2030 - High risk pesticides application rates reduced in 2030 - 50% reduction of food loss by 2050 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 30% protected areas by 2030, environmental capacity distribution - Restoration of 30% of degraded land by 2030, 50% by 2050, environmental capacity distribution of target - Restoration mainly achieved through transitions to unmanaged land (60%) - Zero absolute forest loss has to be achieved globally from 2040 onwards (90% reduction in deforestation rate by 2030, 100% after) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Medium carbon price (up to 84.71 USD/t CO2 in 2050) - Half of IMI biomass demand increase for energy and construction - Global deforestation rate declining by 90% in 2030, 100% in 2050 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Trade costs following SSP2 - Biodiversity border adjustment tax applied to agricultural products (e.g., bovine meat, soya- and oil palm-based products, sugarcane), with high tax value 	

D5.3 – Lessons learned from the quantification of the pathways

LCS - Local Commons Stewardship	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Full adoption of Eat Lancet 2 Diet by 2070; no NBPA - 80% reduction of food waste by 2050 - Within-country inequalities in food energetic intake reduced by 50% by 2050 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Growth focused in low-yield systems; declining/stable yields in OECD (-0.1%); lowest gains in non-OECD (1% annual increase) - Convergence towards high NUE and improvement of manure recycling by 2050 - 70% reduction of food loss by 2050 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 30% protected areas by 2030, distributed equally - Restoration of 30% of degraded land by 2030, 50% by 2050, equal distribution - Restoration target mainly achieved through deintensification (60%) - Zero net forest loss has to be achieved regionally from 2030 onwards (with compensation between deforestation and restoration allowed within regions, but not across) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Low carbon price (up to 30.245 USD/t CO2 in 2050) - Global deforestation rate declining by 67% in 2030, 90% in 2050 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Trade costs following SSP2 with penalized intercontinental trade - No biodiversity border adjustment tax
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2.3 Projections of quantitative indicators

The GLOBIOM model is a partial equilibrium model of the agricultural, forestry and bioenergy sectors (IBF-IIASA, 2023). It endogenously models resource use and production activities with a gridded spatial resolution of up to 5 arcminutes, and the production, trade, processing and consumption of agricultural products at the level of 59 world economic regions. It is calibrated for the year 2000 and solves recursively for each scenario with a 10-year time step, up to the year 2100. From one time step to another, model input parameters are adjusted from the outcome simulated previous time step (e.g., land use and land cover) and exogenous assumptions (e.g., population, dietary preferences or yield trends). For each time step, model input parameters are adjusted to reflect historical trends until 2020, and scenario-specific future assumptions afterwards. From the model projections, multiple indicators can be produced, such as commodity-level market variables (production, bilateral trade flows, processing, consumption, prices) and derived indicators (such as number of people at risk of hunger) at the regional level, as well as indicators related to resource use variables such as land cover, land use, land management and their change, or agricultural soil nitrogen budgets and GHG emissions from agricultural soils and livestock activities, either at the gridded level or re-aggregated to the regional level.

As described in D2.2 (Kuipers et al., 2025), selected model developments were conducted in the project to improve the modeling of specific transformative change related interventions (e.g., protection, restoration, evolution of dietary preferences, trade regulation) and the estimation of environmental as well as socio-economic impacts (e.g., nutrient, pesticide and labor inputs, health impacts from food consumption, biodiversity impacts on terrestrial, freshwater and marine ecosystems from agricultural land use, GHG emissions and pollution losses).

To provide quantification to the VITAL-Paths-Food pathways, we ran the model to the year 2050, and extracted multiple indicators derived from the model outputs, as detailed in *Table 2*. These cover indirect (e.g., consumption levels) and direct (e.g., land use change) drivers of biodiversity loss, as well as biodiversity impacts (e.g., species extinction risks in terrestrial, freshwater and marine ecosystems from agricultural activities, changes in the compositional integrity of local communities

in terrestrial ecosystems from climate and land use change), other indicators related to environmental impacts (e.g., nitrogen and phosphorus surplus, pesticide inputs) and socio-economic impacts (e.g., prices, revenue from crop and livestock activities, health impacts from food consumption, number of people at risk of hunger).

Table 2: Definition of indicators quantified by the GLOBIOM model for the various scenarios presented in this deliverable. All indicators are available with a 10-year time step from 2020 to 2050, and at three levels of spatial resolution (thirteen AGMIP regions, EUR vs other OECD countries vs non-OECD countries, World).

Indicator name	Indicator unit	Categories	Description
LAND	Million hectares	Cropland, Pasture, Forest, Afforested land, Abandoned land, Natural land, Plantation	Area allocated to each land use category
CROPLAND_DYN	Million hectares	-	Harvested area allocated to the 18 crops dynamically represented in the model
LUM_AGR	Million hectares	Main categories: Conventional, organic, precision farming, silvopasture. Sub-categories: - Conventional- Biochar, other crop measures - All: Soil organic carbon measures.	Physical area allocated within crop and grassland to various management systems. Soil organic carbon measures can come on top of other management systems, including organic and precision farming
LUM_FOREST	Million hectares	Natural forest, close to nature or unharvested, Natural forest, re/afforestation, Seminatural forest Multifunctional, Seminatural Forest Production oriented, Short rotation plantations	Physical area allocated to various forest management types and short rotation plantations (for energy and roundwood)
PROD	Million tons	Crop products (CRP),	Production volume

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	fresh matter	livestock products (LSP)	
CONS	Million tons fresh matter	Crop products (CRP), livestock products (LSP)	Consumption volume
NETT	Million tons fresh matter	Crop products (CRP), livestock products (LSP)	Net trade (= exports - imports) volume
CALO	kg/cap/day	Crop products (CRP), livestock products (LSP)	Per capita volume of food consumed (in energetic content), on average within a product group
FLWT	Kg/cap/yr (fresh matter)	Food wasted as consumer (WAST) or lost during processing (LOSS)	Per capita volume of food loss and waste
LPRT	Million hectares	Strict/Managed protection, and per land use types: Cropland, Pasture, Forest, Natural land, Plantation	Protected land, split by protection and land use type
LRST	Million hectares	Type 1 (restoration of degraded agricultural land into unmanaged land), Type 2 (restoration of degraded agricultural land into better condition agricultural land)	Total restoration land, split by type
YILD	ton dry matter /ha	-	Average yield over the 18 crops dynamically represented in the model
XPRP	USD/t	Crop products (CRP), livestock products (LSP)	Average producer price within each product group
CTAX	USD/tCO ₂ eq	-	Value of the applied carbon price (subsidy to carbon removals in agricultural soils, tax to N ₂ O, CH ₄ and CO ₂ emissions from agriculture and from land use change)
MSAP	%	Climate change, Land use, Total	Change in biodiversity intactness (MSA loss) split by

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MSAV			pressure based on GLOBIO
LCFE	PDF.y	Climate change,	Land Global species loss impacts on
LCME		Occupation,	Land terrestrial (LCTE), freshwater
LCTE		transformation,	(LCFE) and marine (LCME)
		Ecotoxicity,	ecosystems from pressures in a
		Eutrophication,	region, split by pressure
		stress	
EMIS	Mt CO2eq	Land use change (LUC), Soil	Agriculture, Forestry and other
		organic carbon measures	Land Use (AFOLU) GHG
		(SOC), Crop & livestock	emissions, split by source
		emissions (CRP), Foret	
		Management (FORM)	
NUT_INPUT	Million t N, P	Nitrogen, Phosphorus	Nutrient inputs (incl.
			deposition, fixation, manure
			and fertilizer) to croplands
NUT_SURPLUS	Million t N, P	Nitrogen, Phosphorus	Nutrient surplus (defined as
			inputs - outputs) in croplands
PEST_INPUT	Million t	-	Total pesticide application to
			the 18 crops dynamically
			represented in the model,
			based on PEST-CHEMGRID (20
			most prevalent active
			ingredients for 4 dominant
			crops and 6 aggregated crop
			classes), FAOSTAT and JRC data
			(FAOSTAT, 2021; Maggi et al.,
			2019; Udias et al., 2023)
UNDN	Million pers	-	Number of people at risk of
			undernourishment
YLL	Million pers	-	Years of life loss through diet-
			related diseases, based on the
			Global Burden of Disease
FPILCONS,	Million	Imported, Domestic	Footprint embedded in the
FPIButeoCONS	hectares, PDF.y		consumption agricultural
			products, in terms of
			agricultural land (FPILCONS, in
			1000 ha, based on pasture +

				cropland for the 18 crops dynamically represented in the model) and land occupation-related global species loss in terrestrial ecosystems (FPIButeoCONS, in PDF.y, based on cSAR_US16, (Leclère et al., 2020))
ISLA	Million workers	Conventional, Precision farming	Organic,	Crop employment per type of farm, for the 18 crops dynamically represented in the model
BIOM	Million m3/yr	Energy By-Products, Energy Crop residues, Energy Forest & SRP, Energy recycled products, Material Forest & SRP, Material Recycled products		Ligno-cellulosic biomass use, split by end use type and source
CV	-	-		Coefficient of variation of the distribution across the human population in energetic food intake
POPT	Million pers	-		Total population (identical across all scenarios, following SSP2 trends)

All indicators were aggregated to the level of the 13 AGMIP regions (footnote AGMIP region), and the analysis also makes use of two additional aggregation levels (EUR vs NAM-ANZ countries vs ROW; World). These indicator projections, with a 10-year time step over time 2010-2050 period and at the level of AGMIP regions are publicly available as a csv file on zenodo (DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.18310955), together with the R script needed to generate the figures from this deliverable.

Some of the indicators quantified were added based on the feedback collected from stakeholders during an online workshop (see App-Table 6), to better reflect their understanding of what effects and indicators maybe important to understand

better the impacts of cropland restoration to reduce pollution from crop activities. This includes for example the potential revenue from soil organic carbon in agricultural soils, the area of various types of cropland restoration measures adopted and the yield impacts over various types of cropland (conventional farming, precision farming, organic farming). Several indicators mentioned by the stakeholders as important could not be included, as they are currently not quantified in the modeling framework. This includes, for example, the impact of cropland restoration measures on farm cost structure, and, in particular, input and capital expenditures. Similarly, the availability of information to consumers about the environmental impacts of various products, the willingness of consumers to pay a higher price for sustainable products, the value of the price premium paid by consumers for products generated from cropland in which restoration measures are adopted, and the share of it reaching the producers, were all mentioned as important dimensions to consider, but can currently not be quantified by the model.

It should also be noted that, while Task 5.2 RAINFOREST initially proposed to quantify the pathways with projections up to 2070, we decided to limit the analysis to 2050. As mentioned in a latter subsection, we focus the analysis to 2030 as short-term time horizon, and 2050 as long-term time horizon. While extending the projections and the analysis to 2070 might provide the opportunity to explore additional questions (e.g., potential for synergies and trade-off between climate and biodiversity action in the second part of the 21st century), this would go beyond the ambition to provide recommendation on transformative change in the coming decades, and would likely need scenario extensions specifically designed to explore these aspects.

Similarly, while gridded projections were generated by the model and used for estimating many of the indicators reported and analyzed at a coarser spatial resolution, we do not report gridded projections. As done in Leclère et al. (2020), the reporting of gridded projections is usually done at a finer spatial resolution than that of the model, to enable the coupling to complex biodiversity models. This relies on the use of a downscaling algorithm, that however is not tailored to the refined thematic legend adopted in RAINFOREST (e.g., cropland and forest management restoration options). This downscaling algorithm also does not yet consider the additional variables used to estimate biodiversity impacts in this deliverable, such

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as nitrogen and phosphorus losses or pesticide input. In addition, the biodiversity impact quantification methods (relying on LC-IMPACT and GLOBIO) do not require downscaling (see RAINFOREST deliverable D2.2, Kuipers et al., 2025).

2.4 Pathway implementation adjustments to reach the target space

The VITAL-Paths-Food are normative pathways, that are assumed to reach a specific end-point by 2050 when it comes to progress towards climate, biodiversity and socio-economic goals. To finalize the implementation of these pathways in the model, we therefore ensured that the projected outcomes were compatible with that normative assumption. We proceeded in two steps:

1. First, a set of global and EU targets were defined for specific environmental and socio-economic indicators in 2030 and 2050 (see *Table 3*). These targets were broadly aligned with the target space of the Sustainable Development Pathways (SDPs, Van Vuuren et al., 2022), as well as outcome and action targets at global (e.g., Paris Agreement, KMGBF Goals and targets) and EU (EU F2F, EU Climate Law, EU Nature restoration law and EU Biodiversity strategy) scale (see also targets reviewed in RAINFOREST deliverable D1.1, Leclere et al., 2024). Some action targets are not quantified and are therefore treated as indicative only (e.g. agricultural land under KMGBF Target 10; land footprint under KMGBF Target 16); others require interpretation (e.g. Halving food waste in KMGBF Target 16 has been interpreted here as including both processing and consumption waste, but could be interpreted as only consumption waste, depending on definition; SDG2 “End hunger” is interpreted as reaching a prevalence of undernourishment below 5%); lastly, certain targets are considered only for the portion of the impacts covered in GLOBIOM, implicitly assuming a proportional distribution of the efforts (e.g. for SDG3.4 only diet-related noncommunicable diseases are included; for pesticide and nutrient reduction, only pollution on croplands is considered).
2. Then, for the relevant indicators, the outcomes projected with the initial parameterization of each pathway to the targets. A gap was apparent for all three pathways in terms of nutrient losses, pesticide risk as well as food loss and waste reduction. Selected pathway implementation parameters were adjusted so that the simulated outcomes reach the target space. To

maintain consistency with the difference across pathways in dominant trends (e.g., higher rate of technological change might be assumed for IMI, vs higher level of reduction of material demand above sufficiency standards for LCS), different parameters are adjusted in each scenario, as indicated by the *Table 4* below.

Table 5 and Table 6 below present the outcome of the parametrization of the pathways, in terms of the different targets in Table 3, at the global level as well as for European targets, after the adjustments presented in Table 4. Globally, majority of outcome goals and action targets are achieved, with some variation across pathways (see *Table 5* below). Climate, health and biodiversity are further improved than initially targeted in LCS primarily, while pollution and restoration targets are better in IMI and GSO. IMI remains slightly below targets for health, while LCS remains slightly below targets for the reduction of pollution risk to ecosystems (despite pollution reduction targets being met, indicating that those might be insufficient). In all pathways, restored areas substantially exceed the set targets, particularly in high carbon price scenarios. This might reflect an underestimation of the baseline extent of agricultural degraded land or suggest that the target itself may not be sufficiently ambitious. Lastly, global GHG emissions do not reach net zero in any scenario but are reduced by 67% to 85% compared to 1990 levels. This reflects mainly the trajectories of the Engage scenarios chosen for industrial emissions, while global mean temperature increase remains below +2°C above pre-industrial levels.

At the European level, most targets are reached as well. However, despite substantial global restoration efforts, the EU Nature Restoration Law objective of restoring all degraded land by 2050 is not fully achieved, particularly in lower carbon price scenarios such as LCS. While the EU waste reduction targets are defined differently (30% reduction in consumption waste and 10% in processing waste), their overall ambition level is lower than the 50% total reduction interpreted under SDG 12.3. The reductions achieved in the scenarios therefore exceed the EU target.

Table 3: Target space definition

Outcome /target	Indicator category	Indicator	Unit	Baseline year	Target value	Target year	Ref
Outcome	Biodiversity	Ecosystem integrity	% change in MSA	2020	> 0	2050	KMGBF Goal A
Outcome	Climate	Global mean temperature increase	°C	1850-1900	< 1.5–2.0	2100	Paris Agr.
Outcome	Climate	Global emissions	Mt GHG		Net zero	2050	Paris Agr.
Outcome	Climate	EU GHG emission	% change	1990	55% reduc	2030	EU Climate Law
			T CO2eq		Net zero		
Outcome	Human wellbeing	Prevalence of undernourishment	%		<5%	2030	SDG 2
Outcome	Human wellbeing	Diet related deaths	% vs baseline	2015	1/3 reduction	2030	SDG 3.4
Action	Biodiversity	Area protected	%		30%	2030	KMGBF Target 3/ EU BDS
Action	Biodiversity	Degraded ecosystems under restoration	%		30%	2030	KMGBF Target 2/ EU NRL
Action	Pollution	Pesticide risk	% vs baseline	2020	50% reduction	2030	KMGBF Target 7 / EU F2F
Action	Pollution	Nutrient losses (N & P)	% vs baseline	2020	50% reduction	2030	KMGBF Target 7/ EU F2F
Action	Land use	Sustainable agr. land	%		-	2030	KMGBF Target 10
Action	Consumption	Land footprint per capita	% vs 2020	2020	< 0	2050	KMGBF Target 16
Action	Consumption	Food waste per capita	% vs baseline	2020	50% reduction	2030	KMGBF Target 16, SDG 12.3
Action	Consumption	EU Food waste	% vs baseline	2020	50% reduction	2030	Waste framework
Action	Consumption	EU Processing losses	% vs baseline	2020	10% reduction	2030	Waste framework

Table 4: Target space gaps and adjustments for each pathway

Pathway	Target space gap	Adjusted parameters
IMI	Insufficient reduction in pesticide input-related risk	50% reduction pesticide application rates of selected combinations of crop x regions x pesticides with high risk per hectare in and total. (no specific reduction was initially assumed apart from precision farming)
	Insufficient reduction in food loss and waste by 2030	Increase speed primarily of supply chain losses but also of consumption waste improvements
	Insufficient reduction in Years of life lost in 2030	Adjustment of the probability bins of food intake per food and age group in 2030
	MSA improvements after 2030 not sufficient to ensure a bending	Share of minimum degraded agricultural land under restoration by 2060 increased to 60% (instead of 50%) After 2030, Type 1 restoration share increased to 70% of additional restoration (instead of 60%)
GSO	Insufficient reduction in pesticide input-related risk	50% reduction pesticide application rates of selected combinations of crop x regions x pesticides with high risk per hectare in and total. (no specific reduction was initially assumed beside from precision and organic farming)
	Insufficient reduction in FLW	Increase speed of both supply chain and consumption waste improvements
	MSA improvements after 2030 not sufficient to ensure a bending	Share of minimum degraded agricultural land under restoration by 2060 increased to 60% (instead of 50%) After 2030, Type 1 restoration share increased to 70% of additional restoration (instead of 60%)
LCS	Insufficient reduction in nutrient losses and pesticide input-related risk	- Share of type 2 restoration increased (75% instead of 60%) so that more organic agriculture is adopted. - Force organic on high pesticide risk crops and

	region combinations (instead of no specific crop prioritization)
Insufficient reduction in FLW	Increase speed of both supply chain and consumption waste improvements
Lack of a mechanism for scaling restoration efforts beyond targets, and large amount of abandoned land in the full pathway	<p>Progressive restoration of unused abandoned, in priority to afforestation (within afforestation potentials), and to other natural land</p> <p>- Force minimum organic and silvopasture uptake to follow a linear trajectory reaching 65% and 50% respectively by 2050.</p>
MSA loss reductions after 2030 not sufficient to ensure a bending of ecosystem integrity	<p>Share of minimum degraded agricultural land under restoration by 2060 increased to 60% (instead of 50%)</p> <p>After 2030, Type 1 restoration share increased to 40% of additional restoration (instead of 25%)</p>

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Table 5: Target levels and achieved outcomes in calibrated pathways at global level

Indicator category	Indicator	Unit	Base year	Target value	Target year	BAU	IMI	GSO	LCS
Biodiversity	Ecosystem integrity	Change in MSA (vertebrates)	2020	>0	2050	-0.020	0.005	0.008	-0.005
Climate	Global mean temperature increase	°C	1850-1900	< 1.5-2.0	2100	3.4	1.7	1.7	1.6
Climate	Global emissions	Mt GHG		Net zero	2050	19%	-67%	-83%	-85%
Human wellbeing	Prevalence of undernourishment	%		<5%	2030	9%	6%	3%	1%
Human wellbeing	Diet related deaths	% vs base	2015	1/3 reduction	2030	19%	-27%	-39%	-66%
Biodiversity	Area protected	%		30%	2030	14%	30%	29%	30%
Biodiversity	Degraded agr. under restoration	%		30%	2030	8%	101%	97%	50%
Pollution	Pesticide risk (terrestrial)	% vs base	2020	50% reduction	2030	7%	-56%	-55%	-43%
Pollution	Pesticide risk (freshwater)	% vs base	2020	50% reduction	2030	5%	-62%	-61%	-43%
Pollution	Pesticide risk (marine)	% vs base	2020	50% reduction	2030	8%	-54%	-53%	-43%
Pollution	Phosphorus surplus	% vs base	2020	50% reduction	2030	-26%	-94%	-95%	-57%
Pollution	Nitrogen surplus	% vs base	2020	50% reduction	2030	3%	-97%	-92%	-52%
Land use	Agricultural land under sustainable practices	%		No quant. target	2030				
Consumption	Land footprint per capita	% vs 2020	2020	No quant. target	2050	3%	-6%	-7%	-2%
Consumption	Food waste per capita	% vs base	2020	50% reduction	2030	13%	-43%	-57%	-63%

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Table 6: Target levels and achieved outcomes in calibrated pathways at EU level

Indicator category	Indicator	Unit	Base year	Target value	Target year	BAU	IMI	GSO	LCS
Climate	GHG emissions	% GHG emissions	1990	55% reduction	2030	-5%	-30%	-43%	-49%
				Net zero	2050	7%			
Biodiversity	Area protected	%		30%	2030	25%	33%	28%	30%
Biodiversity	Area under strict protection	%		10%	2030	11%	13%	13%	12%
Biodiversity	Degraded ecosystems under restoration	%		30%	2030	3%	66%	54%	33%
				90%	2050	3%	84%	83%	73%
Pollution	Pesticide risk (terrestrial)	% vs baseline	2020	50% reduction	2030	4%	-44%	-48%	-53%
Pollution	Pesticide risk (freshwater)	% vs baseline	2020	50% reduction	2030	2%	-50%	-53%	-56%
Pollution	Pesticide risk (marine)	% vs baseline	2020	50% reduction	2030	6%	-40%	-44%	-51%
Pollution	Phosphorus surplus	% vs baseline	2020	50% reduction	2030	-24%	-78%	-76%	-54%
	Nitrogen surplus	% vs baseline	2020	50% reduction	2030	-30%	-94%	-90%	-57%
Consumption	Food waste per capita	% vs baseline	2020	30% reduction	2030	3%	-33%	-74%	-77%
	Food loss in processing	% vs baseline	2020	10% reduction	2030	1%	-67%	-59%	-69%

2.5 Analysis conceptualization and operationalization

As mentioned in the ‘objectives and overall approach’ sub-section, the projections generated by the GLOBIOM model address two objectives:

1. provide quantitative projections for the VITAL-Paths-Food pathways, in terms of indirect and direct drivers of biodiversity loss, biodiversity impacts and socio-economic impacts associated with the agricultural and forestry sectors.
2. support an analysis of the distributive impacts of efforts and impacts of the pathways across major world regions (with a focus on Europe) and actors (e.g., producers vs consumers). More specifically, the analysis aims to answer the following questions:
 - a. For each pathway, what level of effort in various intervention domains is needed to reach nature-, climate- and people goals, and how are those efforts distributed between regions?
 - b. For each pathway, what are the expected impacts on consumers, producers and the environment, how do those differ across regions and pathways, and how do those relate to different interventions?

The first objective furthers the specification of the VITAL-Paths-Food by complementing the qualitative narrative elements by quantitative elements, and can be achieved by generating indicator projections for each of the 3 pathways as 3 distinct scenarios. The second objective builds on the first objective, it aims to investigate these pathways in more detail and requires additional methodological steps further detailed below.

Counterfactual scenario and definition of efforts and impacts

The notion of efforts and impacts necessitates clarifying against which counterfactual the outcomes the VITAL-Paths-Food pathways are measured. We define the counterfactual as a ‘business-as-usual’ future scenario (BAU scenario), in which trends for the land use sectors follow historical trends (interpreted as the status-quo), and efforts to reach nature-, climate- and people goals beyond the status-quo are absent. The parameterization of such a business-as-usual (BAU) future scenario is provided in the ‘Initial Pathway implementation’ sub-section.

Once the counterfactual is clarified, the notions of efforts and impacts need to be specified. We rely on the following definitions:

- Efforts are understood as deviations to the BAU scenario in terms of consumption (e.g., food consumption per capita, energy and material woody biomass use), resource management (e.g., protection and restoration, changes in nutrient use efficiency) and commodity flows (e.g., supply, consumption, net trade) assumed to occur in the pathways as action directed at reaching the nature-, climate- and socio-economic goals of the pathways (e.g., changes in dietary preferences), or resulting from it (e.g., changes in commodity flows). Efforts can be understood as purposeful changes in indirect drivers of biodiversity loss.
- Impacts are defined as deviations to the BAU scenario in terms of a broader range of outcomes that affect climate, biodiversity and human wellbeing, and are resulting from food and biomass systems-wide adjustments. Impacts can be understood as broad changes in direct drivers of biodiversity loss, biodiversity loss and socio-economic outcomes, resulting from the efforts, either directly or through system-wide adjustments.

Table 7 summarizes how efforts and impacts are analyzed from the quantitative indicator projections generated by the model (see *Table 2*). It should be noted that even efforts and impacts are defined as deviations to the BAU scenario in specific indicator values, but in order to better understand how indicators change over time in the BAU and the VITAL-Paths-Food pathways, the indicators will often be provided in absolute value for 2020, 2030 and 2050 time horizons, or as absolute or relative change between 2020 and future time horizons (2030 and 2050).

Table 7: Definition of key efforts analyzed in this deliverable, and how they are derived from indicator projections

Category	Effort category	Relation to projected indicators
Efforts		
	Changes in dietary preferences and waste & loss	Changes in per capita food consumption (CALO, distinguished between crop and animal-based products), in per capita food loss and waste (FLWT, differentiated between waste and loss), and in within-country inequalities in
	Changes in woody biomass consumption, in particular in relation to climate mitigation efforts, as well as circularity aspects (recycling & re-use, cascading principle)	Changes in woody biomass use (BIOM, distinguished by source and end use)
	Changes in cropland and forest management	Changes in land use (LAND, CROPLAND_DYN), land management classes (LUM_CROP, LUM_FOREST), average crop yield (YILD), pesticide (PEST_INPUT) and nutrient (NUT_INPUT) inputs
	Changes in protected areas	Changes in protected areas (LPRT)
	Changes in restored areas	Changes in restoration land (LRST)
	Changes in commodity flows	Changes in market balance, including production (PROD), consumption (CONS) and net trade (NETT)
Impacts		
	Changes in land use extent	Changes in land use (LAND), by land use type
	Changes in AFOLU emissions	Changes in GHG emissions (EMIS), by source
	Changes in other agricultural pollution	Changes in nitrogen and phosphorous surplus (NUT_SURPLUS) and pesticide inputs (PEST_INPUT)
	Changes in ecosystem integrity loss	Changes in MSA loss (MSAP, MSAV)

	distinguished by pressure (land, climate)
Changes in global species extinction risks from agricultural activities	Changes in extinction risks in terrestrial (LCTE), freshwater (LCFE) and marine (LCME) ecosystems, differentiated by pressure (land occupation, land transformation, climate change, water stress, eutrophication, ecotoxicity)
Changes in the value of production	Changes in production volumes (PROD), prices (XPRP) and cropland area (CROPLAND_DYN) for the 18 crop dynamically represented in the model
Changes in the value of carbon removal in agricultural soils	Changes in related carbon removals (EMIS) and carbon price levels (CTAX)
Changes in cropland labor requirement	Changes in labor input requirement (ISLA, with differentiation between conventional, organic and precision farming) and cropland area (CROPLAND_DYN) for the 18 crops dynamically represented in the model
Changes in risks of undernourishment	Changes in the number of people at risk of undernourishment (UNDN)
Changes in health impacts from food consumption	Changes in the health impacts from diet-related diseases (YLL)
Changes in the footprint of consumption	Changes in the agricultural land (FPILCONS) and land occupation-related global species loss in terrestrial ecosystems (FPIButeoCONS) from the consumption of agricultural products

Decomposition scenarios and intervention bundles

The identification of the relationship between efforts and actions is not feasible when comparing each of the VITAL-Paths-Food pathways to the baseline, as multiple efforts are mobilized at the same time. To facilitate this step, we generated additional decomposition scenarios for each pathway, in which only a few model input parameters, related to a subset of interventions, follow the pathway narrative, while other model input parameters follow the BAU scenario. For example, an additional scenario exploring the impact of the dietary preferences assumed in the IMI scenario ('BAU-but-IMI-diets' scenario) would follow the BAU assumptions for all model input parameters, except for dietary preferences trends (which would follow the IMI scenario). Such scenarios were estimated as particularly valuable by stakeholders during an online workshop on the modelling toolbox, as both the model and the scenarios are complex, making it very difficult to understand the assumptions and their impacts on simulated outcomes (see Appendix).

To limit the number of scenarios, we bundle interventions by group: e.g., testing jointly waste reduction and dietary preferences as a demand-side intervention package. *Table 8* summarizes the different single bundles considered. These scenarios help us answer the following questions: How much does each effort individually contribute to desired outcomes? Are some efforts generating unintended adverse outcomes?

Table 8: Bundle definition

Abb	Bundle	Interventions considered
Dem	Demand side interventions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Dietary preferences for food products - Waste reduction for agricultural products - Within-country food intake inequality reduction
Cons	Conservation assumptions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Land protected - Land restored - Forest loss compensation
Sup	Other supply side assumptions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - NUE trends - Pesticide application rates - Yield trends - Additional uptake of organic/silvopasture
Clim	Other climate mitigation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Carbon price applied (subsidy on removals, tax on GHG emissions) - Energy and material woody biomass demand - Deforestation trends
Trd	Trade	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Trade costs and regulation

Summary of scenarios

We generated quantitative model projections for 19 scenarios, differing by their assumptions on individual intervention bundles, as detailed in *Table 9*. For decomposition scenarios, for each pathway [Scen] (IMI, GSO, LCS), and intervention bundle [Int], by convention the scenarios will be named ‘BAU_[Scen]-[Int]’ (e.g., BAU_IMI-Dem).

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Table 9: Summary of assumptions for the 19 scenarios for which GLOBIOM model projections were simulated

Scenario		Assumptions for individual intervention bundles								
Type	Name	Demand side		Conservation		Supply side		Climate mitigation		Trade
		Diet	Waste	Prot.	Rest.	NUE	Yield	C price	Biom.	Trade
Counterfactual	BAU	BAU	BAU	BAU	BAU	BAU	BAU	BAU	BAU	BAU
	VIITAL-Paths-Food pathways									
	IMI	IMI	IMI	IMI	IMI	IMI	IMI	IMI	IMI	IMI
	GSO	GSO	GSO	GSO	GSO	GSO	GSO	GSO	GSO	GSO
	LCS	LCS	LCS	LCS	LCS	LCS	LCS	LCS	LCS	LCS
Decomposition	BAU_IMI-Dem	IMI	IMI	BAU	BAU	BAU	BAU	BAU	BAU	BAU
	BAU_IMI-Cons	BAU	BAU	IMI	IMI	BAU	BAU	BAU	BAU	BAU
	BAU_IMI-Sup	BAU	BAU	BAU	BAU	IMI	IMI	BAU	BAU	BAU
	BAU_IMI-Clim	BAU	BAU	BAU	BAU	BAU	BAU	IMI	IMI	BAU
	BAU_IMI-Trd	BAU	BAU	BAU	BAU	BAU	BAU	BAU	BAU	IMI
	BAU_GSO-Dem	GSO	GSO	BAU	BAU	BAU	BAU	BAU	BAU	BAU
	BAU_GSO-Cons	BAU	BAU	GSO	GSO	BAU	BAU	BAU	BAU	BAU
	BAU_GSO-Sup	BAU	BAU	BAU	BAU	GSO	GSO	BAU	BAU	BAU
	BAU_GSO-Clim	BAU	BAU	BAU	BAU	BAU	BAU	GSO	GSO	BAU
	BAU_GSO-Trd	BAU	BAU	BAU	BAU	BAU	BAU	BAU	BAU	GSO
	BAU_LCS-Dem	LCS	LCS	BAU	BAU	BAU	BAU	BAU	BAU	BAU
	BAU_LCS-Cons	BAU	BAU	LCS	LCS	BAU	BAU	BAU	BAU	BAU
	BAU_LCS-Sup	BAU	BAU	BAU	BAU	LCS	LCS	BAU	BAU	BAU
	BAU_LCS-Clim	BAU	BAU	BAU	BAU	BAU	BAU	LCS	LCS	BAU
	BAU_LCS-Trd	BAU	BAU	BAU	BAU	BAU	BAU	BAU	BAU	LCS

2.6 Lessons learned

Preliminary results and lessons learned were discussed with stakeholders during an online workshop, and their feedback included. We synthesized the results presented in this deliverable, as well as limits and possible avenues for future research into key lessons learned.

3. RESULTS FROM PATHWAY QUANTIFICATION

3.1 Distribution of efforts across pathways, regions and actors

3.1.1 Consumption, waste and loss in the agricultural sector

Average food energetic intake per capita

Figure 1 depicts the projected changes in average food energetic intake per capita for crop and livestock products, which can be interpreted as changes in diets.

Projections for the BAU scenario consistently show an increase in consumption of both animal and crop products by 2030 and 2050, as compared to 2020. In contrast, across most regions, consumption in the VITAL-Paths-Food shifts away from animal-based products over the same period. This reduction is particularly pronounced in EUR and NAM-ANZ regions, where we also observe, to a lesser extent, a reduction in crop products. In contrast, the ROW region shows limited decline in animal-based products, and smaller decline in crop products than in other regions, with some variation across pathways. This is consistent with the assumed reduction in overconsumption (including a universal shift in dietary preferences towards the Eat Lancet 2.0 dietary targets) in the LCS and (to a lower extent) GSO pathways, and the adoption of novel plant-based alternative products (NBPA, also varied across pathways). Across the different pathways, LCS shows the strongest reductions in all regions and especially for animal products in EUR and NAM-ANZ regions. Regarding reductions in animal products, GSO and IMI show similar ambition at World level, while LCS leads to stronger reductions, in particular in EUR & NAM-ANZ regions. For crop products, IMI shows similar levels to BAU at World level, reflecting the assumed higher adoption of NPBA and the limited effort to reduce over-consumption.

Figure 1: Projected changes in average per capita food energetic intake, split by livestock (LSP) and crop products (CRP). Panel a) provides absolute changes in intake levels as compared to 2020 (in kg/cap/yr) for the BAU and the VITAL-Paths-Food scenarios (core scenarios), while the panel b) (resp. c)) provides relative differences (in percentage) in 2050 between the decomposition scenarios and the BAU scenario at the World (resp. EUR) level.

The deviations to the BAU consumption levels by 2050 for the decomposition scenarios at the World (panel b)) and EUR (panel c)) level highlight the predominant role of the demand-side intervention bundle, but also the existence of smaller consumption dampening associated with conservation and climate mitigation intervention bundles, particularly in GSO and IMI, because of heightened prices for agricultural products. Similarly, yield increases from supply-side measures induce a slight increase in consumption at World level of crop products in the IMI scenario, through higher availability.

The amplitude of the decrease in the average intake of livestock products per capita projected in the VITAL-Paths-Food scenarios as compared to the BAU scenario by 2050 are systematically larger at EUR level than at global scale in absolute terms (panel a)), but are comparable in relative terms (panels b) and c), about -21% and -27% for the GSO and IMI pathways), except for the LCS pathway (about -45% at the world level, and -68% at the EU level). For crop products, deviations to the BAU scenario are higher at EUR than World level, in relative terms, except for the IMI pathways.

Food loss & waste

Figure 2 below describes projected changes in food loss and waste, as compared to 2020 for the BAU and the VITAL-Paths-Food pathways (upper panel), as well as the contribution of the different intervention bundles to the 2050 difference between the VITAL-Paths-Food pathways and the BAU at the world (middle panel) and EUR (bottom panel).

Both loss and waste are projected to remain stable in the BAU scenario (in particular in EUR), and decrease all VITAL-Paths-Food pathways. Difference between the BAU scenario and the VITAL-Paths-Food pathways in 2050 vary across regions and component (i.e., loss vs waste), in relation to different intervention bundles: for example, the loss reductions (as part of the supply-side intervention bundle) tend to be slightly stronger in IMI & LCS and particularly stronger in the ROW region, while the waste reductions are stronger in the GSO and IMI pathways, and in OECD regions.

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Figure 2: Projected changes in food loss and waste. Panel a) provides absolute changes in waste and losses levels as compared to 2020 (in kg/cap/yr) for the BAU and the VITAL-Paths-Food scenarios (core scenarios), while the panel b) (resp. c)) provides relative differences (in percentage) in 2050 between the decomposition scenarios and the BAU scenario at the World (resp. EUR) level.

This distribution reflects mostly our pathway assumptions around food loss and waste (mostly formulated as uniform relative decrease across regions), as well as differences across regions in absolute levels of food loss and waste. However, they are also modulated by trends in production and food consumption levels. In relative terms, the amplitude of the decrease in the food loss and waste per capita projected as compared to the BAU scenario by 2050 is relatively comparable between World and EUR levels for both losses and waste.

Inequalities in energetic food intake

Figure 3 displays the projected changes in the coefficient of variation (CV) of the distribution across the human population in energetic food intake, which can be interpreted as a measure of food consumption inequality. It includes heterogeneity in food energetic intake across countries, based on the average per capita consumption endogenously simulated by the model in each region (as described in Figure 1). The latter is affected by both exogenous assumptions about dietary preferences, as well as endogenously-simulated commodity price dynamics, with consumption levels increasing when prices decrease and vice-versa. However, the changes in the CV reported in Figure 3 also includes heterogeneity in energetic food intake within countries, as estimated following Hasegawa et al. (2015). The within-country inequality is assumed to follow a normal distribution, whose CV evolves in the BAU scenario according to BAU trends income levels, and a relationship between income levels and CV estimated over historical data (see Hasegawa et al., 2015). In the VITAL-Paths-Food scenarios, varying levels of reduction in the within-country CV of energetic food intake are assumed on top of the BAU scenario, as additional efforts to reduce food security risks¹ (see also section 3.2).

¹ It should be noted that, within a model region, assumptions about trends in within-country CV of energetic food intake distribution are an important driver of projections of undernourishment, but do not affect the projected average energetic intake per capita, which is entirely determined by exogenous trends in average dietary preferences and supply-demand dynamics. This holds as long as the assumed reductions in the within-country CV of food energetic intake are assumed symmetric with respect to the average intake.

Figure 3: Projected changes in the coefficient of variation (CV) of the distribution of food energetic intake across the population (including within-country distribution). The upper panel provides absolute changes in CV values as compared to 2020 (dimensionless) for the BAU and the VITAL-Paths-Food scenarios, while the lower panel provides relative differences (in percentage) in 2050 between the decomposition scenarios and the BAU scenario at world level.

In the BAU scenario, inequalities in food energetic intake are projected to remain relatively stable, with a slight increase globally, peaking before 2050. In contrast, inequalities in food energetic intake are projected to follow a moderate (about 10%, IMI scenario) to high (about 50%, LCS scenario) reduction in total CV of food consumption, following closely the assumptions about within-country CV reduction for those scenarios. In particular, as food energetic inequality is much higher within countries than across countries globally, even the universal convergence in dietary preferences towards the Eat Lancet 2.0 diet assumed in the LCS pathway contributes little to overall energetic intake inequalities as compared to the 50% reduction of within-country CV assumed in this pathway.

Decreases in within-country food intake inequalities are similar at EUR and global level, by assumption. This leads to decreases in total food intake inequality at EUR level in all scenarios, except for LCS by 2050: in this scenario, the average food intake decrease is large, which mechanically inflates the impact of differences across countries of EUR in average food intake on the total EUR food intake inequality.

3.1.2 Protection and agricultural land restoration efforts

Protection

Figure 4 below presents the differences across pathways in the area protected, split between strict protection (i.e., excluding biomass production activities) and permissive protection (with low- to mid-intensity extractive activities allowed, such as close-to-nature and multifunctional forest management), as well as between types of land use (forest, agricultural land and other vegetation).

Increased protection efforts vary across regions and pathways, reflecting both the pathway-specific assumptions, the pre-existing level of protection, and the availability of land of high-conservation value.

In Europe, the share of land moving in 2030 under strict protection is limited and remains relatively stable across pathways, due to limited land assumed suitable (i.e., of high conservation value without restoration), and the already relatively high share of protected areas in 2020. Within protected areas, forest as well as managed and unmanaged non-forest land are evenly distributed. IMI shows a slightly higher overall share of protected land in Europe compared to GSO and LCS.

Figure 4: Projected land area under protection. The upper panel provides share of protected areas as (in percentage) for the BAU and the VITAL-Paths-Food scenarios in 2030, while the lower panel provides total protected areas (in Mha) in 2030 split by land use types.

In NAM-ANZ region, we observe the largest increase in the share of land under strict protection between 2020 and 2030, especially in GSO, and the additional protected land is concentrated mainly (but not exclusively) on unmanaged non-forest areas GSO, and forest areas in IMI & LCS. However, in absolute area, most of the additional protected land is located in the ROW region, mainly (but not exclusively) in forest areas.

It should be noted that these estimates do not include restored land as part of protected areas, although the restored land is also assumed to remain under either strict or permissive management (see below). Importantly, our implementation of the VITAL-Paths-Food assumes no further increase in protection after 2030, while restoration efforts are assumed to continue until 2050. Overall, our implementation

of the VITAL-Paths-Food pathways assumes that large expansions of protected areas (in addition to continued restoration efforts) may not be easily feasible, and that sustainable production and consumption efforts will be key to preserving the remaining high conservation-value ecosystems.

Agricultural land restoration

Figure 5: below presents the achieved type 1 (restoration of degraded agricultural land into unmanaged land) and type 2 (restoration of degraded agricultural land into better condition agricultural land) restoration in the different scenarios as well as decomposition analysis.

No restoration is assumed in the BAU scenario, although some of the measures corresponding to type 2 restoration marginally expand. As shown in Figure 5 a), the three pathways exceed restoration targets assumed as part of the conservation intervention bundle, with a largest exceedance in IMI, and lowest in LCS. We project a large amount of type-2 restoration, covering an area ranging from 1239 Mha (LCS pathway) to 1,567 Mha (GSO pathway) globally by 2050 (range in 2030: 570-1237 Mha). In comparison, we project type-1 restoration ranging from 454 Mha (LCS pathway) to 478 Mha (GSO pathway) globally by 2050 (range in 2030: 235-244 Mha). In comparison, the target for restoration (an area roughly corresponding to 30% - by 2030 - and 60% - by 2050 - of ca 2020 degraded agricultural land restored), defining the total restoration area as part of the conservation intervention bundle, amounts to about 356-426 Mha by 2030 and 714-761 Mha globally. Total restoration efforts are therefore always at least twice the minimum restoration targets, and for IMI & GSO by 2030, three times the minimum restoration targets. This stems from assumptions about type-2 restoration in relation to climate mitigation efforts (in particular for IMI and GSO) and, for LCS, a broad land use extensification trend.

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Figure 5: Projected restored degraded agricultural land area. Panel a) provides the absolute area of restored degraded agricultural land by 2030 and 2050, split by large region (EU, OECD non-EU, non-OECD, World) and by restoration type (type 1 = natural forest restoration, type 2 = adoption of sustainable agricultural management practices) for the core BAU and the VITAL-Paths-Food scenarios. Panel b) (resp. c)) provides the difference in restored degraded agricultural land between the decomposition scenarios and the BAU scenario by 2050 due, normalized to the total

land area at the World (resp. EUR) level.

As shown in Figure 5 b) at global scale, the occurrence of type-2 restoration beyond the restoration targets (assumed as part of the conservation intervention bundle) is related for a part to the payment for carbon removal in agricultural soils (assumed as part of the climate mitigation intervention bundle), in particular for IMI & GSO pathways. It leads to higher adoption of deintensification options. Due to an assumed limited use of market-based instruments (i.e., lower carbon price), the uptake of type-2 restoration beyond what is assumed as part of the conservation intervention bundle is much lower in the LCS scenario. However, this pathway instead assumes a progressive shift towards more extensive production methods (as part of the supply-side intervention bundle). This results in slightly lower amount of type 2 restoration achieved across the three pathways, despite LCS assuming the highest target share for type 2 restoration (70%, instead of 40% in IMI and GSO). In addition, despite a lower share of type-1 restoration in minimum restoration targets in LCS, this type of restoration isn't much lower than in other pathways, due to the assumed restoration (primarily through afforestation) of large amounts of abandoned agricultural land in EUR and NAM-ANZ regions. These outcomes highlight that in our pathways, restoration outcomes are affected by multiple, and sometimes conflicting narrative elements, including value preferences about human-nature relationships (affecting the preference for various forms of restoration and for broader land management patterns), about the use of market-based instruments (also affecting land management patterns) and about approaches to sustainable consumption (affecting patterns of land pressure and opportunities for restoration).

In all scenarios, a larger share of type-1 restoration happens in ROW countries than in EUR and NAM-ANZ regions. However, the share of EUR and NAM-ANZ regions is slightly higher in LCS (due to the combined consumption change and restoration assumptions) and, except for EUR, in GSO (due to an assumed slightly higher share of NAM-ANZ in minimum restoration efforts towards the global restoration target). The share of total land projected to be under type-1 restoration is slightly lower at EUR than World level, except for LCS (due to the assumed combination of consumption changes and abandoned land restoration). The share of type-2 restoration represents in total land is slightly higher at EUR than World level: this is due to either a slightly higher uptake of restoration measures as part of the climate

mitigation intervention bundle (in IMI & GSO) or a higher amount of abandoned land (in LCS), as well as a slightly higher share of degraded land, partially compensated in the GSO and IMI pathways by a lower share of EUR in minimum restoration efforts towards the global restoration target).

3.1.3 Agricultural production practices, yields and input use efficiencies

Adoption of alternative farming practices in cropland and pasture

As detailed in Table 10, a range of alternative cropland and pasture management strategies can be adopted in response to both climate mitigation financial incentives (carbon tax as part of the climate mitigation intervention bundle), minimum restoration areal adoption constraints (as part of the conservation intervention bundle), and general uptake of extensive practices (as part of the supply-side intervention bundle, for LCS) with distinct effects on multiple parameters such as yields / harvested biomass, fertilizer and pesticide input use and input use efficiency, soil organic carbon stocks, GHG emissions, production costs etc.. These include alternative techniques on cropland such as organic farming (with full reduction of synthetic fertilizer and pesticide application, and yield penalties), precision farming (with partial reduction in pesticide application and improvement in nutrient use efficiency, nutrient losses and GHG emissions), but also soil biochar application, practices focused on improving soil organic carbon in cropland, other cropland practices focused GHG emission mitigation, as well as silvopastures (see effects in Table 10). Not every alternative farming practice is eligible towards the restoration targets (due to assumed preferences for restoration across pathways), and some measures can be combined on the same area. Measures counting for restoration are treated as exclusive in the model to ensure that the restored area target is achieved.

Table 10: considered alternative cropland and pasture management practices in the VITAL-Paths-Food quantitative projections

Group	Definition	Effects	Coverage in intervention bundles	Additionality
Cropland organic farming	Adoption of organic farming standards with no synthetic fertilizer or pesticide application allowed. Source: (Kuipers et al., 2025)	Reduced yields (amplitude depends on crop type), 100% reduction in pesticide application and synthetic fertilizers, 35% (resp. 19% for rice) reduction in N ₂ O emissions, resulting in reduction in total N/P application rate (leading to reduced losses), belongs to ‘low intensity’ cropland class for GLOBIO, no additional cost assumed,	Not emerging under carbon tax, eligible for type-2 restoration in GSO and LCS pathways, assumed to expand in as part of the supply-side intervention bundle in LCS	Cannot be combined in the same cropland area with other crop management, except biochar application and soil organic carbon measures except when they count together for the restoration target (to avoid double counting) . Contributes towards restoration targets with measures XYZ (when included in intervention bundle).
Cropland precision farming	Adoption of variable rate techniques with increased nutrient and pesticide input use efficiency. Source: (Frank et al., 2024)	Yields unaffected, 20% reduction in pesticide application (increasing to 30% in 2050) and 20% reduction in N ₂ O emissions, resulting in reductions in total N/P application rate (leading to reduced losses), no additional cost assumed	Not emerging under carbon tax, eligible for type-2 restoration in GSO and IMI pathways	Cannot be combined in the same cropland area with other crop management, except biochar application and soil organic carbon measures except when they count together for the restoration target (to avoid double counting)
Biochar application to soils	Biochar application to croplands for increased carbon sequestration and crop productivity. Source: (Frank et al., 2024)	CO ₂ emission reductions following carbon sequestration (-0.53 to -5.11t CO ₂ eq/ha), with saturation after 30 years, yield improvement (amplitude depends on sequestered carbon), cost ranges from 19\$ to 184\$/ha	Emerging under carbon tax, eligible for type-2 restoration in GSO, LCS and IMI pathways	Can be combined with any other crop management practice except when they count together for the restoration target (to avoid double counting)
Other soil organic carbon increase-focused techniques	Improved management practices on cropland and pasture, aiming enhance carbon sequestration. Source: (Frank et al., 2024)	CO ₂ emission reduction following carbon sequestration (-0.19 to -2.76t CO ₂ eq/ha), with saturation after 20 years, Improved crop yields (amplitude depends on sequestered carbon), costs range from 0.1\$ to 13\$/ha	Emerging under carbon tax, only soil organic carbon measures on pasture eligible for type-2 restoration in GSO, LCS and IMI pathways	Can be combined with any other crop management practice except when they count together for the restoration target (to avoid double counting)
Other cropland GHG mitigation techniques	Adoption of other various improved fertiliser management (e.g. auto fertilisation, residue incorporation) and rice management option (e.g. continuous flooding). Source: (Frank et	GHG emission reduction, yield improvements and N ₂ O emission reductions, detail on the effect of specific measures is available in (Frank et al., 2018)	Emerging under carbon tax, <i>no tillage</i> and <i>100% residue incorporation</i> eligible for type 2 restoration	Cannot be combined in the same cropland area with other crop management, except biochar application and soil organic carbon measures except when they count

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	al., 2018)			together for the restoration target (to avoid double counting)
Silvopastures	Silvopasture_IP: Pastures with 25% tree coverage for bioenergy (Short rotation plantation) and 10 year rotation Silvopasture: pastures with 25% tree coverage and 30 year rotation. Source: (Frank et al., 2024)	CO2 emission reduction following carbon sequestration (-0.72 to -3.26t CO2e/ha), with saturation after 10 years (for bioenergy production) or 30 years (without), Increased N2O emissions leading to increase in N/P applications (when for bioenergy production only), Reduced pasture yields (25% area tree coverage), costs range from 0.5\$ to 0.9\$/ha or to 110\$/ha when for bioenergy production	Emerging under carbon tax, both types of silvopasture eligible for type-2 restoration in GSO, only silvopasture for bioenergy production in IMI and without bioenergy for LCS, assumed to expand in as part of the supply-side intervention bundle in LCS	Can be combined with soil organic carbon measures on pasture in the same cropland area in any pathway, except when they count together for restoration target (to avoid double counting)

While the area of organic farming follows trends reported by the FAO over 2000-2020, due to a lack of data we do not force adoption of other alternative farming practices in all scenarios until 2020 (some marginal uptake still occurs). In the BAU scenario, we assume we do not impose additional developments in either organic farming or any other alternative farming practices (some marginal uptake occurs).

As illustrated in Figure 6, we project the adoption of alternative management practices in the VITAL-Paths-Food scenarios, with differences across pathways and regions. It's important to note that some of the alternative management practices can be accumulated within the same agricultural area, and the total area shown is therefore larger than the extent of type-2 restoration area displayed in Figure 5.

As part of restoration efforts in the conservation intervention bundle (see BAU_*-Cons scenarios in panels b) and c)), precision farming adoption is projected in IMI and GSO, while LS focuses more on organic farming. Even if organic farming is also a management option in GSO, it is outcompeted by precision farming, which has better yield outcomes. The distribution across regions also differs across pathways (due to the assumed effort sharing principles): highest adoption of organic agriculture in LCS is projected in regions such as USA (part of NAM-ANZ) or BRA (part of ROW), while highest adoption of precision farming in IMI and GSO is projected in ROW, including CHN, IND or BRA. Next to precision and organic cropland management, the conservation intervention bundle also leads to the adoption of alternative cropland management practices focused on increasing soil organic carbon content, and silvopastures. Globally we observe a higher adoption of alternative agricultural management practices in LCS than in IMI and GSO, reflecting the relatively high level of extensification assumed in LCS.

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Figure 6: Projections for the area of alternative agricultural management practices. Panel a) provides for aggregated regions the projected absolute agricultural area over which specific alternative management practices are adopted from 2020 to 2030 and 2050, for the core scenarios (in million hectares Mha, cropland for measures except for silvopastures). Panel b) (resp. c)) provides the difference to the BAU scenario in 2050 in the agricultural area (in Mha) occupied by various alternative management practices for the decomposition scenarios at the World (resp., EUR) level.

While organic farming and precision farming adoption are mainly governed by the minimum type-2 restoration constraint and (for LCS) pesticide reduction

assumptions, the adoption of other alternative management practices are mainly (and for some, exclusively) driven by the carbon removal and GHG emission reduction financial incentives assumed as part of the climate mitigation intervention bundle (see BAU_*-Clim scenarios in panels b) and c)). The geographical pattern therefore reflects differences in relative mitigation potentials, while the scenario patterns reflect differences in financial incentives. Adoption is higher in regions with higher baseline emission intensities. Silvopasture is widely adopted across scenarios, often as of 2030.

In the LCS pathway, organic cropland and silvopasture are projected to expand as part of the supply-side intervention bundle. By 2050, this represents an area larger than the total uptake of alternative agricultural management practices under the conservation intervention bundle, but lower than total uptake of alternative agricultural management practices under the climate mitigation intervention bundle in the IMI & GSO pathway.

It is important to note that significant uncertainties remain regarding the effects and scalability of several options, and the projections are therefore sensitive to modeling assumptions regarding for example the maximum adoption rates and the technical and economic applicability of individual practices.

Average crop yield

Figure 7 presents the regional evolution of yields from 2020 to 2050 across the core scenarios (BAU & VITAL-Paths-Food pathways), as well as the difference to the BAU scenario by 2050 for the decomposition scenarios.

Compared to 2020 levels, due to research and development effort-induced technological progress, we project by 2050 an increase in crop yields in the BAU scenario, ranging from +13% in NAM-ANZ to +27% in ROW countries, based on the SSP2 scenario assumptions.

Yields are projected to remain stable as compared to 2020 globally in the LCS scenario, with moderate reductions (resp. increases) in EUR & NAM (rep. ROW) regions of up to -25% (resp. +11%) by 2050, and lower yields everywhere as compared to the BAU scenario (-17% at World level, -13% at ROW level, -37% at EUR level). The type-2 restoration from the increased conservation intervention bundles does not

have a large effect (BAU_LCS-Cons in panels b) and c)), despite to assumed yield gap from organic agriculture (between 13% and 29% depending in the crop group). However, a significant decrease is projected as a result of the supply-side intervention bundle (especially at EUR level) due to the higher uptake of organic farming (and for EUR, a lower assumed level of technological progress), as well as for demand-side interventions (BAU_LCS-Dem, especially at World level) due to resulting changes in the allocation of cropland across regions and crops (e.g., low- vs high- yielding regions/crops).

Similar (GSO) or higher (IMI) future yield gains are projected by 2050 as compared to the BAU globally (+9% for IMI, -1% for GSO), with larger deviations to BAU for ROW in IMI (+13%), and for both GSO (-13%) and IMI (-9%) for EUR. For both pathways, the conservation, supply-side and demand-side intervention bundles have effects of a similar order of magnitude but varying directions.

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Figure 7: Projected changes in average crop yield regions for the core scenarios (panel a) and differences to BAU in 2050 for the decomposition scenarios at World (panel b) and EUR level (panel c).

Input use efficiency

Figure 8 and Figure 9 show the projections of changes input use efficiencies, calculated as the ratio of crop output to N input use, for nitrogen, phosphorus and pesticides. These indicators capture changes in the technical efficiency of cropping systems over time and across pathways.

In the BAU scenario, we project moderate changes to input use efficiency. This entails a moderate increase in NUE by 2050 in EUR & NAM-ANZ regions and a stable

NUE for ROW. PUE is projected to moderately decrease in EUR & NAM-ANZ and significantly increase in ROW. Pesticide use efficiency is projected to moderately increase as a result the assumed yield gains, and constant application rates.

Figure 8: Projected changes in a) nutrient and b) pesticide use efficiency as compared to 2020 for the core scenarios.

For VITAL-Paths-Food scenarios, we projected a generalized increase in input use efficiency by 2030 as compared to 2020, with a delay for nutrient in LCS (similar levels reached in 2050 only) and an additional increase from 2030 to 2050 for pesticides. The increase by 2050 is particularly larger for ROW: between a doubling (GSO) and a tripling (IMI, LCS) for pesticide use efficiency, about a doubling for phosphorous (all 3 pathways), and a 40% increase for nitrogen. In contrast, for EUR

region the input use efficiency increase is comparable to BAU for nitrogen, remain constant (instead of declining) for phosphorous, and increase more than BAU for pesticide for LCS (up to a doubling) but not for other pathways. This reflects the relatively lower potential for input use efficiency EUR as compared to ROW regions, except for pesticides. It should be noted that the pace with which input use efficiency gains are particularly high for ROW regions.

As illustrated in Figure 9, the improvements to input use efficiency in the VITAL-Paths-Food scenarios as compared to the BAU scenario by 2050 are dominated at global level by the assumed increases in input use efficiency as part of the supply-side intervention bundle, except for pesticide in the LCS pathway. For the latter, the increase in organic agriculture, prioritized to crops contributing most to pesticide application risk, assumed as part of the conservation intervention bundle, dominates. This effect leads slight decreases in nitrogen use efficiency at EUR level.

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Figure 9: Projected changes in a) nutrient and b) pesticide use efficiency in 2050 between the decomposition scenario and the BAU scenario, at World and EUR level.

3.1.4 Market balance of agricultural products

Market balance for agricultural products

The projected changes in the supply, consumption and net trade of agricultural products across scenarios and regions are shown in Figure 10 for livestock products and Figure 11 for crop products. This includes changes to 2020 for the core scenarios by 2030 and 2050, as well as the difference between the BAU scenario in 2050 for the decomposition scenarios, at world level. The projected values for net trade are further detailed in Figure 12, while a decomposition of all three market balance components is provided at EUR level in Figure 13.

In the BAU scenario, we project an increase in supply and consumption in all regions, for both livestock and crop products. In relative terms as compared to 2020, by 2050 the projected increase in supply is about +39% (resp. +20%) for crop products at World (resp. EUR) level, and +37% (resp. +14%) for livestock products at World (resp. EUR) level. The amplitude of relative changes in consumption is the same than that of supply at World level, and is slightly lower at EUR level for crop products (+17%) and , resp. for livestock products, +9%). Projected changes to the net trade balance varies across regions, with increases in net trade (i.e., increase in net exports, decrease in net imports, or swap from net importing to net exporting status) of crop products for BRA, IND, OSA, OAS and FSU, decrease in net trade (i.e., increase in net imports, decrease in net exports, or swap from net exporting to net importing status) of crop products for SSA, USA, MEN and CHN, increase in net trade of livestock products for ANZ, USA, BRA, CAN, EUR, SEA, OSA, and decrease in net trade of livestock products for IND, SSA, MEN and OAS. While the amount of traded commodities across the 13 regions is expected to roughly double between 2020 and 2050 in the BAU, the major importing and exporting regions are however expected to remain relatively similar to 2020, with by 2050 major net imports (resp. net exports) of crop products for CHN, EUR, SSA, MEN (resp. BRA, OSA, FSU) and major net imports (resp. exports) of livestock products for MEN, SEA, OAS, SSA (resp. EUR, ANZ, CAN, BRA).

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Figure 10: Projected changes in the market balance of livestock products, split by region (colored bars) and balance term (supply, consumption and net trade, in separate panels; net trade is defined supply - consumption). The upper panel provides absolute changes in market balance as compared to 2020 (in million t of fresh product per year) for the BAU and the VITAL-Paths-Food scenarios. The bottom panel provides the difference in market balance terms to BAU in 2050 for the decomposition scenarios, normalized by the total supply at world level (%).

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Figure 11: Projected changes in the market balance of crop products, split by region (colored bars) and balance term (supply, consumption and net trade, in separate panels; net trade is defined supply - consumption). The upper panel provides absolute changes in market balance as compared to 2020 (in million t of fresh product per year) for the BAU and the VITAL-Paths-Food scenarios. The bottom panel provides the difference in market balance terms to BAU in 2050 for the decomposition scenarios, normalized by the total supply at world level (%).

In contrast, for the VITAL-Paths-Food scenarios, as compared to 2020 we project by 2050 either a much more moderate increase (or even a net decrease for half of regions in IMI, and most regions except SSA, SEA and IND in LCS) in the consumption of livestock products, and a much more moderate increase in the consumption of crop products in most cases (with a net decrease in a few cases, e.g., CHN in all pathways, as well as EUR, FSU and USA in LCS). In relative terms, across VITAL-Paths-Food scenarios the projected consumption levels by 2050 are 27-46% (resp. 9-32%) lower than in the BAU scenario at World level for livestock (resp. crop) products. At EUR level, it is 19-68% (resp. 11-53%) for livestock (resp. crop) products. Projected differences between the VITAL-Paths-Food scenarios and the BAU scenario for supply matches that of consumption at the World level. At regional scale, this is in general also the case (including for the EUR region), with however some differences in amplitude due to trade: e.g., in absolute terms, for crop products, decreases in VITAL-Paths-Food as compared to the BAU scenario in 2050 are larger for supply than for consumption in major exporting regions (e.g., BRA), and the way around for major importing regions (e.g., CHN, SSA). As livestock products are comparatively less traded, this is often less the case (or to a lower extent).

Overall, as compared to the BAU, in the VITAL-Paths-Food scenarios, future increases in the total volume of traded commodities are strongly moderated for crop products (if not cancelled, with 2050 levels very close to 2020), while less strongly affected for livestock products (with 2050 levels close to the BAU scenario) except for the LCS pathway (2050 levels close to 2020 levels). As illustrated in Figure 12, while patterns of net exporting and importing regions remains similar to the BAU, some regions consistently change status across pathways and commodity groups (e.g., IND becomes a large importer of both crop and livestock products, especially in IMI & GSO pathways). Similarly, some major exporting / importing regions can have very different deviations to the BAU across pathways: for example, the USA might turn into a large exporter of crop products in the IMI pathway, but a net importer in the GSO and LCS pathways; CHN could maintain a relatively small trade balance of livestock products for the GSO & LCS pathways, but become a large net importer in IMI.

Figure 12: Projected values for net trade (in million tons of fresh matter) a) from 2020, 2030 and 2050 in the core scenarios and b) by 2050 for decomposition scenarios, split by region (colored bars) and crop vs livestock product groups (sub-panels; CRP = crops, LSP = livestock).

As illustrated in Figure 10 b) and Figure 11 b), the difference in consumption levels between the VITAL-Paths-Food scenarios and the BAU scenario in 2050 are primarily driven by demand-side intervention bundles. Through their impact on supply potentials, the climate mitigation and conservation interventions bundles have small

negative impacts, and, for crop products, the supply-side intervention bundle a small positive impact. Except for the LCS pathway, and in general more for crop than for livestock products, the relative dominance of demand-side intervention bundles is less pronounced for changes in supply. The trade intervention bundle can be important for a few regions, in particular for IMI. At last, net trade seems to be significantly affected by most measures, with the conservation intervention bundle leading to increased total volume of trade for crop products, the demand-side limiting futures increase in trade, the trade intervention bundle increasing trade in IMI (in particular for livestock products) and decreasing trade in LCS.

In EUR decreases in supply are smaller than decreases in consumption (which lowers net exports of livestock products and reduces increase net imports of crops) except for crop products in LCS and livestock products in IMI.

D5.3 – Lessons learned from the quantification of the pathways

Figure 13: Projected changes in the market balance of EU as compared to the BAU in 2050, split by product category (bottom vs lower panel) and balance term (supply, consumption and net trade, in separate panels; net trade is defined supply - consumption). Values are absolute differences in market balance term value in 2050 between the decomposition scenarios and the BAU scenario in million t of fresh product per year, normalized by the EUR-level supply for the BAU scenario in 2050 (%).

3.1.5 Ligno-cellulosic biomass use, forestry and forest management

Ligno-cellulosic biomass use and sourcing

Figure 14 provides the projected amount of ligno-cellulosic biomass used by end-use type (with a distinction between energy and material use), and by source (with a distinction between primary sources such as crop residues vs harvest from forest and short rotation plantations, and secondary sources such as recycled wood and forest industry by-products). It provides an illustration of trends in multiple woody biomass supply chain components.

In the BAU scenario, ligno-cellulosic biomass use for energy (for both fuelwood and industrial heat & electricity generation) is assumed to remain constant globally, while moderate increases in material use are projected, primarily in the ROW region. This reflects assumed trends in energy and material demand, as well as the relatively larger biomass potential from ROW as compared to the EUR and NAM-ANZ regions. A large share of the increase in material use is related to the pulp and paper industry, with traditionally a high share of recycling. The contribution of crop residues increases in ROW, and decreases slightly in NAM-ANZ.

D5.3 – Lessons learned from the quantification of the pathways

Figure 14: Projected changes in ligno-cellulosic biomass use, split by end-use type (Ene for energy use, colored bars; Mat for material use, white bars with colored contours; sum for total Ene+Mat, black dots) and source (primary biomass from crop residues in brown, for Ene use only; primary biomass from forests and short rotation plantations in dark green; forest industry by-products in grey, for Ene use only; recycled wood products in blue). The upper panel provides absolute changes in biomass use levels as compared to 2020 (in million m³ per year) for the BAU and the VITAL-Paths-Food scenarios, while the middle (resp. lower) panel provides relative differences in 2050 between the decomposition scenarios and the BAU scenario, normalized to total use for BAU in 2050, at the World (resp. EUR) level.

In the VITAL-Paths-Food scenarios, the use of ligno-cellulosic biomass is projected to be more contrasted, ranging from no change in the LCS scenario (+0%), to an increase by 19% and 38% in the GSO and IMI pathways. As illustrated in the middle panel of Figure 14 (BAU_IMI-Clim, BAU_GSO-Clim and BAU_LCS-Clim scenarios), this primarily relates to the contrasted assumptions about biomass use for climate mitigation purposes across the pathways. While the LCS pathway assumes the same level of demand than the BAU scenario, the IMI pathway is assumed to have a higher reliance on biomass use (together with efforts to increase recycling and re-use), for both material and energy use. The projected increase in material use is assuming that 90% of the new urban population will live in wooden buildings after 2020 (Mishra et al 2022), while the projected increase in energy use assumes a 37% increase in biomass-based bioenergy by 2050 as compared to 2020. The latter is compatible with a doubling of biomass energy use by 2100 (to about 114 EJ/yr), an outcome typical of climate stabilization pathways compatible with the Paris Agreement (Rogelj et al., 2019). The GSO pathway assumes half of the IMI ligno-cellulosic biomass increase. Therefore, the GSO pathway, and even more so the LCS pathway, assume stronger GHG emission reductions in the rest of the economy, than assumed in the typical climate stabilization pathway compatible with the Paris Agreement. Other interventions have small impacts on total demand, through price-driven adjustments to wood demand, and a slightly larger impact on sourcing patterns.

Next to the assumed levels of biomass demand, the contrasted assumptions across VITAL-Paths-Food pathways about recycling and reuse, demand for crop products, as well as roundwood forest plantation expansion and agricultural product demand, are important to understand changes to the sourcing of ligno-cellulosic biomass. As illustrated by the BAU_IMI-Dem and BAU_GSO-Dem scenarios, the assumed increased re-use and recycling rate is projected to cancel the increased use of forest and SRP biomass needed to sustain the increased material demand, as well as the increased use of forest industry by-products for energy. As illustrated by the BAU_IMI-Dem and BAU_GSO-Dem scenarios, demand-side interventions may limit the potential contribution of crop residues, with potential for increased pressure on forest ecosystems. However, additionally assuming an expansion of roundwood short rotation plantations and reductions in animal product consumption (as illustrated by

the difference between BAU_IMI-Clim and IMI in Figure 14) might lead to a significantly higher share of forest and short-rotation plantation-based ligno-cellulosic biomass use (in particular for energy, through short rotation protection expansion over abandoned pastures), instead of crop residues. As highlighted in Figure 15 (see also next subsection on forest management), pressure on existing forests could reduce concomitantly, with the abandonment of semi-natural forests under production-oriented forest management.

Overall, deviations to the BAU scenario (and to 2020) are very limited at the EU level, as compared to the rest of the world. The increase in total ligno-cellulosic biomass-based products use in the VITAL-Paths-Food as compared to the BAU scenario in 2050 remains below 10% (while at World level it ranges 19-38% for the IMI & GSO pathways), and circular economy measures partially buffer the impact of additional demand on forest & SRP biomass.

Area of forest management classes and short rotation plantations

The projected changes in the area forest (distinguished by management classes) and short rotation plantation (SRP) across the different scenarios are presented in Figure 15. In the BAU scenario, no additional afforestation occurs and deforestation continues at a slightly reduced pace, leading to a net loss of forest cover (excl. SRP) of 215 million hectares (Mha) over 2020-2050. The management of existing forests is expected to intensify in response to the increasing wood demand for material use, with an increase in semi-natural forest under production-oriented management (+105 Mha) and a decrease in multifunctional management (-42 Mha). SRP for both energy and material use remain constant. Most changes are projected to occur in ROW, although some forest intensification occurs in EUR and some deforestation occurs in NAM-ANZ.

In the VITAL-Paths-Food scenarios, the area of both forests and, for IMI, short rotation plantations is expected to increase. The projected reduction in deforestation (through exogenous trends in deforestation) and the increase in re/afforestation efforts (through the assumed type-1 restoration efforts) lead to net forest gains from 2030 onwards. By 2050, accumulated deforestation since 2020 is more strongly reduced in GSO (17 Mha) than in LCS (55 Mha), and even more so, IMI (112 Mha), while accumulated afforestation is slightly lower in LCS (375 Mha) than in

IMI & GSO (resp. 464 and 478 Mha). By 2050, as compared to the BAU scenario, net forest cover gains in the range of +15-18% are projected, slightly higher for GSO than for IMI (due to lower deforestation reduction) and LCS (due to lower afforestation). This highlights that through restoration and deforestation control combined, net changes in forest cover are affected by multiple narrative elements that can play on both directions within a single pathway.

As compared to the BAU in 2050, forests are also projected to undergo a small extensification in GSO, through a net decrease in both multifunctional semi-natural forests (through the forest protection as part of conservation intervention bundle) and production-oriented semi-natural forests (through circular economy measures of the demand-side intervention bundle), to the benefit of natural forests under no or limited pressure. A similar but slightly different picture occurs in IMI, with a small increase in multifunctional semi-natural forest, a larger decrease in production-oriented semi-natural forest, with some of the pressure displaced from forest to abandoned agricultural land and other natural land, through the increased reliance on SRP (assumed as part of the supply-side intervention bundle). In the LCS pathway, semi-natural forest under production-oriented management slightly decrease in 2050 as compared to the BAU scenario, while both semi-natural forest under multifunctional management and natural forest under no or low extractive pressure only increase.

D5.3 – Lessons learned from the quantification of the pathways

Figure 15: Projected changes in forest and short rotation plantation area, with a split of forest area by forest type (re/afforestation vs existing forest) and, for existing forests, by management type (close-to-nature or unharvested primary and secondary natural forests, semi-natural forests with multifunctional management, and semi-natural forests with production-oriented management). The upper panel provides absolute changes in area as compared to 2020 (in million hectare Mha) for the BAU and the VITAL-Paths-Food scenarios, while the middle (resp. lower) panel provides at the World (resp. EUR) level the differences in 2050 between the decomposition scenarios and the BAU scenario, normalized by the total forest area (i.e., excl. SRP) in BAU by 2050.

In addition to changes in forest cover and management, the area dedicated to short rotation plantations is expected to increase in the IMI pathway by +108 million hectares as compared to the BAU scenario in 2050.

Across all scenarios, changes to SRP area, as well as most changes to total forest area and management, are primarily occurring in in the ROW region in absolute terms. The picture is more mixed in relative terms. The increase in total forest area (excl. SRP) in the VITAL-Paths-Food pathways as compared to the BAU scenario in 2050 is close to half lower at EUR level than at World level for the IMI (18% at World level vs 8% at EUR level) and GSO (15% vs 9%) pathways, but ambitions are more comparable for the LCS pathway (15% vs 13%). This reflects the relatively lower importance of deforestation as a driver in EUR, but also slightly afforestation ambitions, except for the LCS pathway. However, the share of existing forests converted from semi-natural forest under production-oriented management to lower intensity is higher at EUR than World level for the GSO pathway (6.3% vs 1.5%) and to a lower extent for the IMI pathway (9.4% vs 6.3%), but that pattern is reversed in the LCS pathway (1.7% vs 3.9%).

3.2 Distribution of impacts on the environment, consumers and producers across regions and pathways

3.2.1 Land use, AFOLU GHG emissions and agricultural inputs

Land use

Figure 16 presents global land use change in the different land use categories (Cropland, Pasture, Short rotation plantations, Abandoned agricultural land, Nature-friendly afforestation, Non-forest restoration, Forest existing in year 2000, and Other natural land) in 2050 compared to 2020 at EUR, NAM-ANZ, ROW regions and World level for the core scenarios, as well as the difference to BAU in 2050 for the decomposition scenarios at World and EUR level.

In the BAU, and as previously discussed (section 3.1.5), we project a net loss in forest areas of 215 Mha compared to 2020, with 94% of the loss happening outside of EUR and NAM-ANZ. This goes together with an increase in agricultural lands (+ 57 Mha cropland and + 78 Mha pasture), also primarily in ROW, in line with the projected increase in production and consumption in BAU (see section 3.1.3).

In contrast to BAU, all three pathways are characterized by much lower deforestation and an increase in restoration (primarily in the form of nature-friendly afforestation) at the expense of cropland and pasture. Restoration to nature-friendly afforestation and non-forest restoration reaches 453 Mha (LCS scenario) to 477 Mha (GSO scenario) at World level compared to 2020 (range by 2030: 234-244 Mha). While most occurs in ROW regions, the amount of restoration is notably higher in EUR and NAM-ANZ in LCS and GSO as compared to IMI. At EUR level, by 2050 restoration as nature-friendly afforestation is projected to reach 13 Mha in the GSO pathway to 22 Mha in the LCS pathway (range 2030: 2-9 Mha), which represents a similar (resp. slightly higher) share of total land than at World level for IMI & GSO pathways (resp. LCS pathway). Avoided deforestation represents a much lower share of total land at EU than at World level.

D5.3 – Lessons learned from the quantification of the pathways

Figure 16: Projected changes in land use, split by land use category (color bars) The upper panel provides absolute changes in land use area as compared to 2020 (in million hectare) for the BAU and the VITAL-Paths-Food scenarios, while the bottom panel provides relative differences in 2050 between the decomposition scenarios and the BAU scenario, normalized to total land area (%), at the World & EUR levels.

This reflects the different mechanisms driving restoration in the pathways (see section 3.1.2). Type-1 restoration mainly occurs through minimum efforts towards

global restoration targets in IMI and GSO, with a large share assumed to occur in ROW, even if equity principles underlying their distribution vary across pathways. For the LCS pathway, the minimum restoration targets however lead to a lower target for type-1 restoration in EUR: while the distribution of total (type-1 and type-2 combined) restoration efforts leads to higher restoration in EUR as compared to other pathways, it prioritizes type-2 restoration over type-1 restoration. However, this pathway additionally assumes a progressive restoration of abandoned agricultural land, leading to comparable amount of type-1 restoration globally, and higher amounts in EUR. This leads to type-1 restoration in EUR and NAM-ANZ being higher in LCS than other pathways, and a higher relative contribution at EUR than at World level.

As a result of the supply assumptions there is an increase in Short Rotation Plantations in IMI, which occurs almost exclusively in ROW regions. At EUR level changes are largely influenced by changes on the demand side, especially in the LCS pathway, where overall changes due to the demand interventions are also substantially larger than in the other pathways.

GHG emissions

Figure 17 below presents the change in AFOLU GHG emissions between 2020 and 2050 across the core scenarios, as well as the difference in emissions between the decomposition scenarios and the BAU by 2050. AFOLU GHG emissions are differentiated by sources, between crop (CRP) and livestock (LSP) non-CO₂ emissions from agriculture, changes in soil organic carbon from agricultural land (SOC), as well as land use change (LUC) and forest management (FORM). While CRP and LSP are net emissions, LUC, SOC and FORM can be either a net source or a net sink (in which case, positive values indicates a weakening of the sink).

In BAU, global livestock and crop emissions are projected to increase by 893 Mt CO₂eq/yr, particularly in ROW regions (+ 807 Mt CO₂eq/yr). On the other hand, LUC emissions decline by 1845 Mt CO₂eq/yr, following a limited reduction in deforestation rate. Forest management sink decreases, as a result of a shift in the forest age class distribution towards older forests. The FORM source is however

notoriously uncertain², and is excluded from the total in BAU by 2050 used as a normalization factor to compare differences to the BAU scenario by 2050 in Figure 17 b).

The net GHG balance from the AFOLU sector is significantly lower (i.e., higher sink) for all three VITAL pathway scenarios. The largest absolute emission reductions relate to LUC emissions (-3.2 to -5.0 GtCO₂eq/yr as compared to BAU in 2050 globally), in particular in ROW regions. However, the magnitude of the LUC emission reductions, the trends in other emission sources, and the response to intervention bundles differ across pathways and regions. The largest reductions in LUC emissions occur in GSO and represent 64% of total AFOLU emissions in BAU 2050 (excl. FORM) as illustrated in Figure 17b). IMI and LCS reach respectively a reduction corresponding to 47% and 41%. As illustrated in Figure 17 b), the trends in LUC emissions are primarily affected by efforts to limit deforestation (as part of the climate mitigation intervention bundle, with efforts in GSO and lowest in IMI) and afforestation (as part of the conservation intervention bundle). The relatively lower reduction of LUC emissions in LCS as compared to other VITAL pathways (for relatively similar amounts of afforestation) stems partly from a higher proportion of afforestation in temperate regions (instead of tropical regions), and delayed afforestation (leading to limited sink by 2050).

The projected reduction in livestock and crops emissions represents a comparable source of reductions in the GHG emissions from the AFOLU sector (-3.5 to -3.8 GtCO₂eq/yr as compared to BAU by 2050, excl. soil organic sequestration in agricultural land), representing in the GSO, IMI and LCS pathways about 44%-49% of total GHG AFOLU emissions (excl. FORM) in 2050 for the BAU scenario. These reductions are primarily driven by the climate mitigation intervention bundle, with adoption of mitigation technologies across livestock, pasture and cropland. In addition, reductions in meat consumption, either through transition to Eat-Lancet diets (in LCS and to a lower extent GSO), or through replacing it by NPBA (IMI and to a lower extent GSO), are projected to result in additional reductions, in particular in EUR. Lastly, adoption of alternative agriculture management practices through

² With a global estimate of -6.6 GtCO₂eq/yr for the 2010-2020 period, our estimate lies within the range (-8.7 to -0.2 GtCO₂eq/yr for the 2011-2020 average) found across estimates contained in the version 3.1 of the LULUCF Data Hub (NGHGI 2025 release, (Melo et al., 2026))

restoration targets (Cons), or assumed extensification (Sup, for LCS), contribute to additional, much smaller, reductions.

A small share of emission reduction is driven by SOC increases in agricultural soils (representing for the LCS, IMI and GSO pathways 8%, 18%, 21% of total AFOLU emissions excl. FORM in the BAU by 2050), with however higher values in 2030 than in 2050. This reflects the large early deployment of soil management measures, primarily through the climate mitigation intervention bundle (see 3.1.3). However the effect of this measure rapidly reaches saturation as soils approach their equilibrium, assumed after 20 years ((Frank et al., 2024), following IPCC guidelines).

We project relatively less variation in the sink from forest management between the BAU and the VITAL-Paths-Food pathways, with similar projected decrease over time due to aging of forests. However, the IMI pathways is projected to more strongly deviate from the BAU trend, with an additional sink reduction associated with the forest management intensification following the increase in demand for biomass (BAU_IMI-Clim), more than compensated for by forest management deintensification from circular economy measures (BAU_IMI-Dem) and the expansion of roundwood short rotation plantations (BAU_IMI-Sup).

At EUR level, emissions are slightly more reduced in the LCS pathway than in the two others (126% in LCS vs 97-103% in GSO and IMI as compared to total EUR AFOLU emissions exc. FORM), while at global scale we observe the opposite with slightly higher proportional reduction for the IMI and GSO pathways (118-127%), than for LCS (100%). The reductions in livestock and crop emissions dominate (with a larger contribution from demand-side interventions comparatively to the global scale), while the contribution from the LUC emission reduction / sink enhancement is comparatively lower (and more clearly dominated by the type-1 restoration from the conservation intervention bundle).

D5.3 – Lessons learned from the quantification of the pathways

Figure 17: Projected changes in GHG emissions, with a split of emissions by emission source (CRP: Croplands, LSP: livestock, LUC: land use change, FORM: Carbon sequestration, SOC: soil organic carbon). The upper panel provides absolute changes in emissions as compared to 2020 (in million tonnes CO₂eq per year) for the BAU and the VITAL-Paths-Food scenarios, while the lower panel provides at the World and EUR level the differences in 2050 between the decomposition scenarios and the BAU scenario, normalized by the total emissions in BAU by 2050

Agricultural inputs and losses over cropland

Figure 18 presents the absolute changes in cropland nitrogen and phosphorus surplus compared to 2020 for BAU and the Vital-Paths Food, split by regions (upper panel), as well as the change compared to BAU 2050 for the decomposition scenarios, in Europe and globally, normalized by the total surplus in BAU in 2050 (lower panel).

In BAU we observe an increase in Nitrogen surplus globally (+26 Mt), especially in BRA and SSA, in line with increasing crop production, and nitrogen use efficiency patterns. On the other hand, we project a 5 Mt decrease in phosphorus surplus globally, primarily in CHN and IND.

In the VITAL-Paths, the global cropland nutrient surplus is projected to decrease by 2050 as compared to 2020 (range across pathways: -46% to -54% for nitrogen, and -98% to -100% for phosphorous). Measures from the supply-side intervention bundle alone would be sufficient to reach at least half (or more, for phosphorous) of the total reduction observed in the full pathways, while measures from the demand-side (in particular for LCS), climate mitigation and conservation bundles provide additional contributions. Geographical patterns of surplus reductions across pathways are similar and largely driven by a few large regions with relatively low NUE in 2020: CHN, IND, BRA and SEA. In GSO and IMI, for both phosphorus and nitrogen surplus, the largest share of the reductions occurs by 2030, reflecting the earlier implementation of improvements in nutrient use efficiency (NUE) (see section 3.1.3). In contrast, in LCS, the reduction is relatively linear, in relation to the assumed slower phasing of assumed NUE trends as well as demand-side measures (see section 3.1.1).

At EUR level we project in 2050 a reduction in nitrogen (resp. phosphorus) surplus compared to BAU in 2050 of 13% (resp. 135%) in IMI, 12% (resp. 145%) in GSO and 21% (resp. 90%) in LCS. As compared to the World level, the decrease in nitrogen surplus as compared to the BAU scenario by 2050 is systematically lower in relative terms, and the role of measures in the supply-side intervention bundle is much lower (with even an increase in nitrogen surplus in LCS).

D5.3 – Lessons learned from the quantification of the pathways

Figure 18: Projected changes in nitrogen and phosphorus surplus, with a split by region. The upper panel provides absolute changes in emissions as compared to 2020 (in million tonnes N or P per year) for the BAU and the VITAL-Paths-Food scenarios, while the middle (resp. lower) panel provides at the World (resp. EUR) level the differences in 2050 between the decomposition scenarios and the BAU scenario, normalized by the total surplus in BAU by 2050

Figure 19 presents the projected change in pesticides applied to croplands as estimated in the different pathways and BAU compared to 2020, as well the relative change to the total pesticide application in BAU in 2050 for the decomposition scenarios.

Under BAU, a small increase is observed in 2030 (about +1% as compared to 2020 globally), driven by higher agricultural production, as pesticide application rates are assumed to remain at 2020 levels in this pathway. In contrast, the three pathways show a steep decline from 2030 onwards, with reductions of about 48% (GSO) to 66% (LCS) by 2050 as compared to 2020. In the pathways, a large part of the reduction happens in a few regions (SEA, BRA, USA) with large crop production volume and high baseline application rates.

As shown by the decomposition analysis, this outcome is related to different mechanisms in the different scenarios. The decline in pesticide use in LCS is primarily associated with the expansion of organic farming, both for achieving the restoration target, and due to the extensification trends assumed as part of the supply intervention bundle as well as a small contribution from demand-side interventions. In GSO and IMI, reductions are mainly driven by supply side improvements, reflecting assumptions of convergence away from currently very high pesticide application rates in some countries toward lower, more sustainable levels, particularly for the most hazardous substances.

In Europe, reductions in relative terms are lower than at world level (e.g., -20% in IMI and -26% in GSO in EUR vs -55% and -52% in the world as compared to BAU in 2050) except for the LCS pathway (-75% in EUR vs -68%). In IMI & GSO, this relatively lower ambition comes with less dominant role of the supply-side intervention bundle and is due to a lower share of EUR in the global risk from pesticide. In LCS, the relative pesticide reduction and the role of the conservation intervention bundle are more comparable between EUR and World level, as the type-2 restoration target underpinning the conversion to organic farming is relatively high for EUR, and the application rate of all pesticides (even if not representing a large share of global risk) is reduced by 100% when switching to organic (instead of 40% when targeting most risky pesticide x crop x region combinations in IMI & GSO).

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Figure 19: Projected changes in pesticide applied to cropland, with a split by region. The upper panel provides absolute changes in pesticide application as compared to 2020 (in million tonnes per year) for the BAU and the VITAL-Paths-Food scenarios, while the lower panel provides at the World & EUR level the differences in 2050 between the decomposition scenarios and the BAU scenario, normalized by the total pesticides in BAU by 2050.

3.2.2 Biodiversity

Extinction risks from agricultural activities

Figure 20: Projected changes in extinction risks from agricultural activities, as measured in terms of Potentially Disappeared Fraction (PDF.y) of global species richness, with a split by ecosystem (rows; LCTE= terrestrial ecosystems, LCFE = freshwater ecosystems, LCME = marine ecosystems), pressure (colors; climate change, eutrophication, ecotoxicity, water stress, land occupation and land transformation) and region (columns), as compared to 2020 for the BAU and the VITAL-Paths-Food scenarios.

Figure 20 presents the absolute change in biodiversity impacts (PDF.y) across regions and ecosystem types, split by pressure for the three Vital-Path-Food and

BAU, as compared to 2020. The results broadly reflect the results on pressures presented in the previous section (3.2.1). Additionally,

Figure 21 below presents the relative changes in biodiversity impact in 2050 as compared to BAU, both in Europe and globally, normalised to the total impact by 2050 in BAU. It should be noted that this metric should be interpreted as change in global risks from local changes in pressures associated with agriculture and forestry

sectors, within each realm³. It should also be noted that impacts reported for a specific time horizon are annualized impacts associated with annualized underlying pressures (i.e., amount of land allocated to various land uses in 1 year for land occupation), but in some cases include cumulative impacts over time (e.g., land transformation provides impacts cumulated over the time required for effective restoration, once the occupation would cease). It therefore cannot be interpreted as biodiversity state indicator, such as portion of global species richness at risk of extinction for the related time horizon.

In the BAU scenario, the impact on terrestrial (+4% globally), freshwater (+8% globally) and marine ecosystems (+34% globally) is projected to increase or remain relatively stable across most regions, as compared to 2020. The main increases are due to water stress in NAM-ANZ region (for freshwater ecosystems⁴), Eutrophication in ROW (for marine ecosystems), and land occupation in ROW (for terrestrial ecosystems).

The three pathways generally depict a decrease in biodiversity impact as compared to 2020, ranging across pathway by 2050 from -25% (IMI & GSO) to -33% (LCS) for terrestrial ecosystems (range 2030: -19% to -60%), from -2% (LCS) to -13% (GSO) for freshwater ecosystems (range 2030: -2% to 2%), and from -33% (GSO) to -44% (LCS) for marine ecosystems (range 2030: -20% to -36%). However, the relative reduction varies across regions, as do the importance of various biodiversity pressures in some ecosystems: for example, reductions as compared to the BAU in 2050 are larger in relative terms at EUR than at World level for the GSO pathway (while more comparable for IMI & LCS) in terrestrial ecosystems, while for marine ecosystems reductions are systematically lower at EUR level than at World level (with a lower reduction in eutrophication impacts in EUR). For freshwater ecosystems, reductions are slightly higher in relative terms at EUR level, but dominated by

³ E.g., the impacts reported for terrestrial ecosystems and land occupation for the EUR region depicts impacts associated with land use change (which only affect local terrestrial ecosystems), and local GHG emissions (which affects all terrestrial ecosystems globally). It therefore does not account for the full amount of pressures generated by the economy (i.e., climate change impacts does not include GHG emissions from other economic sectors), does not take a ‘consumer’ perspective (by ignoring impacts from imported products), but capture impacts on distant ecosystems (impacts from GHG emissions in EUR on ecosystems in another continent

⁴ It should be noted that for freshwater ecosystems, the impacts from water stress dominates that of other pressures, and are particularly high in the USA (water stress impact in the USA dominates total freshwater ecosystem impacts across world regions and pressures).

different pressures: climate change and ecotoxicity at EUR level, vs water stress at World level. The relatively lower impact reduction at global level for freshwater ecosystems as compared to other ecosystems may relate to the lack of assumptions about irrigation water abstraction efficiency.

In terrestrial ecosystems, biodiversity improvements associated with reduced land occupation and land transformation are generally more pronounced in IMI and GSO than in LCS, especially in ROW regions. It should be noted that our results are influenced by methodological assumptions in the land-use impact assessment. In particular, the LC-Impact characterization factors do not account for differences in management intensity, likely leading to an underestimation of the biodiversity gains of the VITAL-Paths-Food scenarios for terrestrial biodiversity over agricultural land⁵, and of the nuances across pathways in the preferred types of sustainable management practices. The methodology is however able to capture such benefits for freshwater and marine ecosystems, through explicit estimates of ecotoxicological risks from pesticides inputs and eutrophication risks from nutrient losses.

The decomposition analysis highlights that the terrestrial biodiversity impact are strongly linked to conservation and climate mitigation intervention bundles, reflecting the dominant contribution of avoided natural land loss and type-1 restoration. However, as mentioned in the previous paragraph, the benefits from more sustainable agricultural management practices (as part of the same intervention bundles, but also of the supply-side intervention bundle) on terrestrial ecosystems are underestimated. Similarly, the impact of the demand-side intervention bundle is likely underestimated, as without combination with the restoration intervention bundle (as done in the full pathway), the large amounts of abandoned land are assumed to remain with a relatively limited biodiversity value. The decomposition of impacts for freshwater and marine ecosystems reflects the differences between World and EUR level on the dominant pressures (e.g., water stress at World level vs climate change and eutrophication at EUR level for freshwater ecosystems), and on the impact of various intervention bundles on the

⁵ Future work could address this limitation by applying land-use characterization factors that differentiate between low- and high-intensity land use, such as those proposed by Scherer et al. (2023). Uncertainties in the specific impact of management intensity is however highly uncertain (Ceașu et al., 2025).

related pressures (see section 3.2.1).

Figure 21: Projected change in biodiversity impacts in 2050 compared to BAU, in the three realms (LCTE: terrestrial, LCFE: freshwater and LCME: marine) and split per pressure (Climate change, Eutrophication, Land transformation, Land occupation, Ecotoxicity, Water stress) for the decomposition scenarios, for World and EUR. (2320)

Integrity of ecosystems

Figure 22: Projected MSA changes across regions for BAU and the VITAL-Paths Food as compared to 2020, for vertebrates (MSAV) and plants (MSAP), with the contribution of climate change and land use pressure to the total MSA.

Figure 22 shows changes in biodiversity intactness (MSA) for vertebrates (left) and plants (right) in 2030 and 2050 as compared to 2020, separating the contributions of climate change and land use pressures. Figure 23 presents the changes in 2050 compared to BAU across the decomposition scenarios, normalized to the total MSA losses in BAU in 2050, in Europe as well as in the world. In contrast to the LC_IMPACT

extinction risk metric, the MSA estimates capture total impacts from land use and climate pressures (i.e., GHG emissions from the entire economy are accounted for) on the ecosystems within a given region, and changes in MSA in a given region from one time step to another can be interpreted as a change in biodiversity state variable. However, it should be noted that i) potential delays from biodiversity recovery (e.g., from land restoration) are not included, and that ii) losses related to climate change are estimated at the global level and do not vary across regions within each pathway (differences across regions in a given pathway are solely driven by changes in land use)⁶.

In BAU, losses from climate change are projected globally both for vertebrates (-0.014) and plants (-0.026), compared to 2020. Additionally, land use changes induce further losses of smaller magnitude globally, with larger effects at regional level (e.g., in BRA, SEA and OSA).

Across the three VITAL-Paths-Food pathways, impacts from the climate pressure are significantly reduced but remain negative, while a reversal stronger reductions in land use pressure (with net gain in natural ecosystems) generate biodiversity improvements in most regions compared to 2020, for both vertebrates and plants: largest land use related biodiversity changes for plants are in IND in GSO (+0.07), IMI (+0.06) and LCS (+0.03). The gains from reduced land use impact reduction are however slower for LCS than for the other two pathways, due to a slower uptake of type-1 restoration. Nevertheless, by 2050 these gains nearly offset the losses from climate change for vertebrates and plants in most regions, but the offset is generally smaller for plants since climate change has a larger impact on plants than on vertebrates. As a result at the global level, net biodiversity change by 2050 as compared to 2020 is positive or close to zero in the three pathways for vertebrates, and close to zero for plants, with the highest positive changes in GSO (+0.0067 for vertebrates and 0.0003 for plants) and the lowest for LCS (-0.0047 for vertebrates and -0.0064 for plants). By contrast, in Europe, LCS projects the highest biodiversity changes.

As compared to BAU in 2050, the reductions in biodiversity loss are generally

⁶ In reality, the impacts of climate change on biodiversity are expected to be much more contrasted across regions, and regional values from climate change (and total effects) should be interpreted with care

higher in relative terms at world than at EUR level, except for the LCS pathway, where losses in relative terms are comparable at world and EUR.

The decomposition analysis shows the dominant role of the climate mitigation intervention bundle on reducing the impacts climate pressure⁷, and a more mixed picture for the contribution of various intervention bundles on reducing the land use pressure. For the latter, the conservation intervention bundles consistently plays a large role across plant and vertebrate species groups, and across World and EUR regions. The supply-side intervention (in particular for IMI, but more for vertebrates than for plants, and more at World than at EUR level) and demand-side intervention bundle plays an important as well (in particular for LCS and GSO, but more for vertebrates than for plants, and more at EUR than at World level)⁸. The climate mitigation intervention bundle also plays a stronger role in shaping the land use related impact on vertebrates than on plants. This likely reflects the higher estimated sensitivity of vertebrates to reductions in cropland intensity in Globio (Schipper et al, 2020), leading to a larger beneficial impact for vertebrates than for plants, from the adoption of alternative sustainable agricultural management practices. The main differences across pathways are also reflected, with a higher influence of the supply assumptions in IMI, while demand bundle has a larger impact in LCS, especially for vertebrates in Europe.

⁷ It should be noted that this relates to reductions in GHG emissions from not only the AFOLU sector (as presented in section 3.2.1), but also the rest of the economy (see App-Table 4 in the Appendix section)

⁸ It should be noted that impacts presented here are relatively pessimistic about the biodiversity value of the large amounts of abandoned land demand side intervention bundle, restored only when combined with the conservation intervention bundle

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Figure 23: Projected difference to BAU in MSA by 2050 across the decomposition scenarios, for vertebrates (MSAV) and plants (MSAP), with the contribution of climate change and land use pressure to the total losses, normalized to the total MSA value in BAU in 2050

3.2.2 Agricultural producers

Value of production

Figure 24 presents the projected changes in value of production, defined as the product between production and producer price, relative to 2020 for the VITAL-Paths Food and BAU, as well as the changes in 2050 compared to BAU for the decomposition scenarios both in Europe and globally.

In BAU, we project a 21% increase in value added globally, corresponding to a 30% increase in ROW partially buffered by small decreases in EUR (5%) and NAM-ANZ (11%), with the livestock sector contributing to 59% of the global increase.

In contrast to BAU, a loss in the value of agricultural production is observed across all the VITAL-Paths-Food by 2050 as compared to 2020, with enhanced losses in EUR and NAM-ANZ regions and much lower increase in ROW. At World level, losses as compared to BAU in 2050 are higher for LCS (-36%) than for GSO and IMI (-19%).

Most reductions in the value of agricultural production are driven by declines in the livestock sector, whereas increases are projected as compared to 2020 for crop production in IMI by 2050 at global level, and for all pathways at ROW level (although much less than in BAU). These patterns largely reflect changes in consumption (see section 3.1.1), as shown by the decomposition analysis. In IMI and GSO, some of the losses are compensated by the climate and conservation bundles, but also the trade assumptions in IMI in Europe.

Figure 24: Projected changes in value of production, with a split between crop and livestock products. The upper panel (a) provides absolute changes in value of production as compared to 2020 (in billion USD 2000) for the BAU and the VITAL-Paths-Food scenarios, while the lower panel (b) provides relative differences (in percentage) in 2050 between the decomposition scenarios and the BAU scenario.

Figure 25 provides a closer look at the change in the value of production for the crop sector normalized per hectare, as a proxy of changes in farming revenue (i.e., adjusted for decrease or increase in cropland). In BAU, we project a decrease by 2050 as compared to 2020 in the value of production per hectare in NAM-ANZ (-335 USD per ha, -25%) and EUR (-116USD per ha, -5%), but an increase in ROW (+144 USD

per ha, +9%), resulting in a net increase of 98 USD per ha at global level (+6%). Across pathways, as compared to BAU in 2050, we project a higher 2020-2050 increase in the value of production per ha at World level, three times larger for IMI (+18%), twice larger for GSO (+11% at World level), while LCS lies in between (+15% at World level). Trends from 2020 to 2050 are slightly better than in the BAU at EUR level in IMI (-1%) and LCS (+1%) but not GSO (-8%), systematically (but only marginally, except in LCS) better in NAM-ANZ, and systematically and significantly better for ROW. The contribution of the different bundles differs as compared to that projected for the value of production, with a lower influence from demand-side intervention bundle, and a higher influence from the conservation intervention bundle (in particular for GSO and LCS), and the trade intervention bundle in IMI. However, there are significant interactions across interventions: for example in IMI, at both World and EUR levels the net gain is much smaller than the sum of effects across the IMI decomposition scenarios. It should also be mentioned that, by 2030 decreases in the value of production per hectare of cropland as compared to the BAU are expected for all pathways in all regions (and in particular for EUR). This points to potentially larger risks for crop producers on the short term,

Projections in value of production, even when measured per hectare, is a very partial view on the economic impacts for farmers (Blockeel et al., 2025; Moret-Bailly & Muro, 2024). First, it ignores changes in operating costs in relation to input use, which are expected to decrease in all VITAL-Paths-Food scenarios in significant proportions (thereby potentially also leading to unitary input price decreases). At the same time, the adoption of sustainable management practices underlying these trends may require increases in some operational costs (e.g., labor, services) and is expected to require upfront capital costs associated to machinery and/or training. In addition, producers adopting such practices may be able to access specific payment for ecosystem services and consumers may, to some extent, be ready to pay higher prices for more sustainable products, with uncertainties about the transmission of such price premium through supply chains all the way to the farmer. All these aspects are expected to be contextual across pathways, types of farmers and regions, in relation to the production orientation, the type of practices assumed and their present-day uptake, and the evolution of the governance of agricultural production and supply chains. These aspects were pointed to during a stakeholder

workshop as of particular importance to better understand the impact of the adoption of sustainable production practices on farmers. While the following sections provide some illustration of these aspects, our approach remains limited and additional work, employing complementary methodologies, will be required to capture these aspects.

Figure 25: Projected changes in crop value of production per ha. The upper panel (a) provides absolute changes in value of production as compared to 2020 (in USD 2000 per ha) for the BAU and the VITAL-Paths-Food scenarios, while the lower panel (b) provides relative differences (in percentage) in 2050 between the decomposition scenarios and the BAU scenario.

Value from carbon removal in agricultural soils

Figure 26 represents the estimated total value of carbon removals within agricultural soils (upper panel) and, for the area of crops represented in the model, the change in the per hectare value of carbon removal and value of production, as compared to 2050 in BAU. In BAU we assume no adoption in SOC removal measures, and no associated value of carbon removal. This provides an example of the role of potential revenue streams to the farmers associated by the adoption of more sustainable practices, and how they could play out in the pathways.

At World level, we project by 2050 a total value of carbon removals in agricultural soils of 16, 132 and 182 billion USD2000 per year in respectively the LCS, GSO and IMI pathways. Removal of soil organic carbon is projected in all regions, with however a high share in the ROW region (in particular in Latin America and Asia), in the USA and to some extent, in EUR. While SOC removal rates saturate two decades (see section 3.2.2), this is partially compensated by an increasing carbon price value over time.

As illustrated for cropland in the bottom panel, while production levels are expected to decrease in VITAL-Paths-Food scenarios as compared to the BAU, this is not necessarily the case per hectare and the value of carbon removals in agricultural soils could represent a significant contribution to farming revenue streams. Adding up the value of carbon removal per hectare change in cropland to change in the value of production per hectare of cropland leads to a doubling of the increases in potential revenue in the IMI & GSO pathways at the World level. For these two pathways, the value of carbon removal per hectare of cropland provides a comparatively larger contribution than that of the value of production per hectare of cropland in NAM-ANZ and EUR (where it fully compensate for the losses in the value of production per hectare of cropland for GSO). In contrast, in the LCS pathway market instruments are assumed limited and a low value of carbon removals cannot counterbalance the more significant decreases in the value of production. In that pathway, the economic situation of farmers may however be improved by significantly lower operating costs, due to reduced input levels (even though partially canceled by higher labor requirements).

Figure 26: Projected changes in the total value of carbon removal (upper panel; calculated as the product of the carbon price and the carbon removed in agricultural soils via soil organic carbon measures) by region (colored bars), and, for cropland area occupied by the 18 crops covered in the model, in the difference in the per hectare value of the carbon removal in agricultural soils and the per hectare value of production by large regions (bottom panel).

Farm labor requirements in crop production

Figure 27 shows the projected crop labor requirements at farm level. Agricultural employment represents less than 5% of total employment in EUR and NAM-ANZ, but more than 30% in many countries of Asia and Sub-Saharan Africa, where large changes

in agricultural labor may have comparatively larger socio-economic implications.

In the BAU scenario, we project an increase in labor requirements as compared to 2020, primarily in SSA & IND. This corresponds to a relative increase of 9.6% and 3.8% at respectively World and EUR level. Labor requirements are instead projected to decrease by 2050 across all VITAL-Paths-Food scenarios as compared to 2020, with decreases in non-OECD countries of -10% in the LCS pathway, -12% in GSO and -16% in IMI. The largest reductions occur in major producing regions such as CHN, IND, and SEA. However, in relative terms, declines are comparable at EUR and World levels, except for the LCS pathway (29% from 2020 to 2050 at EUR level, vs 10% at World level), reflecting the relatively larger decrease in crop supply in EUR (see section 3.1.4), even though decreases in labor requirements are half lower than that of crop supply. Decreases are highest in CHN and IND (in both relative and absolute terms), while SSA stands as an exception, with increases as compared to 2020 and 2050 levels slightly below (IMI, GSO) or comparable (LCS) to BAU.

Changes in production volume are a key driver, incl. demand-side interventions (see 3.1.4). The latter also has an impact through changes in crop composition. Changes to the composition of cropland in terms of agricultural management practices (conservation intervention bundle, as well as for LCS, supply-side intervention bundle, see 3.1.3) have an even higher impact, with lower (resp. higher) labor requirement per hectare for precision farming (resp. organic farming). It should however be noted that labor requirements across crops and cropping systems are uncertain. The decomposition analysis shows that, as compared to the BAU scenario by 2050, the impacts from the conservation intervention bundle are negative for IMI & GSO (through precision-farming adoption) at World and EUR level, but a slightly positive impact in the LCS pathway at World level (through organic-farming adoption). In this pathway, the supply-side intervention bundle has a larger positive

impact. The demand-side intervention bundle has a negative impact, largest in LCS.

Figure 27: Projected change in crop employment across the Vital-Paths compared to 2020 (a) split by farm type and countries in absolute terms, and (b) as percentage change relative to 2020 employment

It should be noted that our estimates are likely to overestimate future agricultural labor requirements in most scenarios, and to underestimate the deviation to BAU (towards lower labor requirements) associated with the more technology-driven

VITAL-Paths-Food scenarios (IMI, and to some extent GSO). First, if defined as a prolongation of historical trends, in the BAU scenario agricultural employment may be expected to decrease (rather than increase), through increases in total factor productivity (TFP) (Fuglie et al., 2024), which are not captured in our future estimate. It might also be reasonable to expect a differentiation of future TFP growth across pathways, highest for IMI and lowest for LCS. The larger reduction in crop labor requirement projected for IMI as compared to LCS may therefore be amplified when accounting for TFP effects. This might also be the case due to rural-urban migration, another factor affecting agricultural employment not factored in our analysis (Mizik et al., 2025), and expected to be strongest in IMI and lowest in LCS. In addition, our approach is restricted to annual crops explicitly represented in the GLOBIOM model. While this means we may miss the increased labor requirements associated with the increased production of vegetables, fruits and nuts in the LCS pathway, the significant reduction in livestock production projected in our scenario is expected to generate a significant number of additional workers released from agriculture.

3.2.3 Consumers

Risks of undernourishment

Figure 28 presents projections of the population at risk of undernourishment across the core scenarios (for ROW region, as we don't project undernourishment in EUR and NAM-ANZ regions), as well as the change compared to BAU for the decomposed scenarios. It informs on risks of hunger, and is responsive to trends in food availability through endogenous changes in production and consumption volumes, but also food access through endogenous changes in prices and exogenous trends in within-country inequalities in food consumption.

A significant reduction is projected from 2020 to 2050 in the BAU scenario (from 868 to 430 million people, i.e., -51%), primarily due to faster increases in production than in demand. Even higher reductions are projected for all three VITAL-Paths-Food pathways, already in 2030. By 2050, undernourishment is nearly eliminated in GSO and LCS, while some undernourishment persists in IMI (144 million people).

These trends largely reflect assumptions from the demand-side intervention bundle, in particular regarding the inequality of food distribution across scenarios (see section 3.1.1). However, the decomposition analysis also shows adverse effects can be expected from the conservation, climate mitigation intervention bundles, as well as, for LCS, the trade intervention bundle. These adverse effects stem from the impact of these intervention bundles on production levels (see 3.1.4) and prices in key regions like IND and SSA.

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Figure 28: Projected evolution of the undernourished population in the scenarios and change in undernourished population compared to BAU in 2020 (panel a) and in the different decomposition runs compared to BAU in 2050 (panel b)

Health impacts from food consumption

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Figure 29 shows the evolution of years of life lost (YLL) due to diet-related diseases from 2020 to 2030 and 2050 for the core scenarios, and as well as the relative impact of the different interventions. The risk of diseases increases by 74% in the BAU scenario, because of increases in population and an evolution of dietary preferences reflecting historical trends. In contrast, despite the same population trajectory, we project a clear reduction in health impacts from food consumption all VITAL-Paths-Food: as compared to 2020, by 2050 the risks are reduced by 43% in the IMI pathway 74% in the GSO pathway, and 99% in the LCS pathway.

Figure 29: Projected changes in the health impacts from food consumption (measured in years of life lost YLL from diet-related diseases), with a split between crop and livestock products. The upper panel (a) provides absolute changes in YLL as compared to 2020 (in million years) for the BAU and the VITAL-Paths-Food scenarios, while the lower panel (b) provides relative differences (in percentage) in 2050 between the decomposition scenarios and the BAU scenario.

The decomposition analysis illustrates the dominant role of the demand-side intervention bundle on health outcomes, and small impacts from the climate mitigation, conservation, trade and supply-side intervention bundles, primarily in GSO and IMI scenarios in a few regions (OAS, SEA). At EUR level, the changes in YLL are driven exclusively by demand assumptions, while in GSO and IMI the relative decrease in risk as compared to then BAU in 2050 is slightly lower than at World

level.

Land and biodiversity footprint from the consumption of agricultural products

The projected changes in the agricultural land area embedded in the consumption of agricultural products across the scenarios is presented in Figure 30 for all regions, while the same diagnosis for the related biodiversity impacts (land occupation on terrestrial ecosystems) is presented in Figure 31.

In the BAU scenario, the amount of agricultural land embedded in the consumption of agricultural products is projected to remain close to stable at global scale for domestic footprint (upper left panel; with increases in some regions - e.g., SSA, MEN - compensated by decreases in other - e.g., BRA, ANZ, FSU -), while the imported footprint (upper middle panel) is expected to increase at global scale (driven by increases in SSA, MEN and OAS), leading to a net increase in total agricultural land footprint (by about 150 million hectares per year by 2050). The associated biodiversity losses is relatively similar: stable at global scale for domestic footprint, while the imported footprint (upper middle panel) is expected to increase at global scale, leading to a net increase in total biodiversity land occupation footprint (by about 0.004 PDF.y per year by 2050).

D5.3 – Lessons learned from the quantification of the pathways

Figure 30: Projected changes in the global agricultural land footprint from the consumption of agricultural products, split by region (colored bars, with the global sum indicated by a black dot) and source (domestic, component and total, in separate panels). The upper panels provide absolute changes in the agricultural land embedded in the consumption of agricultural products as compared

to 2020 (in million m³ per year) for the BAU and the VITAL-Paths-Food scenarios for domestic (upper left panel), imported (upper middle panel) and total (upper right panel) footprint. The middle (resp. bottom) panel provides the relative differences between the decomposition scenarios and the BAU scenario by 2050 in the imported (resp. domestic) footprint, normalized by the total global footprint for the BAU scenario in 2050.

In contrast, by 2050 the total land footprint and its land occupation-based biodiversity impacts on terrestrial ecosystems are projected to decrease considerably as compared to 2020 in the VITAL-Paths-Food scenarios. The amplitude of the projected decrease in the global land footprint as compared to that of the BAU scenario by 2050 is larger for the GSO scenario (-444 million hectares per year Mha/yr or -18.0%) and IMI scenario (-405 Mha/yr, -16.4%) than for the LCS scenario (-291 Mha or -11.8%). The decrease in the domestic footprint is projected to be systematic across regions and pathways (with very few exceptions, like ANZ in the IMI scenario), and to contribute the largest fraction to the total agricultural land footprint reduction. Reductions in the imported footprint are of lower amplitude (with still a net increase globally for the GSO pathway as compared to 2020), and are less systematic, with some regions (e.g., IND) showing increases for all VITAL pathways as compared to both 2020 and 2050 in the BAU.

As compared to the land footprint, the biodiversity footprint from land occupation is projected to reduce slightly more in relative terms (as compared to the BAU in 2050, range across scenarios -18.2% to -26.7%), with a slightly different ranking between the IMI and GSO pathways.

Figure 31: Projected changes in the global biodiversity footprint (from land occupation) from the consumption of agricultural products, split by region (colored bars, with the global sum indicated by a black dot) and source (domestic, component and total, in separate panels). The upper panels

provide absolute changes in the biodiversity footprint embedded in the consumption of agricultural products as compared to 2020 (in PDF.yr per year) for the BAU and the VITAL-Paths-Food scenarios for domestic (upper left panel), imported (upper middle panel) and total (upper right panel) footprint. The middle (resp. bottom) panel provides the relative differences between the decomposition scenarios and the BAU scenario by 2050 in the imported (resp. domestic) footprint, normalized by the total global footprint for the BAU scenario in 2050.

The impact of the various intervention bundles on projected deviations to the BAU scenario by 2050 differs across imported and domestic agricultural land footprints, and across regions (Figure 30, middle and bottom panels). The demand-side intervention bundle consistently decreases both footprints in all regions and VITAL-Paths-Food scenarios, except for IND in LCS. The conservation intervention bundle leads to large reductions in the domestic footprint but less impact on the imported footprint, with increased impacts for IND in all VITAL-Paths-Food scenarios. The climate mitigation intervention bundle leads to a small global reduction in domestic and (except for IND in IMI) imported footprints. The supply intervention bundle has limited impacts across all pathways. The trade intervention bundle has often opposite impacts on domestic and imported footprints globally but not necessarily at regional level. The picture is relatively similar for the land occupation-based biodiversity impact footprint, with however some variations (e.g., higher overall impacts on imported footprints, larger impacts from the trade intervention bundle, different relative contributions of various regions in World total).

Figure 32 provides a closer look at the deviations to the BAU scenario in the footprint of the EUR, for both agricultural land use and the related land occupation impacts on biodiversity. For both land and related biodiversity footprints, the amplitude of agricultural land footprint reductions in the VITAL-Paths-Food as compared to the BAU scenario by 2050 in the EUR region is comparable to the global ambition for the GSO pathway (for land footprint, EUR: -20.5%, global: -18.0%), but higher than the global ambition for the IMI (for land, EUR: -26.0%, global: -16.4%) and LCS pathways (for land, EUR: -22.6%, global: -11.8%). Similar to the global scale, the improvements in biodiversity footprints are slightly higher for biodiversity impacts from land occupation than for land occupation itself.

Figure 32: Projected deviations to the BAU scenario in the EU agricultural land footprint (upper panel) and related biodiversity impacts from land occupation (lower panel), from the consumption of agricultural products by 2050, split by source (domestic, imported and total; colored bars and black dot). The values displayed are the relative differences between the decomposition scenarios and the BAU scenario by 2050 in the source-specific footprint, normalized by the total EU footprint for the BAU scenario in 2050.

This confirms that the impact of various intervention bundles varies significantly across pathways at the regional level and are not always positive. Both the domestic and imported agricultural footprints of EUR consumption can increase for specific intervention bundles in some pathways: e.g., imported footprints for the demand-side and (for LCS) conservation intervention bundles, and domestic footprints for the supply-side and trade intervention bundles for LCS. The effect of interventions can also differ between types of footprints: for example, both the trade intervention bundle in IMI and the conservation intervention bundle in GSO have significantly

higher impacts on the land occupation biodiversity footprint than on the land footprint.

As a result, while the level of total biodiversity footprint reduction at EUR level remains relatively comparable across pathways, those can differ significantly about the share of domestic vs imported footprint reductions (with IMI relying a lot more on imported footprint reduction than GSO and LCS, with a particular importance of trade regulation in IMI), and about how this is achieved (e.g., a dominant contribution from conservation efforts in GSO, but almost exclusively demand-side efforts in LCS).

4. DISCUSSION

4.1 Methodological limitations

4.1.1. Influence of key choices in scenario implementation

The task of parameterizing scenarios in models and generating quantitative projections inevitably involves choices and simplification. As detailed in section 2, this is also the case at multiple stages for our approach. As summarized in *Table 1*, and further documented in the Appendix section, the parametrization of the BAU & VITAL-Paths-Food narratives implies specifying values for the key model drivers. The BAU scenario embeds many assumptions, and each of the three pathways deviate from it for multiple assumption domains simultaneously (e.g., demand-side efforts, restoration efforts, financial incentives to carbon removal, trade costs etc.), each covering multiple model parameters. As pointed to by stakeholder during the model development phase (see appendix), this makes it challenging to understand the impact of specific scenario assumptions within the pathways on modeled outcomes. It might therefore be useful to shed light on key choices, and the potential impacts of alternative choices where relevant.

We first relied on a well-documented scenario for the BAU (the Shared Socio-economic Pathway 2) and provided extensive documentation of the different model parameter assumptions underlying the parameters for the VITAL-Paths-Food scenarios assumption, and their expected effects in the model (*App-Table 1 to*

App-Table 5). In addition, as analyzed in section 3, we make the model quantitative outputs publicly available, including many indicators directly related to model assumptions. Finally, we grouped the various model parameters into five topical intervention bundles (climate mitigation, conservation, supply-side measures, demand-side measures, trade-related measures) and provided a decomposition analysis of their effects. This analysis consisted of 15 additional scenarios, each deviating from the BAU by model parameter assumptions associated with one of the five intervention bundles, for one of the three VITAL pathways. In a structured manner, this helps identifying the role of the various components of the pathway implementation and assess the impact of differences across pathways in assumptions within each topical intervention bundle. However, several of these steps

entail subjective choices.

First, for each individual model parameter and each scenario, several parameter values may be considered as a valid interpretation of the narratives. There is also subjectivity in how parameter values are chosen across intervention bundles within a pathway, and which parameter is considered. For example, our IMI pathway includes changes in the demand-side through a substitution of 33% of animal-based products by novel plant-based alternatives by 2050, and 20% or 50% might be considered equally relevant. Our IMI pathway also assumes region-specific improvements in crop yields and pesticide use efficiency, altogether picturing a future in which demand for meat- and dairy-like products are maintained, with efforts to decouple their consumption from their environmental impacts (through replacing pasture by cropland, and reducing cropland pesticide application rates). An alternative parameterization with lower change in consumer preferences (including a lower substitution of animal products by novel plant-based alternatives) and higher decoupling efforts might be equally valid under such a narrative. This could include the modification of additional model parameters: for example, the use of macroalgae as livestock feed as a complementary form of decoupling (e.g., Spillias et al., 2023). We choose to exclude it here due to the lack of capacity to measure potential impacts on marine ecosystems.

Similarly, the scenarios we consider are normative in nature: they are expected to reach specific outcomes for multiple indicators (altogether defining a target space), and adjustments to the pathways conducted to ensure that the target space is met carry some level of subjectivity. For example, the ambition of minimum restoration efforts after 2030 was increased to ensure that trends in MSA indicator for ecological intactness, subject to both land use and climate pressures, are reversed. By doing so, we increased ambition to mitigate one pressure (land use), and one could have instead (or in addition) increased the ambition on another pressure (climate). The challenge of subjectivity in scenario implementation is high as our scenario narratives consider multiple indirect driver, values and normative targets, which increases the risk for conflicting implications for specific model drivers. E.g., in LCS, should the high amount of agricultural land abandonment lead to further extensification (to keep the distinctive ‘extensification’ element of this pathway as compared to others), or should it instead lead to restoration to natural

ecosystems (to ensure a reversal decline in ecological integrity)? Overall, we did our best to generate consistent scenario implementations for key model drivers, but multiple attempts to quantify the same scenarios will lead to a broader set of assumptions and outcomes. This is one of the reasons for which model-intercomparison is essential (Aschi et al., 2026).

Alternative choices could also have been made for the decomposition analysis, with implications for the capacity to inform policy options. First, a higher number of scenarios could have been considered, to differentiate the impact of interventions that are currently grouped together (e.g., diet shift vs waste reduction vs within-country food consumption inequality reduction). While this would allow a finer understanding of the scenario implementation and the impact of underlying interventions, this would come at the cost of higher computational requirements, and higher analysis complexity. We instead tried to report indicators related to the various assumptions within each intervention bundle.

Second, the grouping of interventions into thematic intervention bundles also entails some modeler preference between various objectives. Should restoration measures that are relevant to both climate mitigation and conservation goals be included in both intervention drivers (e.g., to allow a more realistic representation of the various intervention bundles), or instead be included in only one of the two (to better isolate the outcomes associated with specific drivers)? Our approach is a mix of the two objectives, and as such may require careful analysis before drawing general conclusions on the impact of various intervention drivers. For example, type-2 restoration efforts are included in both the climate mitigation and conservation intervention bundles (albeit with different parameterizations), while type-1 restoration is included only in the conservation intervention bundle, even though it often constitutes a key pillar of land-based climate mitigation efforts.

Finally, the decomposition analysis presented here could easily become more complex, to uncover the impact of mixing assumptions across pathways, or how intervention bundles interact with one another. For example, the impact of the conservation intervention bundle in the LCS pathway assumes the restoration of abandoned agricultural land, and therefore leads to higher restoration when combined with demand-side measures. While we considered scenarios deviating from

the BAU scenario by one intervention bundle, we did not consider the symmetric case of scenarios deviating from full blown pathways (rather than from the BAU) by one intervention bundle, or scenario combining two or more (but not all) intervention bundles. While useful for a better understanding of the pathways and underlying interventions, larger decomposition analysis would require more resources and lead to more complex analysis.

4.1.2. Limitations about the quantitative modeling framework

The modeling of the sectoral dynamics of the land-based sectors for broad transformative change scenarios as considered here, as well as their multiple socio-economic and environmental impacts, is inherently subject to large uncertainties. Despite relying on the state-of-art GLOBIOM modeling framework, with improvements conducted during the course of the project (see Deliverable 2.1 and Deliverable 2.2 (Kuipers et al., 2023, 2025)), this is also the case for the results described in this deliverable. We here provide a brief overview of noteworthy limits and uncertainties.

It should be mentioned that only 18 crops are explicitly considered in the model. While they collectively represent more than 80% of current harvested area globally, some missing crops like fruits, vegetables and some nuts are important from a nutritional point of view (so may increase in extent in LCS & GSO pathways), and can have particularly large fertilizer and pesticide application rates, and labor requirements. The lack of inclusion of these crops may lead to an incomplete and possibly optimistic picture when it comes to the impact of a shift towards healthy diets on some pressures like land occupation or ecotoxicological impacts from pesticides, but a possibly pessimistic picture when it comes value added and labor. In the future, it may be feasible to add more crops to address this gap.

Another limitation relates to uncertainties in the type, productivity, and management intensity of pastures. Our model has a detailed representation of livestock production systems at subnational level, including mixed vs grass-based ruminant production systems. Yet uncertainties in underlying data about the type of managed grassland (e.g., regularly sown pasture vs permanent pasture vs rangeland), its carrying capacity (e.g. grass productivity) and use level (e.g., extracted biomass) are large. Our estimate of total pasture land relies on the combination of remote

sensing data, ruminant production system distribution and grassland extracted biomass and is lower than FAO's estimate of permanent grassland, upon which other models are often aligned (with lower grassland productivity). This may limit the projection of large amounts of managed grassland restoration in our model as compared to other models, but the extent to which such restoration is beneficial to biodiversity for low intensity natural or semi-natural grassland ecosystems is unclear. In general, uncertainties about pasture dynamics, its link to livestock dynamics but also to other aspects such as forest frontier governance, are large.

Despite a relatively detailed coverage of various cropland and pasture management practices, it should be acknowledged that uncertainties about their effects on yields, chemical and labor inputs use and operating costs, or farm gate prices are large. For example, except organic farming, due to a lack of data we assumed zero adoption rate for many practices in 2020, which may overestimate the potential for, and the impact of, further adoption. As noted during a stakeholder workshop, the model is also currently not able to satisfactorily assess farm-scale economic impacts such as operating costs and gross margins, as well as investment needs and transaction costs for the adoption of new practices. Doing better requires extensive data collection to capture the wide variation in key biophysical, ecological, agronomic, economic and social aspects across geographies, and may be challenging at global scale.

Uncertainties are also large when it comes the biodiversity impacts from agricultural land management practices. For example, the effect of various forms of agricultural land management on biodiversity in terrestrial ecosystems was not accounted for in the LC-IMPACT methodology used to estimate extinction risks, and was included with high levels of simplification in the GLOBIO method used to estimate ecosystem integrity. More fundamentally, in both cases, the biodiversity impacts are often measured against a natural ecosystem baseline. While such indicators are necessary to capture trends in biodiversity at large, they may fail to capture the specificities of taxonomically and functionally diverse semi-natural and anthropic managed ecosystems. The lack of a more diverse set of indicators may promote a narrow understanding of what bending the curve of biodiversity loss might look like, by discounting biodiversity improvements outside of natural ecosystems.

Our model also has limited accounting of the processes associated with the physical, chemical and biological degradation of managed land (such as soil erosion and chemical contamination), and the resulting impacts on key ecosystems services (e.g., yields, soil organic carbon removal) and human health impacts (e.g., exposure to pollution from nutrient and pesticide losses). Overlooking these aspects leads to optimistic outcomes in the counterfactual, and a pessimistic impact from transitioning away from the status quo, not only at societal level but also for producers specifically.

Finally, it should be recognized that uncertainties in biodiversity effects from climate change are high, and alternative outcomes would influence how we parameterized our VITAL-Paths-Food pathways, by design assumed to reach a reversal of biodiversity loss by 2050. For example, in our results the VITAL-Paths-Food pathways entail a lower impact from climate change than in the baseline, but still negative. Once this effect is accounted for, the reversal in total MSA loss necessitates not only a reversal in impacts from the land use pressure, but also this land use pressure-related impact reversal to be ambitious enough to cancel the residual climate change impacts. As noted in section 2, we raised the ambition for land use action beyond 2030 to that end. An alternative could have been to instead increase the overall climate change mitigation ambition, this was deemed less likely (as ambition is already high) and less practical (as we are relying external climate change mitigation projections for the rest of the economy) but other approaches could be taken. More importantly, the impacts of climate change on biodiversity are particularly uncertain (Aschi et al., 2026; Pereira et al., 2024), and following the same methodology, a higher estimate of the pure climate change impacts would lead to higher ambitions for land use action.

4.2 Key insights from the results

4.2.1 Efforts required to reach the target space

The first research question we set to explore with the pathway quantification was the following: for each pathway, what level of effort in various intervention domains is needed to reach nature-, climate- and people goals, and how are those efforts

distributed between regions?

To answer this question, we analyzed efforts from the point of view of indirect drivers of biodiversity loss, and other environmental and socio-economic indicators, in relation to conservation (e.g., protection of natural and seminatural land, restoration of degraded agricultural land incl. through more sustainable practices), other supply side measures (e.g., reduction in losses within supply chains, increases in yield and input use efficiency in agriculture, expansion of roundwood short rotation plantations in forestry), demand-side aspects (e.g., more sustainable dietary choices, reduction in within-country inequalities in food consumption, reduction in waste, higher re-use and recycling rates, increases in woody biomass demand for climate mitigation in the energy and construction sectors), and trade (e.g., preference for short- to medium-distance trade, implementation of biodiversity border adjustment mechanism). As detailed in section 2, efforts are analyzed as deviation in related indicators between the VITAL-Paths-Food scenarios and a BAU counterfactual scenario. After an initial implementation of the pathways based on the narratives, additional adjustments were conducted to ensure that the projected outcomes are compatible with the targeted outcome space. In the rest of this sub-section, we summarize the main patterns of projected efforts in three groups (protection, restoration and deforestation control; sustainable production, consumption and trade in the agricultural sector; sustainable consumption and production in the forestry sector), their relation to pathway assumptions, and the implied contribution of Europe to global efforts.

Protection, restoration and deforestation reduction efforts

Summary

Overall, the pathways have a similar global ambition in terms of protected area expansion (with an increase by 2030) and restoration of agricultural land through restoration into natural ecosystems (with 235 to 244 Mha under restoration by 2030, and 454 to 478 Mha by 2050) but slightly more contrasted ambitions about avoided deforestation (103 to 198 Mha). This relates to similar assumptions about World level ambitions (e.g., for protected area expansion), but also to a mix of conflicting narrative elements for restoration to natural ecosystems, differentiated narrative elements about forest loss offsetting, as well as normative choices (e.g., all

pathways must reach an increase in ecosystem integrity).

The pathways are however more contrasted in terms of degraded agricultural land restoration through more sustainable management practices, in terms of types of alternative management practices deployed (e.g., preference for efficiency-oriented practices in IMI vs extensification-oriented practices in LCS). The pathways are also more contrasted in terms of regional scale patterns of protection and restoration efforts. At the scale of large regional groups (e.g., Europe, NAM-ANZ, ROW) the contrast across pathways is however more influenced by factors such as initial geographical differences across these aggregated regions (in, e.g., the extent of protected areas, the area of high conservation value land and the share in global land mass) and value preferences for sustainable consumption (i.e., sufficiency vs decoupling), than by differences in equity principles used to distribute efforts towards global targets for restoration and protection.

As compared to the global scale, Europe is characterized by lower protected area expansion (due to higher coverage in 2020 and, for IMI & GSO, a lower amount of high conservation and carbon value land), as well as a comparatively lower share of land mass under restoration through conversion to natural land in IMI & GSO, but comparatively higher share of land mass under restoration through adoption of more sustainable agricultural practices (due to a higher share of degraded land and a slightly higher uptake of sustainable management practices directed at climate change mitigation). This illustrates that in Europe, as compared to the rest of the World, a comparatively higher ambition for type-2 restoration might be both feasible and justified in our pathways, while comparatively lower ambitions for type-1 restoration might be expected unless relying on equality as principle for burden sharing and/or sufficiency-driven shift towards lower consumption levels. The ambition for restoration (in particular through type-2 restoration) in Europe lies well above minimum restoration efforts assumed needed to meet KMGBF target 2, but may be below that of the European Nature Restoration Regulation (which targets 100% of degraded ecosystems restored by 2050).

Assumptions:

- All pathways assume minimum efforts for protection and restoration that are aligned in terms of ambition at global scale by 2030 (30% of land area

under protection, 30% of degraded agricultural land under restoration) and 2050 (gradual increase to 60% of degraded agricultural land under restoration). The global restoration ambition by 2050 was adjusted upwards to ensure a net increase in ecosystem integrity as compared to 2020.

- The three pathways differ in terms of spatial patterns of minimum protection and restoration efforts: based on a country-specific assessment of degraded agricultural land (excluding indigenous land for LCS) and current protected areas, and alternative equity principles for country-level allocation of the amount of additional land to be protected and of degraded agricultural land to be restored (cost effectiveness for IMI, environmental capacity for GSO, and equal share per country in LCS).
- The pathways also differ in terms of assumed preferences for two types of restoration (type-1 = nature-friendly afforestation, type-2 = adoption of sustainable agricultural land management) and protection (strict vs permissive), with a higher share of type-2 restoration and permissive protection in LCS (resp. type 1 restoration and permissive protection in IMI & type 1 restoration and strict protection in GSO). Within type-2 restoration, organic farming and agroecological practices are preferred in the LCS pathway, efficiency-oriented practices such as precision-farming are preferred in IMI, and GSO lies in between.
- Beyond these minimal restoration efforts, two additional important restoration mechanisms are included: for LCS, a larger uptake of extensive management practices (silvopastures and organic cropland management) is assumed (leading to an uptake well beyond minimum targets for type-2 restoration) and the abandoned agricultural land is progressively restored as type-1 restoration (leading to type-1 restoration well beyond minimum restoration targets in LCS), while for all pathways additional adoption of sustainable management practices is projected in response to climate mitigation financial incentives (higher in IMI and GSO). These mechanisms lead to an amount of total restoration well beyond minimum restoration targets for all pathways (by a factor at least 2).
- Finally, we assume differentiated reduction in deforestation across

pathways as compared to 2020, with a rapid elimination in GSO (90% reduction by 2030, elimination after 2030), a slower reduction in LCS (67% reduction by 2030 and 90% reduction reached by 2050) and an even slower reduction in IMI (50% reduction by 2030, 75% by 2050). As a limited deforestation reduction is assumed in the BAU (30% by 2030, 45% by 2050), the pathways entail a significant reduction in deforestation as compared to BAU. Together with type-1 restoration, this is compatible with reaching zero absolute deforestation after 2030 in GSO, zero net deforestation regionally reached by 2030 in LCS, and globally by 2030 in IMI.

Outcomes:

- The pathways are relatively similar in their global ambition for protection and restoration. Across pathways we project an increase to 30% of protected areas by 2030 (with more permissive protection in LCS and IMI), a significant reduction in accumulated deforestation over 2020-2050 (103 to 198 Mha of avoided deforestation, i.e. a 48% to 92% reduction as compared to the 215 Mha in BAU), 235 to 244 Mha (resp. 570 to 1,237 Mha) of land under type-1 (resp. type-2) restoration by 2030, and 454 to 478 Mha (resp. 1,239 to 1,567 Mah) of land under type-1 (resp. type-2) restoration by 2050. This may be considered as an estimate of minimum efforts required to achieve a net increase in the integrity of ecosystems by 2050 as compared to 2020 (in particular for type-1 restoration and deforestation reduction), achieve AFOLU GHG emissions mitigation efforts compatible with the Paris Agreement (Roe et al 2021) and pollution and pollution risk reduction efforts by 2030 (both type-1 and type-2 restoration) compatible with KMGBF target 7 and EU Green Deal. The extent of type-2 restoration is well above the estimated minimum restoration targets associated with KMGBF target 2.
- Differences across pathways in the global ambition of restoration efforts are slightly higher for avoided deforestation (48% to 92% of BAU, highest in GSOP and lowest in IMI) than for type-2 restoration (highest in GSO and lowest in LCS) and type-1 restoration (highest for LCS - although with a slower pace - and lowest for IMI). All pathways have a higher proportion of

type-1 than type-2 restoration despite a preference for type-1 restoration in minimum restoration efforts for IMI & GSO. This is due to the additional mechanisms for restoration (high type-2 restoration through climate financial incentives in IMI & GSO, general shift to extensive production methods and high restored abandoned agricultural land in LCS) and illustrates the importance of multiple, and at times partially coherent, narrative elements on restoration, in shaping overall restoration efforts.

- Additional protected areas are primarily located in ROW (and to some extent, NAM-ANZ), while limited additional protected areas are projected in Europe (with a high share of permissive protection). This is due to ROW representing a larger share of total land mass and, in the case of IMI and GSO, having high proportions of high conservation-value (ie. Biodiversity or carbon storage value, depending on scenario) unprotected natural land, and both ROW and NAM-ANZ having a low share of land under protection in 2020. This picture is moderately modulated by the alternative equity principles assumed for effort sharing across pathways, with the share of EUR and NAM-ANZ (resp. ROW) in protected area being higher in the GSO (resp. IMI) than in other pathways. Due to high current levels of protection and a limited amount of unprotected high conservation-value natural land, across all pathways Europe is projected to have limited additional protected areas, and a high share of permissive protection. This illustrates the relatively higher importance in our pathways of factors like the differentiated levels in current protection and area of high conservation-value unprotected land as compared to equity principles for the effort sharing of additional protection.
- Reduction in future deforestation is primarily projected in tropical ROW countries (in line with their high share in current deforestation patterns and scenario assumptions).
- Forms and adoption drivers of alternative agricultural management practices vary significantly across pathways: in LCS adoption is driven primarily by minimum type-2 restoration efforts (with a high share of organic farming) and a general shift towards extensive production practices

(as part of the supply-side intervention bundle), while minimum type-2 restoration efforts are lower in the IMI and GSO pathways (with a small share of precision farming and organic farming) but overshadowed by other forms of restoration directed at climate mitigation and spurred by market instruments. This denotes differentiated approaches for sustainable management practices adoption, related to pathway narratives about preferences for both production practices and instruments.

- Restoration areas are primarily located in ROW due to a higher share of total land mass, with a modulation across pathways due to various factors. The share of NAM-ANZ and EUR in type-1 restoration is highest in LCS (due to the large amount of agricultural land abandoned and restored), and for EUR represents a higher share of total land than at World level (in contrast to other pathways). Across pathways, the share of type-2 restoration in total land is slightly higher at EUR than World level, due to a higher share of degraded land and a slightly higher uptake of sustainable management practices directed at climate change mitigation. This illustrates that in Europe, as compared to the rest of the World, a comparatively higher ambition for type-2 restoration might be both feasible and justified in our pathways, while comparatively lower ambitions for type-1 restoration might be expected unless relying on equality as principle for burden sharing and/or sufficiency-driven shift towards lower consumption levels.

Sustainable production, consumption and trade in the agricultural sector

Summary

Overall, as compared to the BAU scenario, all pathways assume significant efforts both on the demand and supply-side, leading to significant reductions in the global volume of consumption and supply (by 2050 as compared to BAU, -27% to -46% for livestock products and -9% to -32% for crop products) and trade (close to a halving as compared to BAU in 2050, i.e., back to 2020 levels) of agricultural products, to a reduction of inequalities in food intake (10% to 50% reduction as compared to BAU in 2050), and to large gains in input use efficiency (up to a doubling for nutrients, a doubling to a tripling for pesticides). However, patterns of efforts differ across regions and pathways, due to differences value preferences across pathways for

sustainable consumption (e.g., preference for decoupling in IMI vs sufficiency and health in LCS), waste and loss reductions (higher emphasis on loss reduction in IMI, vs waste reduction in LCS), trade (a combination of further liberalization and greening market instruments in IMI, vs a combination of halting liberalization and limiting long-distance trade in LCS), but also to initial differences in production patterns (e.g., with a significantly higher input use efficiency in Europe as compared to non-OECD countries). At European level, as compared to the global level the relative decreases in consumption per capita are rarely lower than at global level, and higher for crop products in all pathways and for livestock products in the LCS pathway. While the uptake of sustainable agricultural practices is comparatively higher at European than at World level (previous sub-section), input use efficiency gains are much lower than at global level and can occasionally decrease (e.g., through composition effects to due changes in consumption patterns).

Assumptions:

- All pathways assume a shift away from animal products in diets (highest in LCS and lowest in IMI), a reduction of waste and losses along supply chains, and a reduction in food consumption average level and inequalities (highest in LCS and lowest in IMI).
- The nature and ambition of demand-side efforts is contrasted across pathways and regions, in relation to underlying value assumptions. With a focus on sufficiency, inequalities of food consumption are strongly reduced in the LCS pathway through a convergence in average country food consumption levels towards Eat Lancet 2.0 targets (with large reduction for EUR and NAM-ANZ) and an assumed high reduction of the coefficient of variation of within-country food consumption distribution, while a higher emphasis is put on reductions in waste than in losses. With a focus on decoupling and green growth, the IMI pathway instead assumes a 33% substitution of animal products by novel plant-based alternatives (with no convergence in average food consumption levels), a limited reduction in the coefficient of variation of within-country food consumption distribution, and a higher emphasis on reduction in supply chain losses than waste. The GSO pathway lies in between.

- To ensure that waste and loss reduction targets are met, waste and loss reduction assumptions were adjusted upwards in all pathways.
- The pathways assume deviations to the BAU in terms of research and development-related changes in crop yields. While the BAU assumes a moderate global increase with moderate convergence across nations, higher increases are assumed in ROW (but slightly lower increases in EUR) for the IMI pathway, slightly higher increases are assumed in ROW (and decreases in EUR and NAM-ANZ) in the LCS pathway, while GSO lies in between.
- The pathways assume high gains in nitrogen and pesticide use efficiency, driven by type-2 restoration efforts and additional input use efficiency where needed, with differences across pathways, regions and inputs. Pesticide use efficiency increases via the uptake of organic farming practices in LCS, as part of type-2 minimum restoration and supply-side efforts (100% reduction in pesticide application for all active ingredients and a yield penalty, with for minimum type-2 restoration a prioritization of crops with highest pesticide risks, within regions x crops with highest pesticide application-related ecotoxicological risks). Instead, in IMI & GSO increased pesticide use efficiency is reached via an uptake of precision farming (as part of type-2 minimum restoration efforts, with no yield penalty) and a 50% reduction in pesticide application rates for crops x regions x active ingredients with highest pesticide risks (often located in ROW). Nutrient use efficiency is affected by type-2 restoration efforts, as well as an assumed convergence towards high input use efficiency targets (partial for ROW, due to a higher deviation from targets in 2020) by 2030 in IMI & GSO, and 2050 for LCS.
- To ensure that nutrient surplus and pesticide risk reduction 2030 targets set for by the KMGBF and EU green deal are achieved, the above-mentioned efforts to reduce pesticide risk were adjusted upwards as compared to the initial implementation, and a general shift to more extensive agricultural practices was assumed for LCS.
- The pathways all deviate from the BAU scenario when it comes to

agricultural trade regulation, however in contrasted directions. With a central role for liberalization, green growth and market instruments, the IMI pathway assumes further reduction of trade costs globally, in combination with the adoption of a biodiversity border adjustment mechanism for all agricultural products, as a playing field leveling tool. In contrast, with a focus on sufficiency, the LCS pathway focuses on limiting trade dependency, and in particular, long-distance trade. The GSO pathway lies in between.

Outcomes:

- All pathways lead to a decrease in the consumption and supply of animal products (-27% to -46% at global scale as compared to BAU in 2050) and crop products (-9% to -32% at global scale), a reduction in waste and loss per capita (each ranging between 50% and 80% across pathways), and a reduction in the coefficient of variation of the distribution of food caloric intake by 10% to 50%. This illustrates that our pathways rely on significant efforts in terms of consumption changes.
- The global ambition for demand-side efforts is contrasted across pathways and regions, with LCS often reaching the highest reductions in both average consumption levels and inequalities in food consumption, and a higher ambition in EUR and NAM-ANZ regions. In particular, the adoption of Eat Lancet 2.0 diets by 2050 leads to the highest reduction in the consumption of crop products as well as high reductions in the consumption of animal products at global scale and for EUR and NAM-ANZ regions. In contrast, the assumed 33% substitution of animal-based products by novel plant-based alternatives by 2050 lead to high decreases in consumption at global scale including in ROW, and the lowest decreases in the consumption of crop products. LCS achieves highest waste reduction, while IMI achieves highest loss reductions, and reduction in food waste and loss combined are comparable across pathways. LCS achieves the highest reduction in global food consumption inequality reduction (50%), and IMI lowest (10%). In relative terms, at EUR level as compared to the global level, patterns across pathways are similar although the EUR ambition is occasionally higher, in

particular for the LCS pathway: for example, relative reductions are higher at EUR than at World level for per capita consumption of crop products in all pathways, per capita consumption of livestock products for the LCS pathway, and food losses in the LCS pathway. This points to the importance of competing value perspectives (e.g., green growth vs sufficiency) about the nature and level of ambitions in consumption reductions, at both global and European scale.

- All pathways are projected to lead to a generalized increase in input use efficiency over cropland as compared to 2020 with increases being very contrasted across regions, and particularly large for ROW: between a doubling (GSO, LCS) and a tripling (IMI) for pesticide use efficiency, about a doubling for phosphorous (all 3 pathways), and a 40% increase for nitrogen. In contrast, for EUR region the input use efficiency increases in slightly higher proportions than in BAU for nitrogen, remains constant (instead of declining) for phosphorous, and increases more than BAU for pesticide (up to 50% increase / 2020 for LCS, less for IMI & GSO). While our pathways differ in the assumed nature of efforts to reach these targets, they all point to a high importance of closing the input use efficiency gaps in ROW, and to a modest potential for additional input use efficiency gains in EUR.
- Primarily because of the significant reductions in the levels of consumption and production, our pathways depart from the doubling of the volume of traded commodities projected in the BAU over 2020-2050, with trade volumes much closer to 2020 levels for crop products in all pathways, and for livestock products in the LCS pathway. To some extent, the contrasted assumptions about trade regulation also play a role in reshaping patterns of supply and net trade across regions, in particular in the IMI and LCS pathways. At European level, for IMI and GSO, net exports of animal products, as well as net imports of crop products are increased as compared to the BAU, while opposite trends can be observed for LCS. This suggests that while trade continues to play a role, a transformative change in the agricultural sector may substantially limit future opportunities for major exporting regions, while preferences for trade regulation could also play a

role in reshaping trade patterns.

Sustainable production and consumption in the forestry sector

Summary

Overall, as compared to BAU, the three pathways have contrasted ambitions in terms of biomass demand both for climate mitigation and construction, ranging from an overall 38% increase in the IMI pathway, to no increase as compared to BAU in the LCS pathway. Across pathways with higher biomass use (GSO and IMI), circular economy measures partly help limit raw woody biomass extraction, although energy use still relies largely on raw biomass.

Across all pathways, deforestation is either significantly reduced or eliminated after 2030 and forest systems show some extensification, with some shifts from production oriented semi-natural forests toward multifunctional semi-natural forests or limited extraction natural forests. Afforestation and avoided deforestation expand also the extent of natural forest under no or limited extraction in all pathways.

In Europe, the increase in forest extent is lower as compared to BAU, due to lower deforestation and more limited afforestation ambitions, except in LCS. However, the share of existing forest converted from production-oriented forest to lower intensity is higher at EUR than World level in GSO and IMI, but not for LCS.

Assumptions:

- While a small increase in the use of woody biomass products for material use (primarily in ROW) is assumed for the BAU scenarios at global scale, our pathways feature contrasted trends, related assumptions about the role of woody biomass in climate mitigation. With a focus on green growth and decoupling, the IMI pathway assumes a higher increase in woody biomass use, in relation to increased demand for energy and construction sectors at levels compatible with reaching the climate target from the Paris agreement. The LCS pathway assumes instead no additional contribution from biomass (similar to the BAU scenario), through alternative, more ambitious, climate mitigation strategies in the rest of the economy. The GSO pathway lies in between.

- The additional demand in the IMI and GSO scenarios are primarily located in the ROW region, where most of the potential for increase biomass use lies.
- The pathways also feature contrasted assumptions about circular economy measures in the forest industry (higher recycling and re-use, as well as lower use of forest secondary products for energy in IMI & GSO, but not in LCS), and the possibility to expand short forest plantations for roundwood (allowed in IMI, but not in GSO & LCS). These measures are assumed to develop in pathways with higher demand (IMI, GSO), and help decoupling the woody biomass demand from the demand from raw woody biomass demand.
- Crop residues can be used as source of woody biomass, in particular for energy use, thereby creating an interdependency with the agricultural sector. Another interdependency with the agricultural sector is the competition for land, in particular for short rotation plantations for both energy and roundwood.
- Pathways picture a contrasted approach to deforestation control that, together with restoration assumption picture contrasted approach to the zero deforestation ambition. In GSO, deforestation is effectively halted after 2030 in GSO (zero absolute deforestation achieved globally), in LCS deforestation rates are reduced by 90% in 2050 and no compensation across regions is needed to achieve net zero deforestation at regional level, while in IMI deforestation rates are reduced by 75% only in 2050 and zero net deforestation is achieved globally but not necessarily regionally.

Outcomes:

- The VITAL-Paths-Food pathways feature contrasted future trends in woody biomass uses ranging from a 38% increase as compared to the BAU in the IMI pathway (with a significant role of woody biomass use in climate mitigation in the energy and construction sectors), to no increase as compared to the BAU with in the LCS pathway (with no further climate mitigation contribution from woody biomass use). Due to the assumed demand patterns (reflecting biophysical potentials), most of the additional

woody biomass use in IMI & GSO is projected in ROW, with the projected increases at EUR level remain below 13%.

- The VITAL-Paths-Food scenarios assuming higher biomass use (e.g., IMI, GSO) feature an increase in the use of raw woody biomass from forest and short rotation plantation that is only slightly lower than that total woody biomass use. While increased circularity allows to limit the increase of raw biomass for material use, it decreases slightly the contribution of secondary products to energy use. The latter primarily relies on raw biomass, and the contribution of crop residues is limited by decreases in overall crop supply in all pathways, due to assumed diet shifts.
- Even in scenarios featuring an increased level of biomass use, existing forest undergoes a slight extensification as compared to the BAU by 2050, with small decreases in production-oriented semi-natural forest for all pathways (larger for IMI), and, for GSO, in semi-natural forest under multifunctional management (while the later slightly increase in both IMI and LCS). For the IMI pathway, this is only possible through an expansion of short rotation plantations for roundwood production, with a shifting of pressure on abandoned agricultural land and to some extent, other natural land. The share of existing forests converted from semi-natural forest under production-oriented management to lower intensity is higher at EUR than World level for the GSO pathway (6.3% vs 1.5%) and the IMI pathway (9.4% vs 6.3%), but that pattern is reversed in the LCS pathway (1.7% vs 3.9%).
- In addition, across pathways the extent of natural forests under no or limited extraction increases by an area representing 13-22% of total forest area (excluding short rotation plantations) in BAU, through nature friendly afforestation and, in ROW, reduced deforestation rates. This increase is slightly lower for LCS, as due to more permissive protection, some natural forests under no or limited extraction are converted to semi-natural forest under multipurpose management. As compared to the World level, Europe is projected to have proportionally lower increases in forest extent (through avoided deforestation and nature-friendly afforestation) as compared to the BAU for IMI & GSO, or similar (for LCS). This reflects the

relatively lower importance of deforestation as a driver in EUR, but also slightly lower afforestation ambitions, except for the LCS pathway.

4.2.2 Impacts on the environment, producers and consumers

The second research question we set to explore with the pathway quantification was the following: for each pathway, what are the expected impacts on consumers, producers and the environment, how do those differ across regions and pathways, and how do those relate to different interventions?

To answer this question, we analyzed projected quantitative indicators related to direct drivers of biodiversity loss (e.g., land use, GHG emissions, pollution from agricultural activities), impacts of biodiversity loss (e.g., integrity of ecosystems, extinction risks from agriculture and forestry activities), agricultural producers (e.g., value of production, value of carbon removals in agricultural soils, farm labor input requirement), and consumers (e.g., risks of undernourishment, health impacts from food consumption, footprint of agricultural product consumption). In the rest of this sub-section, we summarize the main patterns of projected impacts in three groups (environmental impacts; producers; consumers), their relation to projected efforts and underlying assumptions, and the emerging picture of how impacts for Europe compare to that in the rest of the world.

Impacts on direct drivers of biodiversity loss and biodiversity

Summary

Overall, positive environmental impacts are expected globally, with limited differentiations across pathways, but some differentiation across regions. All pathways feature a global reversal of declines in forest cover, of increases in nutrient surplus and pesticide application, of increases in global extinction risks from agriculture and forestry activities, and of ecosystem integrity losses. Regional impacts show some variation across pathways (in particular, between LCS and other pathways). In Europe, the overall ambition of environmental impacts reduction is often (but not always) comparatively lower than at global scale except for LCS, and the importance of various efforts differs from the global scale and across pathways. Restoration through nature-friendly afforestation represents a lower share of total land mass than on a global scale, except in LCS. Reductions in nutrient surplus and

pesticide inputs are more limited than at global scale (except for phosphorous in general and for pesticide in LCS), and the role of input use efficiency gains is less dominant than at global scale, due to higher input use efficiencies at present. Reductions in deforestation and other land use changes represent a comparatively less important effort for GHG emissions and biodiversity than at global scale, while demand side measures have higher role. While some additional fine-tuning of effort assumptions may be possible to achieve a more contrasted set of pathways for outcomes, the relatively high level of global ambition limits the possibilities to differentiate the pathways.

Details

- All three pathways lead to a comparable reversal of the continued decline in forest cover projected in the BAU scenario, with comparable amounts of avoided deforestation (103 to 198 Mha), and of type-1 restoration (235 to 244 Mha by 2030, 454 to 478 Mha by 2050) at global scale. This occurs at the expense of agricultural land, with reduction in abandoned agricultural land as well as compared to BAU in 2050. Much of the avoided deforestation and type-1 restoration occurs in ROW in absolute terms (i.e., total area), and relative terms (i.e., in relation to total land area) as well, except for type-1 restoration in LCS, with comparable type-1 restoration efforts in relative terms due to the restoration of the large amount of agricultural land abandoned. At EUR level, restoration as nature-friendly afforestation is projected to reach 2 to 9 Mha by 2030, and 17 to 23 Mha by 2050. It should be noted that the ambition of restoration efforts after 2030 was adjusted upwards in a similar way for all pathways (in order to reach a reversal of trends in ecosystem integrity), which may contribute to a limited differentiation across pathways in their global ambition.
- All three pathways lead to a strengthened net GHG sink from the AFOLU sector, with relatively comparable contributions from Europe (as compared to the rest of the world) in relative terms (slightly lower for IMI & GSPO, slightly higher for LCS), primarily driven by reductions in non-CO2 agricultural emissions (while reduction in land use change emissions dominates globally). The largest source of improvements in net GHG

balance stems from a large reduction in land use change-related GHG emissions (-3.7 to -5.0 GtCO₂eq in 2050 as compared to the BAU), due to deforestation control, restoration efforts and taxation of CO₂ emissions from land use change. These reductions are primarily located in ROW (in relation to land use impacts), and lower for LCS than for the other pathways (due a delayed afforestation, with a higher proportion located in the relatively less productive areas of OECD countries) and IMI (due to lower deforestation control) than for GSO. Large additional reductions in agricultural GHG non-CO₂ emissions are also achieved (-3.5 to -3.8 GtCO₂eq/yr), through the reduction in agricultural product consumption and the adoption of alternative agricultural management practices (through a carbon tax on agricultural GHG emission and to a lower extent, minimum type-2 restoration efforts). These agricultural non-CO₂ GHG reductions are slightly higher in LCS (due to higher dietary shift), and relatively higher in relative terms in Europe as compared to World level. Increased SOC removal in agricultural soils represents a smaller contribution to the improvements in net GHG balance (-0.6 to -1.6 GtCO₂eq/yr), relatively comparable between Europe and World level in relative terms, but saturating impacts after 20 years.

- All three pathways lead to a reduction in nitrogen and phosphorous surplus and pesticide applications, with comparatively lower efforts and impacts in Europe (except for phosphorous, and pesticide in LCS) as compared to ROW, due to a higher input efficiency in 2020, and a strong influence of increases in input use efficiency trends, type-2 restoration efforts, demand-side measures (in particular for LCS) and, for LCS, uptake of organic farming. A large share of reductions is reached as early as 2030, in line with the pollution reduction targets for 2030, with however slower progress for LCS (in particular for nutrients). Across the pathways, by 2050 as compared to 2020, reductions reach 46% (GSO) to 54% (IMI) for nitrogen cropland surplus, 98% to 100% for phosphorous surplus, and 48% (GSO) to 66% (LCS) for pesticide application. As compared to the World level, for Europe the decrease in nutrient surplus and pesticide application as compared to the BAU scenario by 2050 is often lower in relative terms

(except for phosphorous in IMI & GSO, and pesticide in LCS), and the role of measures in the supply-side intervention bundle is lower (with even an increase in nitrogen surplus for LCS), while that of other measures is often larger. It should be noted that the pathways were adjusted to reach higher pesticide (and for LCS, nutrients) reduction by 2030 (to meet global pollution reduction targets). Although different types of efforts were adjusted across pathways (e.g., 50% reduction in pesticide application for most hazardous crop x country x active ingredient combinations in GSO and IMI, vs higher shares of organic farming and faster dietary transition in LCS), the resulting reductions in surplus and pesticide applications are relatively comparable across pathways.

- All three pathways lead to a comparable decrease in the global species extinction risks from agricultural and forestry production as compared to 2020 (instead of an increase in the BAU scenario), more moderate and variable for freshwater ecosystems than for terrestrial and marine ecosystems (due to the lack of dedicated effort on irrigation water use efficiency). The ranking of pathways, as well as the importance of various pressures and types of efforts differ across regions and ecosystems. As compared to the BAU scenario in 2050, decreases range from 27% (IMI) to 35% (LCS) for terrestrial ecosystems, from 9% (IMI) to 19% (GSO) for freshwater ecosystems, and from 53% (IMI) to 58% (LCS) for marine ecosystems. Relative reductions in impacts on terrestrial ecosystems as compared to the BAU in 2050 are larger at EUR than at World level for the GSO pathway (while more comparable for IMI & LCS). For marine ecosystems, reductions are systematically lower at EUR level than at World level (with a lower reduction in eutrophication impacts in EUR, but high reduction in ecotoxicity). For freshwater ecosystems, reductions are slightly higher in relative terms at EUR level, but dominated by different pressures: climate change and ecotoxicity at EUR level, vs water stress at World level.
- All three pathways lead to reversals of decreases in the integrity of ecosystems (as measured by losses in Mean Species Abundance of vertebrates and plants), with a partial reduction in impacts from the

climate pressure (in particular through climate mitigation efforts within the full economy) and a reversal of impacts from the land use pressure (with a high role from the land-based climate mitigation efforts, and restoration efforts). Ecosystem integrity, however, barely increases beyond 2020 levels, in particular in LCS (for both plants and vertebrates) and, for plants, in IMI. Reductions in biodiversity loss are systematically higher in relative terms at EUR than at World level.

Impacts on agricultural producers

Summary

Overall, all pathways lead to a downsizing of agricultural activity and a reduction in farm labor requirement, with some contrast across pathways and regions, and systematic net gains in cropland value per hectare in IMI & GSO when including the value of soil organic carbon removals. We project a decrease in the total value of production across all pathways, in particular in the livestock sector and in Europe, and highest (resp. lowest) in LCS (resp. GSO). We project a concomitant reduction in farm labor requirements (only estimated for crop products), with large potential impacts in absolute terms in ROW (where agriculture represents a large share of total employment), but also significant impacts in relative terms for Europe. However, the labor requirement impacts from agricultural downsizing may be to some extent mitigated by composition effects towards more labor-intensive products and agricultural practices, as illustrated for ROW in the LCS pathway.

In addition, for cropland, losses in value of production per hectare may be limited and even turned into gains for all regions (including Europe) and pathways when including the value from soil organic carbon removal in agricultural soils. In Europe, relative losses in the value of production are comparable to the global scale for IMI & GSO and higher for LCS, while relative reductions in cropland labor input requirements are comparable to that at the World level in IMI and GSO, and significantly higher in LCS. Impacts on the per hectare value of production for cropland are positive for all regions and pathways when including the value of SOC removals. Finally, it should be acknowledged that our approach overlooks many important aspects (e.g., changes in input and machinery cost, access to price premiums and subsidies, capital and knowledge investment requirements), and

additional work is needed to adequately quantify impacts for agricultural producers.

Details

- All three pathways lead to significant losses in the value of agricultural production as compared to the BAU scenario, in particular for the livestock sector and Europe, NAM-ANZ and other major producers such as BRA and CHN. This downsizing of future agricultural economic activity is primarily due to the assumed consumption efforts, with significant variation across pathways: by 2050 losses at World as compared to the BAU range from -19% (GSO) to -36% (LCS). Decreases are projected as compared to 2020 in all pathways and most regions for livestock products, while increases are projected as compared to 2020 for crop products in non-OECD countries for IMI by 2050. Some efforts contribute to mitigating these losses through market price increases over large areas (e.g., climate mitigation, protection and restoration efforts), but also playing field leveling effects in some region and pathways (e.g., border adjustment mechanism in IMI for Europe). In Europe, relative losses in value of production are comparable to the global scale in IM & GSO, but higher in LCS (in particular for livestock products).
- All three pathways are projected to lead to a decrease in cropland labor input requirement as compared to the BAU scenario, and as compared to 2020. In absolute terms, reductions as compared to 2020 are concentrated in ROW, where farming represents a large share of employment, and where losses as compared to 2020 are highest in the IMI pathway (16%) and lowest in the LCS pathway (10%), despite LCS having the largest reductions in crop production. This is due to compositional changes in cropland allocation to more labor-intensive crops (through changes in consumption choices) and agricultural management practices (organic farming, through preferences for form of type-2 restoration). In relative terms, declines are comparable at EUR and World level in IMI & GSO, but three times higher at EUR level than at World level for LCS (29% vs 10%, from 2020 to 2050), indicating risks for rural communities in Europe as well.
- The pathways have mixed implications for potential revenues to crop farms,

with either positive or negative impacts on the value of production per hectare across regions and pathways, and the potential for additional revenue streams from financial incentives to soil organic carbon removal in agricultural soils. Across pathways, as compared to 2020 by 2050, we project a significantly higher increase in the value of production per ha than in the BAU at World level (from +11% in GSO to +18% in IMI, as compared to +6% in BAU), but only slightly better trends in Europe for IMI & LCS and slightly worse trends in GSO). Type-2 restoration efforts (in particular for GSO and LCS) and trade regulation (in IMI) have a more impact on the value of production per hectare than on total value of production. In addition, while more limited in LCS (due to a limited reliance on market instruments), the value of carbon removal per hectare is significant and including in it farm revenue per hectare leads to systematic net gains in all regions and scenarios.

- It should be acknowledged that we provide a very partial view on the economic impacts for farmers, and that additional developments are needed to adequately capture relevant aspects, such as changes in operating costs (with potential gains from reduced input levels), access to price premiums and subsidies, capital and skill investment requirements.

Impacts on consumers

Summary

Overall, all pathways achieve significant reductions in risks of undernourishment, health impacts from diet-related diseases, and terrestrial biodiversity impact embedded in the consumption of agricultural products. Improvements are more contrasted across pathways for undernourishment than for diet-related health impacts, and even more so, than for biodiversity footprints. While the demand-side efforts significantly contribute to improvements for all three indicators, a broader range of efforts is needed to reach reductions in both domestic and imported footprints, and undernourishment can be adversely affected by climate mitigation, conservation and trade regulation efforts: this points to significant benefits of integrated approaches. The ambition in within-country inequality reductions by 2050 is particularly high. In Europe undernourishment is limited and impacts from the

pathways were not estimated, while relative reductions in diet-related health impacts are comparable than at global scale, and reductions in footprints are comparable (GSO) or higher (LCS, IMI) than at global scale.

Details

- All pathways are projected to achieve a significantly larger reduction in the number of people at risk of undernourishment than in the BAU, with some contrast across pathways: a full elimination by 2030 in LCS and 2050 in GSO, and a 74% reduction by 2050 as compared to 2020 in IMI (as compared to 51% in the BAU, from 868 million people in 2020). These outcomes are predominantly driven by efforts on the demand-side (in particular through reductions in within-country inequalities in food intake, with large differences in ambition across pathways), and to a lower extent on the supply-side (through higher yield gains in ROW). It should also be noted that if adopted alone, climate mitigation and conservation efforts (as well as restrictions in long-distance trade in LCS) may increase food security risks (in particular in SSA) through price increases: this highlights the importance of integrated intervention approaches. Undernourishment risks are not estimated for Europe and NAM-ANZ, where they currently are limited. It should be noted that the ambition of undernourishment reductions and underlying efforts towards within-country food intake inequalities are high (in particular in the LCS pathway by 2030) considering trends in the recent past (and for LCS, concerns about the affordability of planetary health diets) and the need for comprehensive intervention packages (including income support to the poorest) and conflict reductions, in particular for least developed countries (Mumah et al., 2025).
- All pathways achieve a reversal of health risks (measures in years of life lost) from diet-related diseases expected in the BAU scenario by 2050, with reductions highest in LCS (-100%, full elimination) and lowest in IMI (-67%, i.e., 43% reduction as compared to 2020). Demand-side efforts, including the reduced share of animal products and, for LCS, reduced overconsumption, play a dominant role, but climate mitigation, conservation, trade and supply-side intervention bundles can provide

contributions as well. At EUR level, demand-side measures play an even more dominant role, and relative reduction in health impacts from food consumption as compared to the BAU are comparable to the World level.

- All pathways reach by 2050 a reversal of the future increases in the land footprint from the consumption of agricultural products and related biodiversity impacts projected in the BAU scenario. The footprint reductions as compared the BAU in 2050 are comparable across pathways for land (-291 to -444 Mha, i.e., 12-18% reduction) and slightly higher in relative terms for occupation-related biodiversity impacts on terrestrial ecosystems (18-27% reduction). Decreases are more pronounced for domestic footprints than imported footprints, but both are significant in all pathways. Multiple efforts affect domestic and imported footprints, with significant variation across types of footprints, regions and pathways. Demand-side efforts provide an important contribution in all pathways, while conservation efforts reduce primarily domestic footprints. The trade efforts have region- and pathway-specific impacts, with often positive impacts on imported footprints but sometimes negative impacts on domestic footprints. This highlights the importance of integrated approaches. At European level, agricultural land footprint reductions as compared to the BAU scenario by 2050 are higher than at World level for IMI & LCS (but comparable for GSO). Related biodiversity footprint reductions are dominated by reductions in imported impacts in IMI, but by reductions in domestic footprint in GSO and LCS (with an important contribution of demand efforts in both, but a dominant contribution from conservation efforts as well in GSO).

4.3 Lessons learned

The quantification of the VITAL-Paths-Food pathways provides an opportunity to understand the nature of transformative change efforts in food and biomass supply chains required to reach nature-, climate- and people-positive futures and related impacts, including what combination of efforts are required across regions and value chain actors to reach the desirable future state, how these can vary based on alternative value perspectives, and what their impacts might be on various indicators of environmental and socioeconomic outcomes.

We adopted the following definitions:

- A nature-, climate- and people-positive future is primarily defined by its outcomes, and is assumed to reach outcomes compatible with the sustainable development agenda (including targets from human wellbeing goals such as eliminating hunger and reducing health impacts from non-communicable diseases), and major international agreements like the Paris Agreement (with a trajectory in GHG emissions compatible with limiting climate change to well below 2 degree Celsius) and the Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework (with a reversal of biodiversity loss by 2050 and multiple action targets by 2030).
- Efforts are defined as quantitative changes in key indicators related to conservation (including protected area expansion, various forms of restoration), sustainable consumption (e.g., dietary choice, waste, consumption volumes, etc.), production (e.g., production volume, land and water use and use efficiency, pollution, re-use and recycling) and trade, as compared to a business-as-usual trajectory and to the current status. This equates efforts to changes in indirect and direct drivers of biodiversity loss.
- Impacts are defined as quantitative changes in key indicators related to direct drivers of climate change and biodiversity loss (GHG emissions, land use change, nutrient surplus and pesticide application, extinction risks, integrity of ecosystems), as well as multiple socio-economic relevant to producers and consumers (e.g., undernourishment and health impacts from

food consumption, value of production, labor input requirements).

- We focus on differences across pathways in the distribution of efforts and impacts across actors (primarily consumers and producers) and regions (with a higher focus on Europe within a global context), emerging from the contrast across pathways in value perspectives and the interactions across various components of the food and biomass value chains.
- Alternative value perspectives are understood as competing worldviews and values, in particular related to human-nature relationships and equity, leading to preferences for distinct and relatively coherent distribution of efforts and impacts across actors and regions, within limits compatible with the end point (nature-, climate- and people-positive future).

Based on the results presented in the previous section, and discussion on a preliminary version of those in a stakeholder workshop, in the rest of this subsection we provide some lessons learned.

4.3.1 Possible transformative change trajectories need to be explored

The result that multiple ways of transforming food and biomass value chains can achieve global goals for biodiversity and climate is not a novel result per se (e.g., (Kok et al., 2018; Van Vuuren et al., 2015), and has been for example pointed to in the first IPBES Global Assessment report (Chan et al., 2020; IPBES, 2019).

However, there are very few studies jointly considering goals covering climate, biodiversity and human well-being, providing detailed quantitative projections of what alternatives efforts and impacts might look like for various regions and value chain actors (e.g., to support a distributive justice analysis, and a in-depth understanding of the contribution of efforts to the impacts). There are also few studies providing an explicit and coherent linkage to underlying value perspectives, and considering multiple value perspectives.

Closing such a gap may support deliberations about progress towards global action and outcome goals through the KMGBF implementation, including the analysis of potential ambition and implementation gaps, and possible options for revised ambition and implementation. This requires sufficient convergence among parties

towards a joint understanding of the relationships between efforts and outcomes, and of what distribution of efforts might be considered fair. As highlighted by stakeholders, this requires a broader evidence base than currently available.

Our pathways all include conservation, sustainable production and consumption efforts, leading to ambitious reductions in environmental impacts from food and biomass value chains, as well as reduced hunger and health hazards from diet-related diseases, but also a downsizing of agricultural activities, with potential for losses of farm labor and farm revenue, although not in all pathways, producers and regions. Our pathways, however, reflect multiple and contrasted value perspectives, leading to significant variations in the distribution of efforts and impacts across pathways. The documentation of the scenario implementation and the quantitative model outputs (including for decomposition scenarios) contribute to a better understanding of the implications of different value perspectives for the distribution of efforts and impacts.

As shown in this report, differences in efforts across regions (for a given pathway) and across pathways (for a given region) are often shaped by the interaction of value perspectives (with sometimes multiple, and at times conflicting, narrative elements involved) and characteristics of the regions (for example, the extent of degraded agricultural land, extant and conservation value remaining natural ecosystems, extent of protected areas). The relation between efforts and impacts are often contextual, and efforts and outcomes can be less contrasted across pathways than the difference in their value perspectives could imply, due to the normative dimension of the scenarios (i.e., they are all assumed to achieve a net increase in ecosystem integrity, or to achieve reductions in pollution). Models and scenarios are particularly valuable tools to explore this complex option space.

While many crucial aspects, such as finance, knowledge transfer, gender or indigenous and local people and their knowledge and traditions are lacking for this analysis, this deliverable provides a humble step through the extensive quantification of novel pathways, a relatively detailed analysis and the provision of underlying quantitative model outputs.

4.3.2 Efforts and impacts: Europe in a global context

Our analysis provides an opportunity to understand how efforts and impacts in Europe might compare to the rest of the world, how this might differ across pathways, and why. While this topic could not be discussed with stakeholders, we here provide a summary of our results.

Efforts

Efforts vary across regions and pathways due to the combination of the three aspects: a) value perspectives underlying the pathways (e.g., burden sharing principles underlying the distribution of restoration and protection efforts, emphasis on instrumental vs relational vs intrinsic value of nature, sufficiency vs efficiency approaches to sustainable consumption and production), b) region-specific characteristics of societies and ecosystems (e.g., consumption, trade and resource use and management pattern - e.g., dietary preferences, trade balance, amount of waste and loss, share of degraded agricultural land and natural ecosystems in land mass, input use efficiency - as well as natural ecosystem characteristics - e.g., conservation value, productivity, etc. -), and c) the normative choice to ensure that specific outcome goals (e.g., net increase in ecosystem integrity by 2050, strong decrease in nutrient and pesticide pollution by 2030) are met in all pathways. As a result, the ambition in Europe deviates from the global scale for some efforts (i.e., for all pathways; for example with lower input-use efficiency gains, and lower protected area expansion) or are more comparable to the global scale for others, and shows more or less contrast across pathways (for example, LCS often stands out from IMI & GSO).

Across the three pathways considered, as compared to the global scale, the ambition of efforts in Europe are:

- Systematically lower for additional ecosystem protection (in terms of the share the additionally protected area represents, and in terms of level of strictness), due to a comparatively higher coverage in 2020, and lower extent natural ecosystems with high conservation and carbon value. Assuming a higher weight of intrinsic nature value (GSO pathway) however leads to a higher share of strict protection as compared to other pathways.

- Systematically lower for additional deforestation control (in terms of the share avoided deforestation represents in total land mass), primarily related to the relatively lower rates of deforestation at present.
- Often lower for additional restoration of degraded agricultural land as nature friendly afforestation (in terms of the share of land mass it represents). Although degraded agricultural land represents a comparatively higher share of land mass in Europe than at global scale, the conservation and carbon value is comparatively lower. However, in the LCS pathway, an ambitious sufficiency-based approach to sustainable consumption leads to high amounts of abandoned agricultural land (despite high extensification) restored as natural land, leading to slightly higher ambition than at global scale (despite this pathway assuming a preference to degraded agricultural land through sustainable management practices adoption due to a relatively higher weight to relational nature values).
- Often comparable or higher for additional restoration of degraded agricultural land through adoption of sustainable management practices. This is due to a relatively high share of degraded agricultural land in land mass, and, depending on the pathway, either the combination of equal burden sharing principle and a relatively higher weight to cultural than intrinsic nature values (in LCS) and to a higher reliance on market instruments for carbon removal in agricultural soils and circular economy measures in the forestry sector (IMI and GSO).
- Often comparable or higher for reductions in food consumption (in terms of per capita consumption volume). This is due to comparatively higher consumption levels (including livestock products), in particular when compared to planetary health dietary recommendations (LCS pathway).
- Systematically lower for increases input use efficiency (in terms of volumes of pesticide or nutrient use per unit of output). This is due to a comparatively higher input use efficiency in 2020 and, for pesticide, to a low contribution to the global ecotoxicological hazards for biodiversity.
- Systematically lower for increased woody biomass use into the construction and energy sector. This is due to a comparatively lower potential for increased

forest biomass supply, higher availability of crop residues, higher contributions from increased re-use and recycling of wood products and, for LCS pathway, the capping of additional biomass demand for climate mitigation in harvested construction and energy sectors

Impacts

Differences in impacts across regions and pathways are shaped by variations in efforts, but also by differences across regions in societal (e.g., consumption levels, net trade position, share of agriculture in total employment) and ecosystems (e.g., relative importance of various pressures, ecosystem types, productivity and species richness) characteristics that influence the response of multiple outcomes to efforts. Impacts and their relation to efforts at European level can show more or less difference to the global scale, more or less contrast across pathways, and often many nuances across estimated impacts, due to the complexity of outcome-specific relation to efforts and the difference in efforts across pathways.

Across the different pathways considered, as compared to the global scale, the impacts in Europe are:

- Either lower, comparable or higher, in terms of environmental impacts reduction, with larger importance of demand-side efforts relative to other types of efforts. In particular, nature-friendly afforestation represents a lower share of total land mass than on a global scale (except in LCS), reductions in deforestation and other land use changes represent a comparatively less important impact for land use, GHG emissions and biodiversity impacts than at global scale, reductions in non-CO2 GHG emissions are higher in relative term than at global level, while reductions in nutrient surplus and pesticide inputs are either more limited (nitrogen surplus and - except in LCS - pesticide input), comparable (pesticide input and phosphorous surplus in LCS) or higher (phosphorous except in LCS) than at global scale, and more strongly influenced by demand-side efforts (due to higher input use efficiencies at present). Reductions in global species extinction risks from agricultural and forestry by 2050 are comparatively higher at European level than at global level in all pathways for freshwater ecosystem (with a lower comparatively lower importance of water stress)

and for terrestrial ecosystems in GSO (but comparable for IMI & LCS), but comparatively lower for marine ecosystems. Reductions in ecosystem integrity loss are systematically higher in relative terms at European than at World level, in particular for vertebrates. At European level, impacts in the LCS pathway often stands out as compared to the other two pathways: for example, a higher (but delayed) nature friendly afforestation and higher reduction in non-CO2 GHG emission from agriculture (due to sufficiency-driven large reductions in the consumption of livestock products), a lower amount of carbon sequestration in agricultural soils (due to a lower reliance on payments for ecosystem services), a higher reduction of pesticide application (through a preference for organic farming as an alternative agricultural management practice), and higher reduction in some biodiversity losses (e.g., ecosystem integrity for plants).

- Often comparable or higher for impacts on producers in relative terms (e.g., losses in value of production - particular for livestock products - and cropland labor input requirements), even though in comparison to total employment, reductions labor input requirements are higher in ROW. Impacts at European level can differ significantly across pathways, with for example losses in value of production about four times larger in LCS than IMI, impacts of opposite sign for the value of production per hectare of cropland between GSO (moderate loss) and LCS (moderate gain), and more comparable impacts on cropland labor input requirements (decrease in all pathways, slightly higher in LCS).
- Often comparable or higher for impacts on consumers, except for food security (which is not estimated for Europe). Relative reductions in diet-related health impacts are comparable to the global scale, and reductions in consumption footprints are comparable (GSO) or higher (LCS, IMI) than at global scale (due to the comparatively higher demand-side efforts). Impacts at European scale can differ markedly across pathways, with for example about twice as high reductions in diet-related health hazards for LCS than for IMI, and reductions in land occupation-related terrestrial biodiversity impacts from agricultural products dominated by reductions in domestic impacts in GSO, but reductions in imported impacts for IMI.

4.3.3 A downsizing must be anticipated, but additional efforts are required to characterize risks for agricultural producers

As discussed in the result section, as compared to the BAU scenario, we project a downsizing of agricultural activities (as measured through either agricultural land area, production volumes or total value of production), particularly large for livestock production. This represents a downsizing as compared to 2020 in multiple region and pathway combinations, and might entail significant risks for agricultural producers, for example through reduced labor requirements, and reduced revenues. Our results also highlight factors that might mitigate these impacts, such as the adoption of more labor-intensive practices and demand shifts towards more labor-intensive products, potential benefits in the value of production once normalized by hectare, and even more so, once accounting for potential revenue streams from payments for ecosystems services. As mentioned in sections 3.2.2 and 4.1.2, this is a very partial picture on farm-scale impacts, and many important factors are missing, such as changes in production costs, changes in subsidies, access to price premiums etc. Yet, it is clear that the transformative change pictured in our pathways may pose significant risks to producers.

During the lessons learned stakeholder workshop, two types of considerations were raised by the stakeholders:

- The results presented might be biased towards negative impacts from restoration, as they do not sufficiently account for the impact of the degradation of agricultural land in the BAU scenario, and the benefits of restoration actions.
- More broadly, land use is a key driver of biodiversity loss, it is in the public interest to reverse biodiversity loss. It is likely unavoidable that this will entail a downsizing of agricultural activities as compared to a BAU scenario and as compared to today. This risk should be recognized, and policies designed to manage this risk (e.g., through promoting and supporting alternative livelihoods, and ensuring decent conditions for remaining farmers).

While additional research is needed to better characterize risks for agricultural producers, our results, reinforced by stakeholder feedback, indicate that a downsizing of agricultural activities must be recognized and anticipated to achieve nature-, climate-, and people-positive futures.

4.3.4 Novel methods are needed to explore transformative change as it unfolds

During the stakeholder workshop on lessons learned from the quantitative analysis provided in this deliverable (see related appendix section), stakeholders expressed the need to understand transformative change as it could dynamically unfold. When discussing the priorities for improvements, stakeholders indicated their interest in complementary model and scenario analyses to inform transformative change.

While our analysis helps to understand what transformative change trajectories might look like under different relatively coherent and time-persistent value perspectives, this does not depict how transformation processes occur dynamically through stepwise actions and reactions within value chains, with globally less coherent and temporally dynamic value perspectives at actor level. To inform the analysis of transformative change dynamics, our projections could be used to identify, across the range of scenarios, what might work best for different value chain actors and regions (as a likely first transformative change step). With additional assumptions about possible reactions throughout the systems (including spillovers, conflicts and setbacks), it might be possible to create more dynamic pathways, featuring actions and reactions that rest on globally incoherent and temporally dynamic value perspectives across value chain actors. While experimenting with those would go beyond the scope of the project, this could be a promising idea for future research, requiring a higher integration with social sciences in a participatory setting.

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APPENDIX

Parameterization of the pathways in the model

The following tables present the assumptions for the three pathways as implemented in GLOBIOM for this analysis, after the adjustments needed to reach the target space (see *Table 4*). They're split into 5 tables *App-Table 1* to

App-Table 5), following the classification from the intervention bundles presented in *Table 8*. References used for parametrization are documented, along with adjustments made to better reflect the narratives.

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App-Table 1: VITAL-Paths-Food Demand side assumptions, as implemented in GLOBIOM. This corresponds to the final implementation, after adjustments were conducted to ensure that the projected outcomes are consistent with the assumed target space (see section 2.4, adjustments are mentioned in blue).

Model input parameters	Demand side assumptions			Impact in the model and references
	International Market Innovation	Global Sustainability Orchestration	Local Commons Stewardship	
Exogenous dietary preferences	SSP2 dietary trends with widespread adoption of Novel Plant-Based Alternatives (NPBA, 33% substitution in 2050 compared to 2020 levels);	Partial transition towards Eat-Lancet 2.0 diet (50% adoption by 2050). Moderate NPBA adoption (25% substitution in 2050 compared to 2020 levels)	Full adoption of Eat-Lancet diet by 2050, with linear transition between 2030 and 2050; no NPBA	In the model, these affect the per capita level of demand prior to price-driven endogenous adjustments. SSP2 trends in dietary preferences reflect historical trends and are detailed in (Valin et al., 2014). Adoption of NPBA based on (Kozicka et al., 2023), the different levels of substitution are adjusted to match the narratives. Eat-Lancet diet refers to planetary health dietary guidelines focusing on human health and food system environmental sustainability (Willet et al 2019), we here use the second version of the EAT-Lancet diets (Rockström et al., 2025).
Maximum consumption levels	No limits; follows baseline assumptions	Overconsumption reduced by 50% (following transition of exogenous dietary preferences)	Overconsumption fully eliminated by 2070 (half of the transition achieved by 2030, transition of exogenous dietary preferences); intake aligned with dietary recommendations	The endogenous food demand of specific products in each region is modeled for an average consumer, whose consumption preferences reflect a broader distribution of consumption patterns and lead to an average food energetic intake per capita. To estimate the risk of hunger, we assume that within a region, the food energetic intake is normally distributed across the human population, and the differences across population quantiles are shaped by the distribution's CV. For the pathways, following (Hasegawa et al., 2015), we translate scenario assumptions inequality reduction into a reduction of the CV, leading to a reduction in the number of people at risk of undernourishment.
Inequality in access and distribution of food	Only partial reduction in inequality: Within-country Coefficient of Variation (CV) of food energetic distribution across the human population remains relatively high: 10% reduction by 2050	Significant reduction of CV through redistribution and food safety networks: 30% reduction by 2050	Maximum reduction in CV through targeted interventions and inclusive systems: 50% reduction by 2050	
Inequality in food intake within age and food group	Minor probability adjustments: 40% (by 2030) to 50% (by 2050) reduction low intake bins for protective food,	Moderate probability adjustments: 33% (by 2030) to 70% (by 2050) reduction low intake bins for protective food, as well as in high	Largest probability adjustments: 33% (by 2030) to 100% (by 2050) reduction low intake bins for protective food, as	Modeled via probability adjustments on intake distributions. Protective foods (vegetables, fruits, legumes, milk, nuts): low-intake bins are reduced, top bin recalculated to keep the mean constant. Risky foods (red meat): high-intake bins are reduced, probability shifted to low-intake bins. These probability adjustments

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	as well as in high intake bins for risky food (adjustment: 33% by 2030 in the initial implementation)	intake bins for risky food	well as in high intake bins for risky food	control the intake distribution, which directly affects the population attributable fraction (PAF) and thus YLL.
Food waste	Moderate reduction (30% in 2030, then 35%) (adjustment: initial implementation assumed linear reduction between 2020 levels and 35% in 2050)	High reduction due to legislation (70% by 2030, 85% by 2050) (adjustment: initial implementation assumed linear reduction between 2020 levels and 85% in 2050)	High reduction driven by awareness (70% by 2030, 80% by 2050) (adjustment: initial implementation assumed linear reduction between 2020 levels and 35% in 2050)	In the model, reductions in food waste reduce the required production needed to satisfy demand. The amount of waste is derived from FAOSTAT data and the parameterization of food waste reduction follows SSP1 trends from (Popp et al., 2017) as minimum improvements, with higher reduction for selected components in most scenarios.
Circular economy for wood supply chains	Maximum recycled wood collection rate: 75%	Maximum recycled wood collection rate: 75%	Baseline recycled wood collection rate : 50%	The circular economy in IMI and GSO is modelled as: 1) an increase in the maximum recycled wood collection rate from 50% to 75%, 2) the addition of sawnwood re-use in the model as an alternative to recycling, and 3) an extension in the cascading use of woody-biomass by excluding sawdust, woodchips and recycled wood energy use. This follows assumptions developed for the CLEVER project (Leclère et al., 2025).
	Reuse of sawnwood	Reuse of sawnwood	No reuse of sawnwood	
	excluding sawdust, woodchips and recycled wood energy use	excluding sawdust, woodchips and recycled wood energy use.	Baseline use of woody biomass	

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App-Table 2 VITAL-Paths-Food Supply side assumptions, as implemented in GLOBIOM. This corresponds to the final implementation, after adjustments were conducted to ensure that the projected outcomes are consistent with the assumed target space (see section 2.4, adjustments are mentioned in blue).

Model input parameters	Supply side assumptions			Impact in the model and references
	International Market Innovation	Global Sustainability Orchestration	Local Commons Stewardship	
Food Losses	High reduction due to the technological improvements along the value chain (65% by 2030, 75% by 2050) (adjustment: initial implementation assumed linear reduction between 2020 levels and 75% in 2050)	Medium reduction due to legislation and subsidies to technologies (cold storage etc): 50% reduction achieved by 2030, no further reduction after (adjustment: initial implementation assumed linear reduction between 2020 levels and 50% in 2050)	High reduction due to shortened value chain (60% by 2030, 70% by 2050) (adjustment: initial implementation assumed linear reduction between 2020 levels and 70% in 2050)	In the model, reductions in food loss reduce the required production needed to satisfy demand. The amount of loss is derived from FAOSTAT data and the parameterization of food loss reduction follows SSP1 trends from Popp et al (2017) as minimum improvements, with higher reduction for selected components in most scenarios.
Yields	Highest increases: ~20% in OECD, 40-130% in non-OECD by 2050, enabled by technology improvements	Stable OECD yields until 2050, then ~20% decline; moderate non-OECD increases (20-115%)	Growth focused in low-yield systems; declining/stable yields in OECD; lowest gains in non-OECD (15-95%)	In the model, these affect two different types of parameters. First, this affects the share of production activities under different technologies, that differ from conventional agriculture in specific ways (e.g., lower yield and lower fertilization organic agriculture, higher yield and lower fertilization for precision farming). Second, this affects additional trends in yields and input (water, nutrients, other chemicals) assumed to occur for all conventional and alternative production systems alike, to reflect long-term trends in agriculture research and development. Agroecological intensification is adjusted from FAO (2018), Frank et al (2024), and considering F2F targets for EU. Yield trajectories are adjusted from IMAGE estimations of the SHAPE pathways in Weindl et al (2024). Nutrient use efficiency trends are based on (Kanter et al., 2020), following high policy scenario for IMI and GSO, and Medium for LCS.
Nutrients improvements - Use efficiency	Convergence towards high NUE by 2030: minimal gains in OECD & EU and regions with high NUE and high improvement in regions with lower NUE. Achieved through uptake of precision farming and complemented with	Convergence towards high NUE by 2030: minimal improvement in OECD & EU and regions with high NUE and high improvement in regions with lower NUE. Achieved through a mix of precision and organic farming and	Convergence towards high NUE by 2050: most improvement in lower NUE regions, while NUE trends might remain stable or moderately increase in high NUE regions. Achieved through both uptake of organic farming and	

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	general NUE improvements within conventional croplands	complemented with general NUE improvements within conventional croplands	general NUE improvements within conventional croplands.	
Nutrients improvements - Manure recycling	90% recycling by 2030 in OECD; 50% increase in recycling in non-OECD by 2030	90% recycling by 2030 in OECD; 50% increase in recycling in non-OECD by 2030	90% recycling by 2050 in OECD; 50% increase in recycling in non-OECD by 2050	In the model, this affects how much manure is recovered from confinements, and available for application on arable land. Based on Kanter et al., (2020) following High policy ambition scenario for GSO and IMI, Middle policy ambition for LCS
Pesticide reduction	50% reduction of application rates in high-risk region x crop x pesticide combinations ⁹ through efficiency gains, in 2030 (adjustment: there was no assumed reduction in the initial implementation)	50% regulatory reduction of application rates in high-risk crop x region x pesticide combinations ³ , in 2030 (adjustment: there was no assumed reduction in the initial implementation)	Prioritization of high-risk crops within each region ³ for the conversion to organic cropland in 2030, as part of type-2 restoration (adjustment: there was no prioritization across crops in the initial implementation)	Same high-risk combinations targeted but different mechanisms across pathways. In the model, the reduced application rate assumed in the IMI and GSO pathways has other no implication (e.g., change in yield or costs, increased application of lower-risk pesticide), while the conversion to organic cropland assumed in the LCS pathways follow assumptions presented in Table 10
Crop management systems			Minimum uptake of organic and silvopasture following a linear trajectory, reaching respectively 65% and 50% by 2050 (adjustment: there was no minimum target in the initial implementation)	
Forest plantation area	Expansion of forest plantation outside of forest area	Fixed 2020 level	Fixed 2020 level	In BAU, LCS and GSO, plantation forests area is fixed at the 2020 level. In IMI, plantation forests area can be expanded outside of forest area under the specified land-use change constraints

⁹ High risk Region x crop x pesticide are defined as the combinations with the highest combined absolute and per ha risk on ecosystems combinations, based on LC-IMPACT.

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App-Table 3: VITAL-Paths-Food Conservation assumptions, as implemented in GLOBIOM. This corresponds to the final implementation, after adjustments were conducted to ensure that the projected outcomes are consistent with the assumed target space (see section 2.4, adjustments are mentioned in blue).

Model input parameters	Conservation			Impact in the model and references
	International Market Innovation	Global Sustainability Orchestration	Local Commons Stewardship	
30% Protection target downscaling (see App-Fig1)	Cost effectiveness distribution at country level, carbon, water and biodiversity at subnational level	Environmental capacity distribution at country level, biodiversity at subnational level	Equal distribution at country level, biodiversity at subnational level	Country downscaled targets for protected area expansion are derived from earlier RAINFOREST work depicted in D1.3 (Nowak et al., 2025) and follow different equity principles for each pathway. For incorporation into the model, further downscaling to subnational level is made using ranked area of importance according to different values (Jung et al., 2021). Habitat in the different areas is identified using (Jung et al., 2020) before integration in GLOBIOM. Since there can be a mismatch between habitat identified and GLOBIOM land use, we use the preferred type of protection to find a suitable option. Strict protected area expansion targets is implemented in the model as minimum area constraints for unmanaged land (i.e., this cannot be converted to managed land), while permissive protection targets are implemented as minimum area constraints for low intensity extractive activities (i.e., this land cannot be abandoned or intensified).
Preferred type of protection	Lower protection: some management allowed on protected croplands, grasslands, forests	Strict protection: as much as possible, protected land is unmanaged forest, natural land.	Lower protection: some management allowed on protected croplands, grasslands, forests	
Restoration target: Degraded land	Degraded land includes indigenous lands	Degraded land includes indigenous lands	Degraded land excludes indigenous lands	Minimum restoration area constraints Similar to protected areas, minimum country-level (type 1) or region-level (type 2) restoration targets are implemented. This is based on a re-aggregation of country-level targets, estimated in five steps. The first step is a country-level estimation of the extent of agricultural degraded land is generated, based on LUH2 data for 2015, with degraded agricultural land defined as high intensity cropland and pastures, and excluding rangeland in non-forest ecosystems (F. Aschi, personal communications, 2025), and pathway-specific decision about whether to include or exclude indigenous lands. In a second step, global restoration targets are defined as a pathway- and time horizon-specific share of the global degraded agricultural land. In a third step, the global area of degraded land to be restored is downscaled at country level, based on alternative distributive justice equity principles, using priorities for restoration from different scenarios from (Strassburg
Restoration target distribution (see App-Fig2)	Cost effectiveness	Environmental capacity	Equal	
Restoration target: share of degraded land	30% globally by 2030, 60% by 2050 (adjustment: initially 50% by 2050)	30% globally by 2030, 60% by 2050 (adjustment: initially 50% by 2050)	30% globally by 2030, 60% by 2050 (adjustment: initially 50% by 2050)	
Restoration type	60% type 1 in 2030 and 70% after, as natural afforestation	60% type 1 in 2030 and 70% after, as natural afforestation (adjustment: initially	25% type 1 in 2030 and 40% after, as natural afforestation (adjustment: initially	

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	(adjustment: initially fixed 60% share of type 1)	fixed 60% share of type 1)	fixed 40% share of type 1)	et al., 2020). In the fourth step, a pathway- and time horizon-specific of different shares of type 1/type 2 are applied, as well as different preferred type 2 options. In this step, the share of grassland vs croplands in 2020 is used to guide the split of type-2 restoration target between cropland and pasture. At last, pathway-specific assumptions are implemented for type-2 restoration options, about what type of restoration is eligible and in which proportions.
Options for restoration type 2	Silvopasture_IP, Precision farming, Biochar application, Grassland management measures for SOC	Silvopasture, Silvopasture_IP, Precision farming, Biochar application, Organic croplands, no tillage, r100, Grassland management measures for SOC	Silvopasture, Organic croplands, no tillage, r100, Grassland management measures for SOC	In the model, type-1 restoration minimum area targets are implemented as a scenario-, time step-, and country-specific minimum area constraint for restoration area nature friendly afforestation, which is only allowed to be sourced from the conversion of cropland and pasture. Maximum nature-friendly afforestation potential varies across locations at subnational scale, based on estimates from the G4M forestry model. In the LCS and BAU_LCS-Cons scenarios, this area is discounted for the amount of abandoned agricultural land restored (see additional restoration mechanisms below). Type-2 restoration minimum area targets are implemented as a scenario-, time step-, and region-specific minimum area constraint for eligible cropland and pasture management options. In some cases, the area target for eligible options may be partially or already fulfilled through climate mitigation incentives (see additional restoration mechanisms below).
Additional constraints for type 2 restoration	Minimum 80% of croplands type 2 restoration achieved via precision farming	Minimum 80% of croplands type 2 restoration achieved either via precision farming or organic croplands	Minimum 80% of croplands type 2 restoration achieved via organic farming	Assumptions about forest loss compensation and zero forest loss links type-1 restoration and deforestation assumptions (see App-Table 4). Zero absolute forest loss implies no deforestation, while zero net forest loss implies that some deforestation can occur as long as it remains lower than type-1 restoration (with either a permissive balance closed at global level only, or stricter balance closed at regional level as well). As the projections were already compatible with these assumptions in the full pathways, no model modification was performed to reach those.
Additional assumption about forest loss compensation and zero forest loss	Zero net forest loss reached at global level by 2030 (with compensation of forest gains and losses across regions allowed)	90% reduction in deforestation at regional level by 2030, and zero absolute forest loss reached at regional level after 2030 (no compensation)	Zero net forest loss is reached at regional level by 2030 (with compensation of forest gains and losses allowed within regions, but not across regions)	Additional restoration mechanisms Two additional mechanisms lead to restoration in the model. First, In a restricted number of scenarios (LCS & BAU_LCS-Cons), it is assumed that abandoned agricultural land not remobilized for production is slowly restored, preferentially to nature-friendly afforestation. It is implemented as rebalancing of part abandoned agricultural land after each time step: two thirds of the
Additional restoration mechanisms	Highest carbon pricing further incentivizes type 2 restoration (see App-Table 4)	Medium carbon pricing further incentivizes type 2 restoration (see App-Table 4)	Minimum carbon pricing further incentivizes type 2 restoration (see App-Table 4) Progressive restoration of unused abandoned, in priority to afforestation (within afforestation potentials), and to other natural land (adjustment: initially no restoration of abandoned land)	

abandoned agricultural land available in the previous time step and not remobilized in the current time step is converted to nature-friendly afforestation (or to non-forest unmanaged restoration land, if the afforestation potential is already reached). Second, some of the eligible type-2 restoration measures over cropland (e.g., biochar application, higher residue incorporation etc.) and pasture (silvopasture) can be adopted as the result of the carbon price assumed as part of climate mitigation (see App-Table 4).

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App-Table 4: VITAL-Paths-Food Climate mitigation and biomass demand assumptions, as implemented in GLOBIOM. This corresponds to the final implementation, after adjustments were conducted to ensure that the projected outcomes are consistent with the assumed target space (see section 2.4, adjustments are mentioned in blue).

Model input parameters	Climate mitigation			Impact in the model and references
	International Market Innovation	Global Sustainability Orchestration	Local Commons Stewardship	
Bioenergy demand	High demand, increase to levels of demand compatible with the Paris Agreement (increase to reach a doubling from 57 EJ/yr in 2020 to 114 EJ/yr in 2100).	Medium demand, half way between low and high demand	Low, constant demand over time (57 EJ/yr)	Bioenergy demand in LCS is fixed at 2020 level, assuming that additional renewable energy needed for the RCP1p9 mitigation target comes from other renewable sources. IMI demand is based on the MESSAGE RCP1p9 net-zero scenario where global bioenergy demand increases (IIASA, 2021). GSO demand is halfway between both scenarios. In the model, this is implemented as demand assumptions for related energy woody biomass-based products, and lead to higher woody biomass use from available sources (crop residues, forest and short rotation plantation raw biomass, forest industry secondary products, recycled wood products).
Demand for wood based construction materials	Maximum uptake of wood in new constructions (90% of the new urban population is assumed to live in wooden buildings)	Half of the demand increase between IMI and BAU	Baseline uptake of wood in construction (SSP2)	In BAU and LCS, demand for wood-based construction materials is based on the demand for semifinished products, driven by SSP2 population and GDP growth. Demand in IMI is based on the “Timber Cities” scenario from (Mishra et al., 2022), where 90% of the new urban population is assumed to live in wooden buildings. Demand in GSO represents half-way progress towards timber cities. In the model, this is implemented as demand assumptions for related material woody biomass-based products, and lead to higher woody biomass use from available sources (forest and short rotation plantation raw biomass, forest industry secondary products, recycled wood products).
Carbon price	Highest carbon price (up to 135.54 USD/t CO ₂ in 2050)	Medium carbon price (up to 84.71 USD/t CO ₂ in 2050)	Low carbon price (up to 30.245 USD/t CO ₂ in 2050)	Values are based on the MESSAGE information for the RCP scenarios (Fricko et al., 2017). In the model, the carbon price is implemented as tax on the GHG emissions from agricultural production activities and land use-change with negative impact on above-ground carbon stocks, and a subsidy to the adoption of GHG mitigation technical options in agricultural systems. This leads to less land use change, lower GHG emissions and increased soil organic carbon removal for agricultural activities, and - when carbon prices are high enough - to a lower (resp. higher) demand

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				for products associated with high GHG emission intensity (resp. high carbon removal in agricultural soils).
Engage Scenario for rest-of-the economy emissions	EN_NPi2020_700f, with some overshoot allowed	EN_NPi2020_600, without overshoot	EN_NPi2020_500, without overshoot	Different Engage scenarios are mapped to the VITAL-Path-Food to add industrial emissions, for deriving total GHG emissions and impacts from climate change on the ecological integrity of ecosystems (MSA projections). The three pathways lead to a temperature increase of around 1.7 degrees, while the BAU leads to 2.3 degrees (EN_NPi2100) (Riahi et al., 2021)
Minimum deforestation	Minimum regional-level deforestation rate declining by 50% in 2030, by 75% in 2050	Minimum regional-level deforestation rate declining by 90% in 2030, 100% in 2050	Minimum regional-level deforestation rate declining by 67% in 2030, 90% in 2050	Imposes a minimum amount of forest conversion to agricultural land at regional level. As GLOBIOM naturally produces lower deforestation rates than observed, a constraint imposes at regional level to reach at least as much deforestation as implied by an exogenous assumption, which is aligned on reported deforestation rate (FAO FRA) over 2000-2020, and set to explicit scenarios after wise (formulated deviations as compared to 2020 deforestation rate)

App-Table 5: VITAL-Paths-Food Trade regulation assumptions, as implemented in GLOBIOM. This corresponds to the final implementation, after adjustments were conducted to ensure that the projected outcomes are consistent with the assumed target space (see section 2.4, adjustments are mentioned in blue).

Model input parameters	Trade regulation			Impact in the model and references
	International Market Innovation	Global Sustainability Orchestration	Local Commons Stewardship	
Trade costs	Trade costs aligned with SSP2 but faster price elasticities transitions	Trade structure similar to BAU (SSP2)	Trade costs similar to BAU (SSP2), but intercontinental trade is penalized with higher costs (SSP3)	Trade costs represent all costs (e.g., transport, tariff and non-tariff measures) and apply to all traded commodities, with specific value for each commodity and bilateral trading region pair. The trade cost function is non-linear, with steeper marginal trade cost increases as the traded volume moves further away from the value simulated in the previous time step. Higher (resp. smaller) trade costs lead to lower (resp. higher) trade volumes, higher (resp. lower) prices in the importing region, lower (resp. higher) prices in the exporting region, and demand and supply adjustments in both importing and exporting regions.
Biodiversity border adjustment mechanism	Biodiversity border tax applied with moderate pricing	Biodiversity border tax applied with low pricing	No biodiversity border tax applied	The biodiversity border adjustment mechanism is modeled as a linear additional component to trade costs, with a tax level proportional to the difference in land occupation-related biodiversity impacts per ton of product, between imported and domestically produced.

Summary of stakeholder interaction

As noted in the method section, the results presented in this report benefited from input from various types of stakeholders (policy makers, NGOs, business, academics), collected through two specific online workshops, associated respectively to the toolbox development (WP2) and the lessons learned (WP5). While the uptake in this report of the feedback collected at this workshop is summarized in the method section, and a more detailed workshop report is available (Kuipers et al., 2025), we here briefly summarize these underpinning workshops and the key feedback received.

WP2 workshop: Environmental Impact Assessment Model Toolbox

On March 26th 2025, a 2h online workshop was organized by the RAINFOREST project partners before model developments finalization to gather feedback on the usefulness and limitations of the model toolbox employed in RAINFOREST, in the context of the case studies and the pathway quantification. After an introduction to the toolbox and its uses, the 18 participants were grouped by in three groups (1] finance and business, 5 experts; 2] governmental organisations, 5 experts; 3] research and non-governmental organisations, 8 experts), and each group participated to the discussion of three separate modelling applications in world café sessions. One of the applications was dedicated to the pathway quantification and focused on understanding the stakeholder views on the importance of various indicators to indicators the impacts of cropland restoration measures aimed at reduction cropland pollution. The below App-Table 6, reproduced from RAINFOREST deliverable D2.2 (Kuipers et al., 2025), provides a summary of the key feedback received, and how it was addressed in model development and pathway quantification.

One additional point mentioned in the workshop was that, while adequate for the quantification of broad transformation pathways, tools like GLOBIOM embed a lot of assumptions about future trends and effects. A related recommendation was to use specific scenario and model techniques (e.g., decomposition to systematically understand the impact of individual scenario assumptions) and a clear description of effects and potential limits, to improve understanding.

App-Table 6: Effects & indicators of impact from cropland pollution reduction measures discussed in WP2 workshop (reproduced from D2.2)

Domain	Relevant effects	Related indicator	Adjustment in model & its use
Yield and soil health	Yield impacts from measures targeting reduced pollution might be highly contextual (e.g., depending on local biophysical conditions and specific forms of restoration) and dynamic (with e.g., potential short-term decreases from reduced input use but expected long-term benefits from improved soil health)	Share of various forms restoration, assumed yield impact for each type of restoration, overall yield impacts	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - we introduced new specific changes in cropland management, with a differentiated uptake across the pathways, and specified yield impacts from each type of restoration (see section 3.1.2). - when quantifying the pathways, we will report on the share of various restoration measures, and resulting yield impacts - when discussing the results, we will consider uncertainties in relevant effects and limits of the modelling
Monetary value of impacts from restoration	Measures targeting reduced pollution might lead to positive downstream impacts whose monetary value should be considered to get a full picture, and these could be a basis for additional revenue streams to farmers (e.g., payments for ecosystems services)	Impacts from reduced pollution (e.g., carbon sequestration, reduced particulate matter concentration, etc.), their monetary value and possible revenue streams to farmers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - we introduced an indicator quantifying the value of the carbon removals achieved through measures leading to increased soil organic carbon content (see section 3.1.3). - when quantifying the pathways, we will report on the share of various restoration measures, and potential impacts - when discussing the results, we will consider uncertainties in relevant effects and limits of the modeling
Farm production costs	Measures targeting reduced pollution might lead to significant changes in the cost structure of farms, with both potential cost savings (via reduced input purchase) and increases (e.g., investment in new machinery, training)	Changes to cost structure and overall costs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - explicitly modeling the impact of the various restoration measures on the structure of production costs is not feasible within RAINFOREST. - when quantifying the pathways, we will not be able to report on such aspects - when discussing the results, we will consider this as a limitation
Differentiation of types of farmers	There is a variety of production techniques available, and main types of farming (e.g., conventional vs organic) differ by their level of pollution,	Yield, pollution levels and uptake of restoration measures differentiated by type of farmer	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - we introduced new specific changes in cropland management, with a differentiated uptake across the pathways (see section 3.1.2 & 3.1.3). - when quantifying the pathways, we will report on the cropland N surplus, Pesticide input, yield by type of farmer (conventional vs organic vs precision) (see 3.1.3) - when discussing the results, we will consider uncertainties in relevant effects and limits of the modeling

WP5 workshop: Lessons learned & co-created recommendations

On October 22nd 2025, a 2h online workshop was organized by the RAINFOREST project partners to discuss results and lessons learned from the case studies and the pathway quantification, and derive key recommendations. After an introduction to the workshop goals, the 13 participants were grouped in three groups, and each group participated in the discussion of one of three separate breakout sessions (governing EU value chains, consumer diet shifts, and quantification of global pathways). The pathways quantification session focused primarily on two questions (How efforts towards global might be distributed across multiple pathways, how the distribution of impacts across actors and regions might differ from one pathway to another) and possible lessons learned, with a short open question to finish (what other topics might be of interest when finalizing the scenarios). A final plenary was dedicated to sharing insights across the breakout groups, and the co-generation of overall lessons learned. More details can be found in the workshop report ([citation](#)). The key lessons learned in relation to the quantification of the pathways, as well as the way we built on those in this report, are summarized in App-Table 7.

Another insight from the workshop discussion was related to the preliminary result that in some transformation pathways (if not all), large risks for producers (e.g., losses in value added, production and employment) are expected. This was perceived as sensible, and needs to be viewed from the negative impacts of the status-quo. These sectors have harmed biodiversity, with negative impacts on some livelihoods, and there seem to be no long-term benefit in collectively staying in such a model. Dealing with the adverse consequences of a transition for producers (e.g., supporting transition to more sustainable forms of production and to alternative sources of livelihood) is essential for a transformation to occur. This was mentioned in the lessons learned section.

App-Table 7 Lesson learned discussed in WP5 workshop, in relation to pathway quantification.

Topic	Description	How it was addressed
<p>Need for a more dynamic view on how actors might act in a transformation trajectory</p>	<p>There is a strong interest for the identification of small steps at a relatively detailed human agency level, and for moving beyond the consideration of multiple perspectives as separate pathways that do not interact, towards blended and interacting transformation action pathways. This requires a novel type of model and scenario applications, likely to support a further understanding of transformations.</p>	<p>This was mentioned as a potential follow-up work in the lessons learned section of this document (4.3.4)</p>
<p>Need for a more comprehensive modeling of the impacts from the business-as-usual and the transformation pathways on nature contributions to people</p>	<p>There is a strong interest in understanding better the implications of nature degradation, and the benefits of reversing this loss, at a very detailed level. This entails for example the many provisioning, regulating and cultural ecosystem services, for which the lack of robust estimates prevents a thorough understanding of the impacts of the various scenarios on actors. Some aspects of it have been covered in the pathway quantification, but it remains partial. This requires additional modeling developments.</p>	<p>This was mentioned as a limit when discussing the pathway results, and mentioned in the lessons learned section of the document (4.3.3).</p>